
Adoption of E-Commerce in Nigerian Supermarkets

**A Thesis Presented to the School of Business and Creative
Industries**

BY

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Abstract

Many business organisations employ e-commerce to enhance their business performance and increase their profitability in the current global competitive environment. Most supermarket chains in developed countries have advanced in their adoption levels of this 21st-century imperative business model, but the adoption levels among supermarket chains in Nigeria and other developing countries still fall below expectation. Also, the sustainability of adoption appears to be problematic for some early adopters within the supermarket industry.

Although a vast literature exists on the adoption of e-commerce in developed as well as in developing countries, those of developing countries are majorly on SMEs. Therefore, this study considers e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains, exploring the current levels of adoption, benefits of adoption, and challenges to adoption. It further seeks to devise measures to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability among supermarket chains. To achieve these objectives, a conceptual framework based on the integration of the Technology-Organisation-Environment framework with the Diffusion of Innovation theory was developed.

The study employs a mixed research method quantitative dominant. One hundred and sixty-six valid questionnaires provided data for quantitative analysis. Fifteen semi-structured interviews provided qualitative data which supported the findings from the quantitative study. Descriptive analysis was used to explain participants' demographic profile, the current e-commerce adoption level and adoption benefits, while multinomial logistic regression was employed to examine the eight proposed hypotheses based on the factors affecting e-commerce adoption.

The research findings reveal that there are three active levels of e-commerce adoption within Nigerian supermarket chains. These three active levels include the e-interactivity, the e-transaction, and the e-enterprise levels, with the e-interactivity level as the dominant level of adoption (72.3%). The top six e-commerce adoption benefits were found to include creating new channels for advertising, enhancing competitive advantage, improving customer services and satisfaction, growing customer base, improving sales and revenue, and extending market reach. The multinomial logistic regression result shows that relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support, managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, and government support were significant predictors with positive influence on the adoption levels of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains. Top government support and government support were the most influential factors as they were both significant in differentiating between e-transaction and e-interactivity levels, and between e-enterprise and

e-interactivity levels of adoption. The other four factors were able to differentiate only between e-transaction and e-interactivity levels, whereas market environment pressure was found to be insignificant in differentiating between any two levels of adoption. Addressing security concerns regarding online transactions is at the top of the list of measures recommended for improving e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains.

The findings have implications for public policymakers, IT vendors, and supermarket chains. The study recommends that public policymakers should employ the findings of this study in making policies and legislations that will improve e-commerce adoption levels and sustainability, not only within the supermarket chains but across many sectors in Nigeria. The need for improving e-commerce and its sustainability in Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized as it is a vibrant source of e-economic growth which can significantly add to the country's GDP. For the IT vendors and e-commerce consultants, it is recommended that they employ the findings of this study to design and develop strategies for a sustainable high level of e-commerce adoption for the supermarket chains in Nigeria. Furthermore, it is recommended that the decision-makers in the supermarkets should employ the framework provided by this study to evaluate their current level of e-commerce adoption and develop a roadmap and strategy to improve their adoption levels for better benefits.

By providing a comprehensive knowledge of the current level of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains, the adoption benefits, factors affecting adoption levels and a framework for a sustainable higher level of adoption, this study has made a significant contribution to both theory and practice. The findings of this study can also be applied in improving e-commerce adoption in supermarket chains in other developing countries.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

E-commerce is a very significant innovation of recent time which has brought a remarkable change in the way of conducting business across the globe, providing more efficient and effective way of carrying out business transactions for both the vendors and buyers (Nacar and Ozdemir, 2022). According to Burt and Sparks (2003), e-commerce has the ability to transform the way business is done, particularly in the distribution and retail sector, and is defined as a process of development that facilitates, using technology, the restructuring of the prevailing channel and business connections, and presents the opportunity for expanding the scope of operations. Similarly, Dussart (2000, cited in Burt and Sparks, 2003, p. 276) reasoned that the business world will be revolutionised by e-commerce adoption with eight interconnected factors: “re-vamping management, re-storing control, re-launching the economy, re-configuring offers, re-structuring markets, re-distributing power, re-defining relationships and re-organising channels”. Xing, Grant, McKinnon and Fernie (2011) suggest that e-commerce growth has changed market requisites, with traditional retail outlets being prompted to reconsider their supply chains for multi-channel retailing, and businesses impelled to redesign their distribution framework to suit the evolving market needs.

Business organisations worldwide are embracing e-commerce to enhance their business performance in the current global competitive environment (Kleisiari, Duquenne and Vlontzos, 2021). According to the Centre for Retail Research, high street stores in the UK decreased from 600,000 stores in 1950 to 290,000 stores in 2012, while e-commerce and home delivery uptake has risen exponentially within the same period, and the number of the stores could fall to 220,000 by 2020, with a possibility of more 100,000 decline by 2030 (Lasisi, 2018). Global e-commerce sales grew from 1.34 trillion USD in 2014 to 4.94 trillion USD in 2021 as shown in Figure 1 and is projected to grow by 50% in the next four years, rising to \$7.39 trillion by 2025 (Chevalier, 2022).

Figure 1: Global e-commerce sales from 2014 to 2025

Source: Chevalier (2022)

Researchers like Kurnia and Peng (2018), Rahayu (2015), Xu and Quaddus (2009) and Alrawi (2007) have shown that e-commerce improves the performance of business organisations by, not only improving its efficiency, but also improving its effectiveness. In fact, e-commerce helps to reduce transaction costs, maximise productivity gain through the facilitation of electronic business transactions, expediting automatic product identification, and facilitate information sharing within the same industry and across different ones. The ability of the internet to facilitate digitisation of record keeping, its networking capability and rapid information dissemination has enhanced responsiveness and flexibility and equally fostered novel and more resourceful intermediaries. Previous studies suggest that e-commerce has improved market access, promoted outsourcing, reduced operating costs, enhanced internal coordination, and decreased time spent to market through linking of orders to products (Almunawar, Auzzali, Oseli and Ariff, 2022; Kareem, Owomoyela and Oyebamiji, 2014; Duan, Deng and Corbitt, 2012).

E-commerce has been rapidly adopted by business organisations globally due to its potentials in this globalisation era (Kwadwo et al., 2016; Gibbs and Kraemer, 2004; Andersen, Bjorn-Anderson and Dedrick, 2003). There is consensus in the literature that e-commerce is advancing and has brought tremendous changes in the traditional modes of business

transactions (Nacar and Ozdemir, 2022; Kwadwo, Martinson, Evans and Esther, 2016; Terzi, 2011). It helps to bridge the digital gap that exists between the developed countries and the developing ones, by enhancing the latter's access to knowledge, information, and expertise, and facilitating extension of supply chain for business organisations around the world and enabling them to engage in global trading effectively and efficiently notwithstanding their geographical locations (Kurnia and Peng, 2018). Nonetheless, e-commerce is faced with several challenges which still impact its adoption and continued use by both businesses and consumers. These challenges which can be categorised into economic, technological, social, and legal are the challenges facing ecommerce in the contemporary crowded online marketplace according to many industry analysts (Rakuten, 2019). According to Lippert and Govindarajulu (2006), the success of e-commerce adoption in any enterprise is underpinned by the customers' understanding and the technology characteristics of the system. However, in any organisation, the decision to adopt e-commerce is subject to numerous complex and usually interconnected stakeholders in the organisation's environment which include the business associates, suppliers, rivals, customers, and government regulations (Yaseen, 2017).

Past studies have shown that e-commerce is extensively employed by many business organisations in the developed countries like the US, the UK, and Australia (Pobee, 2021), and has gained a remarkable rate of adoption by business organisations in the transitional countries like China and Brazil (Tan and Ludwig, 2016; Tan, Tyler and Manica, 2007). The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) posited that the developed countries accounted for 95% of e-commerce trades while Latin America and Africa combined accounted for less than 1%. (Kurnia, 2008; UNCTAD, 2005). Modern supermarkets and grocery retailers have maintained the frontline in the adoption of e-commerce in these developed countries. According to retail analysts IGD, online grocery shopping has been found to be the fastest-growing purchase channel in the United Kingdom, both in terms of value and growth, and has doubled over the last decade (Pasquali, 2022).

In developing countries like Nigeria, the development and advance of internet technology and the increase in the number of people using internet in the country in recent years has resulted in the adoption of e-commerce by some business organisations. There is also an emergence of few new e-businesses, who offer online business and shopping services to the numerous internet users within and outside the country (Ibam, Boyinbode and Afolabi, 2018). Many of these e-businesses in Nigeria are excelling in the current global competitive environment, with

Jumia and Konga who have generated 61 million and 63.5 million US dollars, respectively, from global investors leading in Nigerian e-market (Munford, 2018). Notwithstanding that, e-commerce revolution has presented an immense opportunity for businesses enterprises and customers alike in Nigeria. However, its level of adoption is still below expectation, and is yet to reach its full potential (Yadav and Mahara, 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015; White, Afolayan and Plant, 2014). In this vein, it is concerning that the number of people involved in e-commerce activity in Nigeria is still not proportionate to the population size, and notwithstanding that, the country had 84 million (over 38% of the population) internet users in 2022, a figure that is projected to reach 117 million (48% of the population) in 2027 (Statista, 2022). Although e-commerce adoption in Nigeria has started improving, available data indicate comparatively low level of adoption considering the level of adoption across the globe. And yet, statistics and trend forecast show immense capability for continued growth consequent to the emergence of more e-commerce websites in recent years (Abisoye, 2017).

Unlike in developed countries where the supermarkets chains have maintained the frontline in the adoption of e-commerce, Nigerian supermarkets have not fully embraced this innovation, notwithstanding the recent rapid growth experienced in the industry due to the expansion of foreign supermarket chains like Shoprite and Spar into the country. A 40-billion-dollar growth opportunity has been estimated in Nigerian food and consumer goods between 2008 and 2020, the highest of any nation in Africa (Fiorini et al., 2018). Retail space in Nigeria has increased from 30,000 sqm in 2005 to 326,958 sqm in 2017, growing from just two shopping malls (The Ceddi Plaza in Abuja and the Palms Lekki Mall in Lagos) in 2013 to now several malls such as the Ikeja City Mall and Maryland Mall in Lagos and the Jabi Lake Mall in Abuja among others in Ilorin, Port Harcourt, Onitsha and Owerri (Olutuyi, 2018). Despite these positives, the supermarket industry in the country is still yet to fully harness the potentials of e-commerce adoption like their counterparts in the developed countries.

This study, therefore, considers other literature to explore the adoption and sustainable use of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarkets. Many scholars have made considerable effort to understand the influencing factors on e-commerce adoption in Nigeria and other emerging countries (Usman and Kumar, 2021; Omotayo and Omotope, 2018; Yadav and Mahara, 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015; White et al, 2014; Molla and Licker, 2005). However, these studies were mainly focused on SMEs and the business organisations at large, creating a study gap for in depth exploration of the variables that impact e-commerce adoption in Nigerian

supermarkets chains. Hence, the researcher intends to address this knowledge gap. The study employed a mixed research methodology quantitative dominant.

1.2 Research Problem

E-commerce has become an imperative business model to apply in the 21st century, bringing opportunities as well as some dimensional challenges, like more complex, more dynamic, and more competitive business environment (Yaseen, 2017; Jaradat and Faqih., 2014). As a result, e-commerce impacts upon how business is conducted, and has been known to often lead to rapid growth in trade, improved effectiveness and efficiency, market expansion and economic growth. In developed countries, this mode of commerce has been fully embraced in the supermarket industry, and individual supermarkets have employed the prospects of e-commerce to improve their operational performance. However, in developing countries like Nigeria, the potentials of e-commerce have not been fully harnessed though there is evidence of growth in the industry due to the expansion of foreign giant supermarkets like Shoprite and Spar. Hitherto, only few online supermarkets operate in Nigeria (Ndiomewese, 2018). In this vein, knowledge of the critical success factors for implementation of e-commerce is crucial for business competitiveness and sustainability. Studies suggest that failure to implement e-commerce strategies may have adverse effects on business performance (Kareem et al, 2014). And yet, there is still relatively low e-commerce adoption level in Nigerian supermarket chains.

Previous studies have focused more on e-commerce and ICT adoption by Nigerian businesses, especially in the SMEs (Ali, Usman, Kachalla and Ali, 2021; Igwe, Alaba and Abass, 2021; Yadav and Mahara, 2018; White, et al., 2014). However, e-commerce studies in the context of Nigerian supermarkets are limited, with the available few focussed on the e-commerce benefits (Kareem et al., 2014). Hence this research seeks to contribute to this knowledge gap by conducting a comprehensive study on e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains, investigating the extent of adoption, exploring the adoption benefits and factors affecting the adoption levels. The study equally seeks to develop a framework that will help to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability among supermarket chains. The proposed framework can also be adopted by supermarket chains in other developing countries.

1.3 Research Purpose

Despite an extensive application of advanced level of e-commerce in supermarket chains in developed countries, the extent of application of the e-commerce business model among supermarket chains in Nigeria and other emerging countries is comparatively low. Concerns

have also been raised about the sustainability of advanced level of e-commerce within the supermarkets in Nigeria (Omotayo and Omotope, 2018).

Despite the comparative low application of advanced level of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains, and the sustainability problems surrounding the application of advanced level of e-commerce, there is still a dearth of studies that explore the factors that influence the extent of application of this business model. Hence, there is a need to develop guidelines that can help to improve e-commerce application, adoption, and sustainability within supermarkets. The few available related studies to e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarkets either focused on the impact of adoption on business performance (Kareem et al., 2014) or the determinants of consumers intention to continue to use online shops in general, without focussing on the supermarket chains (Usman and Kumar, 2021; Omotayo and Omotope, 2018).

Therefore, this study aims to address this knowledge gap. This will be achieved by conducting a holistic study on the adoption of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains. In this sense, the study investigates factors that affect the extent of application of e-commerce, and then develops some guidelines that can be used to help supermarkets improve e-commerce application levels and sustainability.

1.3.1 Research Objectives

Based on the established aim of this study, the following objectives have been set for the research.

1. To examine the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains
2. To analyse the benefits of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains
3. To examine the factors that affect the extent of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains
4. To develop measures to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains.

1.3.2 Research Questions

Based on the stated research objectives, this study seeks to answer the following research questions.

1. What is the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains?
2. How beneficial is e-commerce adoption to Nigerian supermarket chains?
3. What factors affect the extent of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains?
4. How can e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains be improved?

1.3.3 Research Hypotheses

Eight hypotheses are proposed for examination in this study. These hypotheses are developed in line with the conceptual framework for this study, which is underpinned by the Technology-Organisation-Environment framework and Diffusion of Innovation theory. The development of these hypotheses is discussed in detail with the conceptual framework in section 3.7. The hypotheses are outlined as follows:

H1: Relative advantage has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H2: Compatibility has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H3: Technology readiness has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H4: Financial barrier has a negative and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H5: Top management support has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H6: Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H7: Market environment pressure has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H8: Government and vendor support has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application of in Nigerian supermarket chains.

1.4 Rationale for Study

Several studies have been carried out on e-commerce adoption. These studies offer perspectives from the point of view of developed countries (Van Droogenbroeck and Van Hove, 2021; Abebe, 2014; Sila, 2013; Duan et al., 2012; Li and Yousept, 2004), transitional countries (Tan and Ludwig, 2016; Tan, Tyler and Manica, 2007), and in developing countries (Al-Ayed, 2022; Ariansyah, Sirait, Nugroho, and Suryanegara, 2021; Yadav and Mahara, 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015). However, relatively few studies focus on e-commerce adoption among supermarkets in developing countries (Lu and Reardon, 2018; Kurnia, Choudrie, Mahbubur and Alzougool, 2015; Kareem et al., 2014).

Whilst studies on e-commerce started in the 1990s, the issue of e-commerce is still a contemporary interesting topic of study. Most of the e-commerce studies conducted between 1990 and 2008 were in developed countries. A comprehensive review of 345 IT innovation related studies published between 1985 and 2007 in 19 peer-reviewed journals revealed that over 82% of the studies were carried out in advanced countries with few or no studies in emerging countries (Rahayu, 2015; Williams, Dwivedi, Lal and Schwarz, 2009). This is not surprising because e-commerce adoption was concentrated in the advanced countries as 95% of e-commerce activities was taking place in developed countries (UNCTAD, 2005). Nevertheless, e-commerce studies in developing countries only started in the past few years. However, these studies were mainly either generalised for business organisations or focused on SMEs, with limited studies in the supermarket/grocery industry which is usually in the frontline of e-commerce uptake in countries with developed economies.

Although few e-commerce studies have been conducted within the supermarket industry in some developed and transitional countries, however, differences exist, not just between countries with developed and developing economies, but even amongst the developed and the developing ones. These differences exist from an economic, environmental, political, cultural, and social points of view, and impact upon e-commerce adoption. The differences are more pronounced between developing and developed nations. For instance, business organisations in developed nations have access to comparatively high-quality internet infrastructure, human resources, and stable governments than their counterparts in emerging nations (Molla and Licker, 2005). According to Kurnia (2008), about 3% of Africans could access internet in 2004, compared to 67% of North Americans that had access to the internet in the same year (Kurnia, 2008). This explains the divide existing between developing and developed nations. These differences influence technological applications as well as the application of e-commerce strategies, frameworks, or innovative business models. Technologies, strategies, frameworks, or model developed in certain circumstances, for instance in developed nation, cannot be suitably applied directly in a developing nation. Adjustments will need to be made according to the conditions of any nation before they could be applied therein.

Differences also exist among the developing nations in terms of political conditions, economic and sociocultural factors. For instance, in Arab countries (Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Saudi Arabia, and Sudan), people were found to have preference for face-to-face market dealing over the use of certain technological interface as the former enables them to create family-like

environment in their business activities. This inclination to such beliefs has made their response to technological advancement slower than in other countries (Yaseen, 2017; Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2013). Furthermore, the level of governmental support, technology readiness and competition also vary even among developing nations. Therefore, research findings from a given emerging nation may not be applicable in other emerging nations. Zhu and Kraemer (2005) reported that changes in political, environmental, social, and cultural dimensions can significantly impact the degree of diffusion of technology innovation over nations. Therefore, the level of IT innovations employed by business organisations vary across the developed countries and developing countries, even more between the developed and developing countries (Yaseen, 2017; Zhu and Kraemer, 2005).

Extant studies on adoption of e-commerce in supermarket industry were mainly conducted in developed, and transitional countries, with limited studies in developing nations. In the case of Nigeria, limited studies are available on e-commerce uptake by Nigerian supermarkets and these few studies are mostly focused on the impact of adoption on business performance with little or no interest on the factors affecting the adoption and measures to improve adoption levels and sustainability. This study, thereby, seeks to address this research gap by investigating the factors that affect the extent of application of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains, and explore the measures to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability.

1.5 Overview of the Methodology

Based on the insights from the initial review of the literature, a mixed (quantitative and qualitative) research method was considered suitable for this research to effectively achieve the aim of this study. The ‘QUAN → qual’ concurrent mixed method research design was adopted, where qualitative study was conducted to further interpret and consolidate the findings from the quantitative study. This helped to offset the limitations in each of the two methods (quantitative and qualitative), and to satisfactorily address all the research objectives. A theoretical framework was built following a systematic review of the literature. Quantitative data was collected to obtain a general knowledge of the extent of use of e-commerce and its post adoption benefits as well as the factors that affect its adoption levels in Nigerian supermarket chains. A qualitative study was then conducted to gain an in-depth understanding of the quantitative data, and to answer the research questions more comprehensively. This approach helped to triangulate the findings and develop more comprehensive measures that can be used to improve e-commerce adoption levels and sustainability.

Since there are 21 supermarket chains in Nigeria eligible for data collection based on number of stores and mode of operation, the entire population was considered for data collection in both the quantitative and qualitative study. In the quantitative study, 10 managers were chosen from the participating stores drawn from each of the 21 supermarket chains, generating a sample of 210 respondents for the quantitative study. In the qualitative study, a sample size of 15 participants was utilised. This is consistent with Morse (1994) who suggests that a minimum of 6 sample size is recommended for qualitative studies.

1.6 Structure of the Research

Chapter one provides the background as well as the aims and objectives of the research. It further presents the rationale for the research in addition to the structure of the research and an overview of the research method. The literature review has three major sections: theoretical, conceptual, and contextual reviews. Theoretical and conceptual reviews are presented in chapter two, while the contextual review and the conceptual framework with the hypothesis development are covered in chapter three. Chapter four covers the research methods, while chapter five presents the data analysis (research findings). Chapter six presents the discussion of the research findings, and chapter seven covers the conclusions, recommendations, suggestions for future studies, and research contributions. The next chapter critically reviews the literature.

CHAPTER 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction to Literature Review

The literature review is divided into three major parts, that is, theoretical, conceptual, and contextual reviews underpinning the study, as illustrated in figure 2. The theoretical and contextual parts are discussed in this Chapter 2, while the conceptual part of the literature review is discussed in Chapter 3. Development of hypothesis and the conceptual framework are further discussed in Chapter 3.

Figure 2: Literature review breakdown

Source: Researcher

2.1 Overview of E-commerce

E-commerce is a system that enables buying and selling online with a key aim of offering a convenience way of shopping that does not involve a visit to a physical store by an individual (Salamai, Ageeli and El-kenawy, 2022). Due to the Covid-19 outbreak, which has overturned the norm in the retail industry, e-commerce growth has accelerated rapidly in 2021 (Villa and Monzón, 2021).

2.1.1 E-Commerce Definition

E-commerce has been diversely defined by different researchers, with some defining it exclusively as online marketing while, some define it to imply application of ICT in the conduction of daily business transactions. For instance, Kareem et al. (2014) referred e-commerce as the process of buying, selling, and marketing goods and services to customers using communications technology especially the internet. Similarly, Kwadwo et al. (2016), defined e-commerce as the process of conducting transactions via internet protocol-based networks or through computer-mediated networks. They further suggest that e-commerce include various forms of commercial transactions, or businesses that require the use of internet

to transfer information. This involves valuable data and information exchanges in the form of goods or services in addition to payments using web-based technologies.

Morri and Siege (2003, cited in Ikemelu, 2012, p. 172) defined e-commerce as “commercial transaction of services in an electronic format”. On the other hand, Chong (2008) defines e-commerce as a process of integrating all activities, processes, and services of a company towards information and products trading, as well as funds exchange with partners of the company using electronic technologies and computer networks. The most comprehensive definition of e-commerce which represents the views of many researchers and economists was given by Rolf Wigand (1997). He argued that e-commerce entails more than just the application of technology. According to Wigand (1997, p. 5),

“Electronic commerce denotes the seamless application of information and communication technology from its point of origin to its endpoint along the entire value chain of business processes conducted electronically and designed to enable the accomplishment of a business goal. These processes may be partial or complete and may encompass business-to-business as well as business-to-consumer and consumer-to-business transactions” (Wigand, 1997, p. 5).

2.1.2 Various E-Commerce Types

There are many classes of e-commerce, but the prominent ones that are discussed in most literatures are business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce (Ocloo et al., 2018). Sajuyigbe (2012, cited in Kareem et al., 2014) identified eight types of e-commerce as follows:

- **Business-to-business (B2B) e-commerce.** In B2B e-commerce, two or more business organisations engage in electronic business transactions.
- **Collaborative e-commerce.** In collaborative commerce, business partners, mainly along the supply chain, collaborate electronically.
- **Business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce** involves electronic transactions between a business organisation and an individual where the individual is the buyer, and the business organisation is the seller.
- **Consumers-to-businesses (C2B).** Consumer makes known a need for a specific good or service while the business organisations bid to satisfy the consumers wants.
- **Consumer-to-consumer (C2C) e-commerce** is a third party facilitated electronic transactions between consumers. For instance, an auction site in which a consumer lists

a product online for sale and other shoppers bargain to buy it. The third party which provides the platform (website) for matching the consumers generally charges a commission or flat fee.

- **Intra-business (intra-organizational) e-commerce** involves the use of electronic commerce internally by business organisations to improve their operations. A special case of intra-business commerce is a business-to-employee (B2E) ecommerce where a company uses an intra-business network to provide products and services its employees.
- **Government-to-citizens (G2C) and to others.** This involves provision of services to citizens by the government using e-commerce technologies. Government can also do business with businesses (G2B) and with other governments (G2G).
- **Mobile commerce (m-commerce).** This is another type of e-commerce which involves accessing the internet for business transactions in a wireless environment using the mobile phone.

This study is guided by these understandings of e-commerce with the intention of unpacking factors that affect the extent of application of e-commerce and positioning the study more strongly within on-going scholarly debates.

2.2 E-Commerce Perspectives

Ecommerce development rate varies in different countries with the developed countries leading in the race while most emerging nations are still falling behind. Hence, understanding the utilisation of e-commerce in both developing and developed countries is of importance.

2.2.1 E-Commerce in Developed Countries

The high level of internet usage in developed countries has facilitated the growth of e-commerce as businesses and individuals have deployed the benefit to flourish in e-commerce. Marketplace has overcome the traditional boundaries and consumers conveniently shop from anywhere and at any time with reduced cost of shopping (Khan and Uwemi, 2018; Brock and Khan, 2017). In these advanced countries, e-commerce has facilitated connection between people, nations and organisations that make it possible for them to function more effectively, leading to greater business opportunities and technological improvement for organisations (Dhingra and Dhingra, 2013). This has led to an increase in productivity and improved effectiveness, thereby enabling businesses to better manage their transactions, operational costs, and consequently to improve their profitability (Khan and Uwemi, 2018; Khan and Awan, 2017).

E-commerce in developed nations has become increasingly important in all market sectors, and it accounts for a significant proportion of total trade in some sectors. Regarding turnover, the European market is leading in e-commerce globally. A European e-commerce report revealed that the European market was ahead of US market in 2010 (Jędrzejczak-Gas, Barska and Siničáková, 2019). According to Yongen and Weening (2013, cited in Jędrzejczak-Gas et al., 2019, p. 209), growth in e-commerce revenues was in the range of 10-15% in Norway, Sweden and UK, while it was observed to fluctuate around 20-25% in France, Germany, Spain and Italy. However, Southern and Eastern European countries were recorded to have the largest increases, with their growth rates ranging from 30% - 40% per year. The top in this group list were Russia, Ukraine, Poland, and Greece (Jędrzejczak-Gas et al., 2019). A more recent report shows that over 40 percent of UK shoppers bought groceries online in 2021, although, the Covid-19 crisis may have contributed to the high volume of online shoppers as online shopping is safer than a visit to the physical shops (Tighe, 2021). However, online shopping was already on the increase before covid-19. In fact, Health Information Management (HIM) online grocery market research found that about 34% of UK shoppers were already buying groceries online as far back as 2016, which was four years before the Covid-19 pandemic (Lumina Intelligence, 2020). A previous study found that nearly 50% of surveyed US consumers buy groceries online as often as once a week (Aull, Begley, Chandra and Mathur, 2021).

2.2.2 E-Commerce in Developing Countries

Developing countries are still catching up in e-commerce development as they are quite behind (Khan and Uwemi, 2018). Previous studies suggest that developing countries tend to adapt the techniques used in more developed countries, like the UK and USA. The economies of these developed countries are well supported with advanced infrastructural developments, and have a competitive advantage achieved through low-cost access to wider markets (Khan and Uwemi, 2018; Khan, Omonaiye and Madhavi Lalitha, 2017). On the contrary, developing countries lack the support, and advanced infrastructural development. For instance, there is poor internet infrastructure in many developing countries, and this has adverse effects on the adoption of the e-commerce business model. Yet, e-commerce uptake in emerging countries has the potential to create opportunities for businesses in developing countries, with the potential of opening up access to national as well as international markets. Notwithstanding the apparent benefits of e-commerce enjoyed by businesses in developed countries, there is evidence to suggest that a low level of e-commerce uptake persist in emerging countries due to certain challenges (Das and Khan, 2016). Hasan and Mardhani (2021) found a low level of e-commerce application

among Indonesian SMEs. Also, a study conducted in Saudi Arabia by Al-Somali, Gholami and Clegg (2015) found that the adoption level of e-commerce in large and small businesses is still low. Among the 201 businesses (67.3% large and 32.7% small businesses) that participated in the study, 19.8% were still at the e-connectivity level, 16.8% at the e-window level, 32.7% at e-interactivity level, 6.4% at e-transaction level, and 24.3% at e-enterprise level. The challenges that lead to this low e-commerce adoption need to be addressed to enable organisations in the developing countries to fully benefit from e-commerce (Khan and Uwemi, 2018). This understanding warrants a critical review of the theories underpinning the adoption of e-commerce.

2.3 Theories Underpinning E-commerce Adoption Studies

Since the commercialisation of the internet in the 1990s, many parties, including scholars, have expressed interest in e-commerce. This is due to e-commerce's eight unique features which include: global reach, ubiquity, interactivity, richness, universally standard, customisation, social technology, and information density. It is considered more powerful than other technological instruments because of these distinguishing characteristics (Laudon and Traver, 2014).

Researchers have conducted numerous studies regarding e-commerce technology, and different theoretical frameworks and models have been developed or employed in these studies. Six theories amongst others have been widely applied in these studies and they include: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), Diffusion of Innovation (DoI) theory, Perceived E-Readiness Model (PERM), Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) Framework, and Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions theory. The following subsections delve into these theories in further depth.

2.3.1 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) originally developed TRA in social psychology to explain the determining factors that cause individuals to exhibit some behaviours, particularly, those behaviours that are volitional in nature. This theory assumes that an individual's conduct is based on their intents to exhibit certain behaviours, and this intent is in turn jointly influenced by two factors including their subjective norm and their attitude toward behaviour (Rahayu, 2015). According to Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), *attitude toward behaviour* is defined as the feelings, pleasant or unpleasant, an individual has in relation to exhibition of a specific behaviour, while *subjective norm* is the person's perspective of the opinions of the individuals that matter most to him, whether they think it is okay for him to perform the behaviour or not.

Consequently, the individual's attitude towards the concerned action is guided by their core values which are occasioned by their assessment of consequences of such behaviour. The subjective norm is prompted by the summation of their normative beliefs, which include their perceived expectations by certain persons or groups of people, and the individual's inspiration to fulfil those expectations (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989). The connection between all the determinant factors in the TRA were described by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) as illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3: Theory of Reasoned Action

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*. Boston: Addison-Wesley.

Adapted from Fishbein and Ajzen (1975, p. 16)

TRA assumes that the more someone believes that a certain action would make positive impact on him/her, the more he/she desires and would be encouraged to exhibit such behaviours, and the more likely he/she would do so. Also, the greater pressure someone feels from their social environment about complying to a certain behaviour, the stronger would be the intention to perform the concerned behaviour.

TRA is not limited to any behaviour (Rahayu, 2015; Davis et al., 1989). Therefore, it has been employed in different situations including technology adoption studies (Ebardo, Padagas and Tuazon, 2021; Gultom, 2020; Xiao, 2020). However, TRA has been successful in the explanation and prediction of behaviours across these situations. Notwithstanding that, the TRA model has been successfully employed in different fields. Regardless, the TRA model has been subjected to criticism due to several reasons. For instance, Ajzen (1991) posited that the model does not work well in a scenario where the individual's behaviour is not volitional, such as in habitual, spontaneous, mindless, or impulsive behaviour. This is because logical reasoning may not be required to be followed in such behaviours (Rahayu, 2015). Also, the theory lacks the capacity to explain some behaviours that require some expertise, event, resources, or require cooperation with another party (Alrousan, 2014). Therefore, researchers that investigate human behaviour using TRA must take individual's salient belief into

consideration since TRA is unable to explain certain individual behaviours that are significantly influenced by their beliefs (Alrouسان, 2014). Furthermore, TRA is more useful in predicting behaviours instead of the outcome of the individual’s behaviours (Alrouسان, 2014; Yousafzai, Foxall and Pallister, 2010). Another criticism is that TRA has a limited predictive power when employed in a situation with high correlation between the actual behaviour and intention (Yousafzai et al., 2010).

2.3.2 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) can be considered as an extension of TRA and was developed by Ajzen in 1991. Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) was added to TRA, as illustrated in figure 4, with the intention of addressing some of the limitations cited in section 2.3.1.

Figure 4: Theory of planned behaviour

Adapted from Ajzen (1991)

PBC refers to individuals’ perception of the difficulty or the ease of performing a given behaviour, and it influences their intention to perform the behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). As illustrated in figure 4, behaviour is influenced by the intention to perform it and the perceived behavioural control (Rahayu, 2015).

In addition to having a direct impact on behaviour in this model, the intention is also presumed to be influenced by PBC. Hence, the intention to perform a certain behaviour in this theory is subject to three determinants: *attitude toward the behaviour*, *subjective norm*, and *perceived*

behavioural control. Just like in TRA, the attitude toward behaviour is subject to the individual's behavioural beliefs, while the subjective norm is subject to the individual's normative belief. However, the PBC in TPB is driven by the control beliefs of the individual regarding their ability (opportunities and resources at their disposal) to exhibit the behaviour as well as each factor's ability to discourage or encourage the behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). This is further elaborated in figure 5.

Figure 5: Elaboration of theory of planned behaviour

Adapted from Rahayu (2015)

In addition to providing a conceptual framework validated by empirical studies, TPB also has a well-founded procedure for measuring the social-psychological constructs that constitute the theory (Sok, Borges, Schmidt and Ajzen, 2021). It has been applied in ICT and e-commerce adoption studies to explain and predict behavioural intention. For instance, TPB was used by Harrison, Mykytyn and Riemenschneider (1997) to examine IT adoption among small businesses' decision makers. They found that the process of making decisions on technology adoption was strongly impacted by subjective norm, perceived behavioural control and attitude towards technology. Also, Riemenschneider and McKinney (2001, cited in Alrousan, 2014), used TBP in their study to explore the behaviours of decision-makers regarding e-commerce uptake by SMEs. They discovered that attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control are all significant determinants of adoption decision. In another study on the impact of e-commerce on SMEs in emerging countries Chile as a case study, Nasco, Grandón and Mykytyn (2008) discovered that subjective norm and attitude constructs were very significant in establishing the level of e-commerce application in SMEs in Chile, while the PBC construct was not.

In a more recent study, Mishra (2014) used TPB in a study of acceptance behaviour of users towards mobile commerce in India. The study's findings demonstrated that attitude and perceived behavioural control have reasonable impact on the prediction of person's intention to use mobile commerce, whereas subjective norm's impact was insignificant. Thus, the TBP model has been proven useful and valid in the study of various forms of technology adoption. In fact, it was found in many studies to be more efficient and comprehensive than TRA in predicting behaviours concerning innovation of technology (Alrousan, 2014; Venkatesh, Morris, Davis and Davis, 2003).

Nevertheless, TPB has some shortcomings in predicting intentions, based on individual behaviours, towards the adoption of IT. Firstly, the TPB, just like TRA, is more useful in predicting the behaviour of individuals rather than the outcome of their behaviour (Alrousan, 2014). Secondly, only one predictor is added in TPB, and ongoing evidence has shown that these antecedents alone are not the only determinants of behavioural intention, but TPB's predictive power in explaining the adoption of technology can be boosted by addition of other factors (Rahayu, 2015; Alrousan, 2014).

2.3.3 Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was adapted from the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and was originally developed by Davis (1989). TAM is one of the models most extensively employed in explaining user acceptance behaviour (Ma and Liu, 2004). It is used in the determination and prediction of factors that impact users' decision to accept or reject technology innovation (Alrousan, 2014). As illustrated in figure 6, TAM is similar to TRA. However, External Variables, Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use were introduced in TAM, while the subjective norm that was in TRA was removed as it was considered insignificant in technology adoption scenarios (Davis, 1989). TAM theory presents Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use as the main factors that influence ICT acceptance and use.

Figure 6: Technology Acceptance Model

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information Technology. *MIS Quarterly*

Adapted from Davis (1989)

Just like in TRA, TAM alleges that the actual behaviour (actual usage) is very much dependent on behavioural intention (intention to use). Nevertheless, the behavioural intention in TAM is determined by *attitude toward usage* (A) as well as *perceived usefulness* (U). Furthermore, the theory postulates that *attitude toward usage* (A) is in turn affected by both *perceived usefulness* and *perceived ease of use* (Rahayu, 2015). While *perceived usefulness* refers to how much an individual believes that the use of a particular technology would enhance their job performance, *perceived ease of use* refers to how easy the person believes the use of that technology would be (Rahayu, 2015; Davis, 1989). There is a shared understanding that *perceived usefulness* is influenced by *perceived ease of use* as well as *external influences*.

A TAM model study conducted by Davis (1989) on word processor technology acceptance found that perceived usefulness has more substantial impact on an individual's intention to use technology than perceived ease of use. It was found that a person would more likely use a technological application irrespective of the ease or difficulty related to the use of the system as long as his or her productivity and job performance would be improved using the system. Nevertheless, this should not be seen as an indication that perceived ease of use does not impact intention to use a particular technology, rather it makes less substantial impact, and should not be overruled as a construct affecting individuals' decision to adopt IT systems (Alrousan, 2014).

Nevertheless, the original TAM only emphasises on an individual without considering environmental and social factors impact on acceptance of technology. Hence, Venkatesh and Davis (2000) extended the model to TAM2 (Figure 7) to incorporate other variables and account for the significant function of subjective norms. As illustrated in figure 7, more

antecedent variables that explain and determine perceived usefulness have been added in TAM 2. These antecedent variables can be categorised into cognitive instrumental processes and social influence. The cognitive instrumental processes include Demonstrability, Output Quality and Job Relevance, while social influence include Voluntariness, Subjective Norms, and Image. Venkatesh and Davis (2000), in a longitudinal study, found TAM2 applicable which had strong affirmation with 60% variance. Cognitive Instrumental Processes and Social Influence were also found to be consistent with TAM 2. Subjective Norms was found to have significant impact on perceived usefulness, when applied in a mandatory scenario. However, the result is not the same when applied in a voluntary setting (Alrousan, 2014).

Figure 7: TAM 2 model

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. D. (2000). A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science*, (46), pp.186-204.

Adopted from Venkatesh and Davis (2000)

Figure 8: TAM 3 model

Adopted from Venkatesh and Bala (2008), reproduced with permission from John Wiley and Sons.

TAM has been further expanded by Venkatesh and Bala (2008) to TAM 3 by the addition of antecedent variables to the Perceived Ease of Use construct, as illustrated in figure 8. The newly added antecedent constructs to the Perceived Ease of Use are grouped into Adjustment and Anchors. While the Adjustment group includes Objective Usability and Perceived Enjoyment, the Anchors group includes computer playfulness, Computer Anxiety, Perception of External Control, and Computer Self-Efficacy. The controls in Adjustment group reflects on individual perception towards system usability, while those in Anchors group reflects level of individual's beliefs towards the use of computer (Alrousan, 2014).

Notwithstanding the expansion and upgrading of TAM to TAM 2 and subsequently to TAM 3 by different researchers, the original TAM remains valid, and is still among the most widely used models in explaining individual's behaviour towards technology adoption. Since the model was specially developed to explain computer technology acceptance behaviour of individuals, it has been applied in several IT studies including acceptance of ICT by university students (Ismael and Ali, 2021), e-procurement system adoption (Aboelmaged, 2010), e-

learning (Park, 2009; Al-Adwan, Al- Adwan and Smedley, 2013), internet banking study (Yousafzai et al., 2010), internet purchasing studies (Olson and Boyer, 2003), ICTs and e-commerce adoption studies (Luu, Nguyen and Dao, 2022; Suryawirawan, 2021; Yusoff et al., 2021; Grandon and Pearson, 2004) and intranet study (Alam, 2009) among others.

This extensive use of TAM in technology adoption studies has been attributed to its inherent advantages (Yousafzai et al., 2010). It was found to possess a superior predictive power and more adequate in explaining technology acceptance and employment among diverse user population within a varying cultural and organisational contexts and levels of expertise than TPB and TRA. Also, it has a robust theoretical framework and a well-grounded valid scale for measurement, which makes it operationally appealing to use. Furthermore, its overall power of explanation has accrued a robust empirical support (Rahayu, 2015; Alrousan, 2014; Yousafzai et al., 2010; Szajna, 1994).

Despite the advantages of TAM, it has been criticised in several studies for some limitations. It has been alleged to provide only a generalised information on system user opinions, without providing information on the formation process of such perceptions or how to manipulate the perceptions to make the system more acceptable. (Yousafzai et al., 2010). Szajna (1996) was worried about the validity of TAM as its constructs were alleged to have discriminant validity. This is because all the constructs in TAM are measured by self-reported measurements. According to Straub, Limayem and Karahanna-Evaristo (1995), only mere artefacts, rather than true, significant effect may be uncovered by research that depended on subjective measures for both dependent variables like system usage and independent variables like perceived usefulness. Hence, Szajna (1996) as well as Straub et al. (1995) are of the opinion that TAM has a limitation pertaining to the discriminatory nature of validity of its measures.

In addition, TAM was faulted for ignoring the effect of some crucial internal and external organisational factors like organisational size, cost, organisational culture, and environmental pressure (El-Gohary, 2012). It has also been criticised as being only useful in the study of an individual's adoption of technology, but not at organisational level, since it fails to consider the internal and external organisational factors relating to organisational adoption of technology (Alrousan, 2014; El-Gohary, 2012; Oliveira and Martins, 2011).

2.3.4 The Perceived e-Readiness Model

Molla and Licker (2005) introduced the Perceived e-Readiness model (PERM) which they developed for e-commerce uptake by business organisations in emerging nations. They

believed that challenges facing businesses in emerging nations somewhat differ from those facing their counterparts in nations with more developed economies. These differences exist in organisational as well as environmental perspectives. Therefore, a model developed for e-commerce adoption by businesses in developed countries will not be suitably applied by businesses in emerging nations.

The theoretical root of PERM was based on interactionism. Molla and Licker (2005) posited that useful predictors of e-commerce adoption in developing countries can be provided by a multi-perspective audit of the internal organisational issues, managerial issues, and external contextual issues. They put forward the perceived e-readiness concept to denote the managers' assessment of the e-commerce adoption contexts. They gave the definition of perceived e-readiness as the firm's assessment of the e-commerce situation, managerial situation, organizational situation, and external situation in making e-commerce adoption decisions. In PERM, they identified two constructs which are "Perceived Organizational E-Readiness (POER)" and "Perceived External E-Readiness (PEER)" (Figure 9). PEER indicates a firm's evaluation and assessment of imperative external environmental factors which include the e-readiness of the government, e-readiness of market forces and the e-readiness of the support industries. On the other hand, POER refers to an audit of:

- 1) the firm's view, understanding predictions of e-commerce and its possible risks and advantages (essential attributes of the innovation);
- 2) the managers' dedication (essential attributes of the managers); and
- 3) essential elements of the organisation, such as its business infrastructure, resources, and processes (essential attributes of the organisation).

POER and PEER are jointly theorized to predict the adoption of e-commerce and explain a substantial amount of the changes in the adoption levels of e-commerce in countries with developing economy (Molla and Licker, 2005).

Figure 9: Perceived e-readiness model

Adopted from Molla and Licker (2005), reproduced with permission from John Wiley and Sons

The perceived e-readiness model has been criticised for its shortcomings regarding its validity and reliability flaws, statistical analysis flaws and its non-consideration of some vital industry descriptors like firm size and employees' educational background (Tan, Tyler and Manica, 2007). Also, the PERM emphasises more on organisational characteristics without considering the individual factors' influence on e-commerce uptake. As, the owner/manager's role in decision making is known to be very influential in small businesses, thus PERM also fails to capture small business' idiosyncrasies (Parker and Castleman, 2009). Nevertheless, PERM has been successfully applied in e-commerce and other ICT studies (Pal, Singh and Dhaliwal, 2020; Farokhizadeh, Toloie Eshlaghy, Radfar and Shoja, 2019; Matsinhe and Kabanda, 2019).

2.3.5 Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) Framework

The TOE framework was originally created by Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990) to explain contextual factors of influence on innovation adoption. In TOE, there are three dimensions of firm's contexts that influence innovation technology adoption. These include organisational context, technological context and environmental (industrial) context. The technological context pertains to the internal as well as the external technologies needed by the organisation. The organisational context relates to the nature of the firm and its resources which is characterised by the firm's size, formalisation, decentralisation, and managerial structure's complexity, whereas environmental context indicates other influencing stake holders in the firm's surroundings like the government, the suppliers, and the competitors (Rahayu, 2015; Zhu, Kraemer and Xu, 2002). The TOE framework is as illustrated in figure 10.

Figure 10: TOE framework

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Tornatzky, L. G. and Fleischer, M. (1990). *The Processes of Technological Innovation*. Lexington Books (Lexington, Mass.).

Adapted from Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990)

Existing research have shown that the TOE framework has explanatory capacity and is applicable across a wide range of technological, as well as national/cultural and industrial contexts. It has been used to explain e-commerce uptake (Almunawar et al., 2022; Nurcahyo and Putra, 2021; Setiyani and Rostiani, 2021; Rawash, 2021; Oliveira and Martins, 2010), e-business (Mkansi, 2021; Zhu, Kraemer and Xu, 2006; Zhu, Kraemer, Xu and Dedrick, 2004), interorganisational system (Mishra, Konana and Barua, 2007), enterprise systems (Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo, 2009), open systems (Chau and Tam, 1997), and a wide range of general IS applications (Thong 1999). Also, TOE framework has been tested in American, European, and Asian contexts in addition to countries with developing economies (Zhu et al., 2006; Zhu and Kraemer, 2005; Zhu et al. 2003). In each of these studies, technological, organisational, and environmental elements have been found to influence a firm's means of identifying the need for searching and adopting a new technology. The TOE framework has been considered a solid theoretical underpinning for identification of factors in adoption of e-commerce (Alrousan, 2014; Oliveira and Martins, 2010).

Nevertheless, TOE has certain limitations. Its first major limitation is its inability to fully identify the managerial factors in technology adoption where the managers of SMEs are

considered the key decision makers (Hashim, 2007). Consequently, some researchers proposed expansion of TOE through addition of a fourth context that will describe the managerial factors (Bao and Sun, 2010; Sarkar, 2008; Thong, 1999). Others studied managerial factors within the context of organisation based on the reasoning that technology adoption success is important to decision makers (Alamro and Tarawneh, 2011; Scupola, 2009). As a matter of fact, different models drawn up by these researchers in their studies acknowledged that managerial factors, such as support from top management as well as the IT knowledge of the manager/owner significantly impact technology adoption, especially e-commerce uptake by SMEs.

The second limitation of TOE is lack of sufficient constructs to adequately explain adoption of technology. For instance, Iacovou, Benbasat and Dexter, (1995) devised a framework anchored on TOE in the study of the influencing factors on organisations' adoption of electronic data interchange. The model is comprised of three factors: Organisational Readiness; Perceived benefit and External Pressure, as illustrated in figure 11.

Figure 11: Iacovou et al model

Adopted from Iacovou et al. (1995)

The Iacovou et al. (1998) model differs from the TOE model in the sense that its context of Organisational Readiness combines organisational and technological factors. Also, another construct (trading partner power) which was considered an important factor in technology adoption has been introduced in the external environment context. Further, a new context (Perceived Benefit) was introduced to the model to explain the possible advantages of innovation implementation as understood by businesses. This was found to be significant (Alrousan, 2014).

2.3.6 Diffusion of Innovation Theory

The diffusion of innovation (DoI) theory, which was developed by Rogers (1983) and often referred to as the Rogers' Model is among the most applied theories in technology uptake studies. Rogers' Model was originally used to explain innovation adoption in the field of rural sociology. The application of the model has, over time, been extended by numerous researchers across diverse fields of study such as medicine, education as well as technology and industry (Alrousan, 2014). The Rogers' model is comprised of four key components pertaining to innovation diffusion process which include innovation, communication channels, time, and social system. The innovation adoption decision is neither a simple task nor a spontaneous move, but follows a procedure known as *the innovation-decision process*, as illustrated in figure 12. This process according to Rogers (2003) involves getting initial knowledge regarding the innovation, establishing an opinion regarding the innovation, deciding whether to accept or decline the innovation, putting the new idea into action, and validating the decision-making process.

Figure 12: The innovation-decision process

Adapted from Rogers (2003)

Pursuant to this theory, the first step in the innovation diffusion process is knowledge of the innovation. This knowledge occurs when the person or unit that makes the decision is informed about the availability and attributes of a certain innovation. When the knowledge of an innovation is gained, the individuals begin to develop either a positive or negative attitude towards the innovation. Rogers refers to this condition as the *persuasion* stage. The gaining of

initial knowledge of an innovation by an individual is not enough to spur the individual into making adoption decision. However, at this stage, the individual gathers information about the innovation from experts, scientific evaluations, colleagues, teachers, peers, and others to get conviction about the innovation and lower the innovation's level of uncertainty. According to Rogers (2003), as the individual's feelings come to play at this stage, the information gained from other parties considerably impacts the individual's feeling and notion about the innovation, and further helps the individual to evaluate the innovation before deciding.

At the decision stage, the individual may decide to either adopt or reject the innovation as the best course of action. If the individual decides to adopt the innovation, the implementation stage will succeed the decision stage. At this point, the innovation is put into action. However, the individuals usually still seek support to assure them that they have made the right decision. If the person receives mixed signals about the invention, the adoption decision may be reconsidered. However, the individual tends to defend their adoption decision by disallowing negative messages and focusing on good ones (Alrousan, 2014; Rogers, 2003). This implies that the attitude of the individual plays a substantial role at the confirmation stage. Nevertheless, rejection may still occur at any stage of the process (Sahin, 2006).

Based on the reviewed literature, DoI theory, especially the elements of Attributes of Innovation, has been extensively applied as the theoretical underpinning several empirical studies on adoption of e-commerce and technological innovation in business organisations (Faisal and Idris, 2020; Issa and Lee, 2020; Alam, Khatibi, Sayed and Isamil, 2008; Tan and Eze, 2008; Hussin and Noor, 2005). In examining the extent of innovation, these studies identified potential significance of factors such as compatibility, relative advantage, trialability, observability and complexity, in improving or impeding adoption of technology by the businesses.

2.3.7 Culture and Technology

A review of some literature on the adoption of e-commerce revealed that influence of culture on adoption of technology by organisations has been a subject of interest in recent information systems studies (Alrousan and Jones, 2016). The influence of culture impacts technology adoption and their usage behaviours. The influence of culture on the uptake and application of technology were acknowledged in these studies (Yoon, 2009; Hasan and Ditsa, 1999).

For instance, a study to understand cultural differences conducted by Hofstede (1984) helped to develop a theory that eventually became a widespread theory in social science disciplines, especially in studying adoption of technology among different cultures (Chen and McQueen,

2008; Nakata and Sivakumar, 2001; Straub, Keila and Brenner, 1997). Hofstede's theory assessed the cultural beliefs across nations and regions that impact organisational and societal behaviour, using over 100,000 questionnaires across over 50 countries. The theory has four dimensions of cultural differences in a national and regional settings which include "Power distance, Individualism-Collectivism, Masculinity-Femininity and Uncertainty Avoidance" (Alrousan, 2014, p. 90). The theory was further improved in Hofstede (2001) to involve a fifth construct known as Long-Term Orientation, as illustrated in figure 13. This addition was to understand time horizon in culture.

Figure 13: Hofstede's cultural dimensions

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Hofstede, G. (2001). *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviours, Institutions, and Organization Across Nations*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage

Adapted from Hofstede (2001)

The Hofstede's cultural dimensions framework was found to be very useful in explaining cultural impact on technology adoption diffusion process within organisations. Therefore, many studies have used it, either exclusively or in combination with another model in predicting adoption of e-commerce in diverse cultures (Alrousan, 2104). For instance, Hasan and Ditsa (1999) applied Hofstede's framework in the study of technology adoption across three nations (in Africa, Australia and in Middle East), and discovered that fear and resistance to change are factors that significantly hinder SMEs managers in middle East from technology adoption, unlike in Africa and Australia.

Also, in another study conducted by Yoon (2009) to predict national culture's effect on Chinese consumers' acceptance of e-commerce, it was found that Uncertainty avoidance and Long-term Orientation dimensions significantly influence intention to shop online. In Veiga, Floyd and Dechant (2001) study on the cultural impact on technology, it was found that Hofstede's cultural dimensions significantly influenced adoption of e-commerce, especially in Perceived Usefulness construct.

Notwithstanding the widespread usefulness of Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions theory, it has been criticised for certain limitations. The first limitation is that Hofstede's study sampled IBM staff, who happen to be "members of a homogeneous corporate culture across different countries instead of heterogeneous cultures within a country" (Alrousan, 2014, p. 91). Secondly, the theory does not consider the changes in cultural aspects that take place over time and is impacted by media and technology. Hence, some researchers consider the outcome of Hofstede's study outdated since the study was carried out in the 1980s (Usunier and Lee, 2009; Kirkman, Lowe and Gibson, 2006). Lastly, Hofstede's cultural emphasis is only on groups, not minding individual differences of members within groups (Collins, Srikes and Louvieris, 2009).

2.3.8 Integrated Models and Theories

Based on the discussions in the above sections, technology innovation and adoption have been investigated in many studies. These studies examined and tested various models and theories relating to adoption of technology, especially adoption of e-commerce by organisations/users. The available literature shows that these theories and models have some limitations. Brief comments and limitations of these theories and models are presented in table 1. The literature suggests that these models and theories lack the capacity to provide adequate explanations on technology when used independently (Wymer and Regan, 2005). Therefore, researchers recommend addition of more constructs to the models and theories or integration of two or more theories to overcome their individual limitations and explain technology adoption more comprehensively. For instance, some researchers have extended TAM through addition of more constructs or integration with other theories/models to improve its capability in explaining behavioural intention to adopt innovation (Abou-Shouk, Megicks and Lim, 2013; Awa, Nwibere and Inyang, 2010; Grandon and Pearson, 2004; Riemenschneider, Harrison and Mykytn, 2003).

Table 1: Comments and limitations of the theories and models

Theory/Model	Comments/limitations	Author(s)
Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)	It is basically employed to study individual's attitude towards the use of technology.	Russel, Robidas, Hossain and Hossain (2021)
	It is limited in the evaluation of someone's behaviour when they cannot fully manage the act of willing	Ying and Isa (2022)
	The theory is unable to explain the beliefs that underpin certain behaviours.	Alrousan (2014); Davis (1989)
Theory of Planed Behaviour (TPB)	Its constructs are insufficient in explaining technology usage among individuals, and more constructs are needed to improve its predictive power.	Alrousan (2014); Werner (2004);
	It only serves in predicting someone's behaviours, but not the consequence of those behaviours.	Foxall (1997)
Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	TAM has better predictive power and is more adequate in explaining acceptance and use of technology than TPB and TRA.	Alrousan (2014); Yousafzai et al. (2010)
	It only predicts individual level technology adoption, but not firm level.	Oliveira and Martins (2011)
	It relies on self-reported data, which cannot validly determine the exact technology usage.	Keung, Jeffery and Kitchenham (2004)
	It comprises of only two factors; additional variables are needed to make it more comprehensive.	Alrousan (2014)
Diffusion of Innovation (DoI)	The innovation-decision process may not always follow the proposed sequence	Kwon, Woo, Sadachar and Huang (2021)
	It is more suitably equipped to assess behavioural intention of technology than TAM	El-Gohary (2012)
	Its constructs are not sufficient to enable understanding of the environment of the organisation because they are solely focused on technological innovation.	Alrousan (2014); Sparling, Cater-Steel and Toleman (2010).

Technology Organization Environment (TOE)	TOE is considered a strong theoretical underpinning for identification of e-commerce adoption factors in organisations	Alrousan (2014); Oliveira and Martins (2010)
	It does not clearly identify the managerial factors in situations where the organisations' managers are deemed to be the key decision makers in technology adoption.	Bao and Sun (2010); Sarkar (2008); Thong (1999).
	More constructs are needed to better explain adoption of technology in organisations	Kumar and Kaur, (2021); Chiu et al. (2017)
Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions	Only IBM employees, who were part of a homogeneous corporate culture across nations instead of multiple cultures inside one nation, were studied for Hofstede's original model.	Alrousan (2014); Shackleton and Ali (1990)
	Since Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions study was conducted in 1980, the outcome of the study is now considered to be outdated; therefore, there is need to replicate the study in different forms of technology adoption.	Kirkman et al. (2006); Usunier and Lee (2009)
	The theory was solely applied in studying national cultures and how they impact uptake of technology. Hence, the constructs in the theory need to be explored among members of the same culture.	Ford, Connelly and Meister (2003); Alrousan (2014)
Perceived e-Readiness Model (PERM)	PERM was designed for adoption of e-commerce by business organisations in developing countries.	Molla and Licker (2005)
	It is flawed in terms of validity and reliability, statistical analysis, and its non-consideration of some vital industry descriptors like firm size and employees' educational background.	Rahayu (2015); Tan, et al. (2007).
	It emphasises more on organisational characteristics without considering the individual factors influence; and fails to capture small business' idiosyncrasies.	Parker and Castleman (2009)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

In similar vein, many researchers have integrated TOE with DoI to boost its strength in determining technology adoption factors in organisations (Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Tan, 2010; Scupola, 2009; Allan et al., 2003). These researchers asserted that TOE blends well with DoI and gives a clearer picture of the technological elements that impact technology adoption in organisations. In addition, some studies have integrated DoI with TOE to identify influencing and inhibiting factors in SMEs technology adoption (Zhu and Kraemer, 2005; Allan et al., 2003). The findings from these studies confirmed that combination of provided a comprehensive explanation in organisations' technology adoption. This is because DoI is independently capable of explaining technological and organisational contexts, but inadequate to explain the environmental context, which is augmented by TOE that includes environmental context in its explanation of organisation's technology adoption (Oliveira and Martins, 2011). Furthermore, in other studies where TOE was integrated with TAM to explain innovation adoption such as e-commerce adoption in SMEs (Awa and Ukoha, 2012) and IT adoption in SMEs (Awa et al., 2010), they found that integrating TOE with TAM provided a robust explanation of e-commerce adoption.

2.3.9 Theory Employed

Having established that single models and theories lack the capacity to provide adequate explanations of technology adoption when used independently (Wymer and Regan, 2005), the current study integrates TOE with DoI to boost its strength in determining e-commerce adoption factors in Nigerian supermarket chains. TOE is an IT/IS system framework for research from the organizational point of view (Chiu, Chen and Chen, 2017). Since the focus of this study is on the application of technological innovation (e-commerce) from the supermarkets' perspective, the TOE framework is used as the major research model. Notwithstanding the success stories associated with the use of TOE in innovation application studies, evidence demonstrates that the initial TOE framework was designed for entities in advanced nations, as the majority of the early TOE-based research streams were conducted in and for advanced nations (Igudia, 2015; Gibbs and Kraemer, 2004). Available literature also suggests that the original TOE has been adjusted or combined with other models because it may not, when used alone, be able to account for all aspects of some technological innovations (Kumar and Kaur, 2021; Chiu et al., 2017; Igudia, 2015), like e-commerce application especially in emerging nations where economic, political, and socio-cultural settings differ from those of advanced nations where the TOE has been widely applied. Considering the success stories associated with the application of different TOE integrated models, especially with DoI, in testing the factors affecting the application of IT/IS innovation in both advanced

and emerging countries (Kumar and Kaur, 2021; Chiu et al., 2017), this study combines the TOE and the DoI to explore the factors that influence different e-commerce adoption levels in Nigerian supermarket chains.

The Rogers' DoI is based on a process-oriented perspective which makes it a suitable analytical framework for the prediction of the intention to use of different types of technology particularly e-commerce. Rogers (1995, cited in Chiu et al., 2017, p. 19) identified five perceptual innovation attributes including “relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability”, which are very instrumental in assessing the adoption rate of an innovation, as they are significant predictors of innovation adoption rate (Sahin, 2006). However, its constructs cannot sufficiently provide a clear picture of the organisational environment because they are solely focused on technological innovation (Alrouسان, 2014). Some of the previous studies have combined TOE with DoI in exploring the use of technological innovations, with the intention of gaining a better understanding of the spread of innovation from an organizational point of view (Hussain et al., 2021; Hussein et al., 2019; Chiu et al., 2017, Rahayu, 2015), and to lay a greater emphasis on the impact of both internal and external factors on the uptake and dissemination of innovation technologies (Chiu et al., 2017; Piaralal, Nair, Yahya and Karim, 2015; Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990). According to Piaralal et al. (2015), combination of TOE with DoI provides an instrumental framework for studying the adoption of green technology by logistics businesses and investigation of the use of innovation technologies by considering both internal and external influences.

In line with these previous studies, the current study combines DoI with TOE which is deemed a strong theoretical underpinning for identification of e-commerce adoption factors in organisations because of its consideration of technological, organisational, and environmental aspects of the organisation which are crucial dimensions of factors that impact the uptake of technology. The integration of DoI with TOE enables the researcher to explore all the factors of interest and their interactions in one robust framework. This provides a suitable integrated framework for the study of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains. TOE has been found to be consistent with DoI, and the combination of the two has been applied in many e-commerce studies (Kumar and Kaur, 2021; Hussain, Arfan, Hassan and Doski, 2021; Rahayu, 2015; Al-Qirim, 2007).

In a study about the impact of Covid-19 on business-to-business e-commerce adoption within the sports and surgical SMEs in Pakistan using an integration of TOE and DoI frameworks,

Hussain et al. (2021) explored the impact of technological factors, organisational factors, and environmental factors on B2B e-commerce. They successfully applied the integrated framework to study the influence of relative advantage and technology readiness constructs in the technological factors, the influence of top management support and adoption cost constructs in the organisation factors, and the influence of competitive pressure and government support constructs in the environmental factors. Also, Rahayu (2015) integrated DoI and TOE in a study about e-commerce adoption among Indonesian SMEs. The researcher examined perceived benefits of e-commerce adoption, compatibility, and the cost of adoption in the investigation of technological factors. In the investigation of organisational factors, the researcher examined the influence of technology readiness and the size of the firm, while pressure from suppliers, pressure from customers, competitive pressure, government support and vendor support were examined as the environmental factors. In addition to the technology, organisation and environmental aspects of the TOE framework, the researcher additionally investigated an individual aspect, in which they examined the influence of business owner/manager's innovativeness, level of involvement, and IT knowledge.

In the current study, relative advantage and compatibility, which are constructs from DoI's attributes of innovation, will be examined in the technological context. Hence, attributes of innovation in this study are also referred to as technological factors (Alrouسان, 2014). Technology readiness and financial barriers will be examined in the organisational context, while market environment pressure, and government and vendor support will be examined in the environmental context. Furthermore, top management support and managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce will be examined in the managerial context. As mentioned earlier, one of the major limitations of TOE is inability to fully identify managerial factors in technology adoption. In addressing this limitation, some researchers added a fourth construct to describe the managerial factors (Bao and Sun, 2010; Sarkar, 2008; Thong, 1999), while others studied managerial factors within the context of organisation based on the reasoning that technology adoption success is important to organisation's decision makers (Bryan and Zuva, 2021; Wallace, Green, Johnson, Cooper and Gilstrap, 2020; Kandil, Ragheb, Ragab and Farouk, 2018; Chiu et al., 2017; Alamro and Tarawneh, 2011; Scupola, 2009). The current study aligns with the researchers that added a fourth context to study the managerial factors. Hence, top management support and managers knowledge and attitude are examined in the context of managerial factors instead of organisational factors. The measured constructs within

the technological, organisational, managerial, and environmental factors were employed in the development of the conceptual framework and hypotheses for this study.

2.4 Factors Affecting the Adoption of E-Commerce

Many factors have been identified by studies that focused on the uptake of e-commerce and technology. Although these factors have been grouped in varying ways in different studies, however, they are categorised, in the current study, into four major groups: organisational factors, technological factors, managerial factors and environmental factors. These factors are further detailed in the following sub-sections.

2.4.1 Technological Factors

Several technology-related factors have been identified from the reviewed literature as illustrated in table 2. Ma, Buhalis and Song (2003) posited that technology adoption decision is not only subject to availability of the technology, but equally depends on the availability of knowledge on effective application of the innovation in order to meet the business needs of the organisation. The identified technological factors include, relative advantage, perceived usefulness, trialability, risk, perceived ease of use, technology competence, security, cost, observability, complexity, task variety, e-commerce barriers, perceived benefits, information systems input, technology integration and technology readiness. Amongst these factors, several researchers found Attributes of Innovation in Rogers (2003) DoI model as the most suitable key factors that explain technological factors, because DoI provides a comprehensive explanation of the influencing factors on technology adoption (Alrousan, 2014; Oliveira and Martins, 2011). Their studies reveal that technological factors consist of relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, observability and trialability.

Consequently, these technology-related factors have been investigated to ascertain their effect on e-commerce and technology adoption by business organisations. Based on the reviewed literature, varying results were obtained from the different studies for the same factor. For instance, in an investigation about e-commerce uptake by Thailand SMEs, using the innovation aspect of the DoI, and adding security as a new construct, Limthongchai and Speece (2003) found that all characteristics of DoI, except trialability, were significant. They also found security to have the least impact on e-commerce uptake. Alam et al. (2008) investigated the uptake of e-commerce in Malaysian manufacturing sector using a similar model to the one used by Limthongchai and Speece (2003) and found DoI factors to be significant in the prediction of e-commerce uptake. Some other researchers discovered various technological factors which

include e-commerce benefits (Rahayu, 2015; Teo et al., 2009; Ifinedo, 2011), task variety (Seyal et al., 2004), perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Raza and Khan, 2021; Luo, Remus and Sheldon, 2006). The different technological factors identified by previous researchers in the reviewed literature are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Identified technological factors from previous studies

Identified Technological Factors	Authors
Compatibility	Rawash (2021); Usman and Kumar (2021); Kandil et al. (2018); Zainuddin et al. (2018); Huy, Van and Truex (2012); Almoawi (2011); Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado (2011); Hung, Yang, Yang and Chuang (2011); Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo (2009); Sparling, Toleman and Cater-steel (2007)
Relative Advantage	Hussain et al. (2021); Rawash (2021); Sánchez-Torres, Rojas Berrío and Ortiz Rendón (2021); Muathe and Muraguri-Makau (2020); Kandil et al. (2018); Zainuddin et al. (2018); Chiu et al., (2017); Huy et al. (2012); Almoawi (2011)
Perceived Usefulness	Raza and Khan, (2021); Luo et al., (2006); Pavlou (2003)
Trialability	Chiu et al. (2017); Hussein (2009); Ramdani et al. (2009); Limthongchai and Speece (2003)
Risk	Huy et al. (2012); Hung et al. (2011); Hussein (2009)
Perceived Ease of Use	Luo et al., (2006); Pavlou (2003)
Technology Competence	Zhu et al. (2003)
Security	Kandil et al. (2018); Xu, Liu and Lu (2010); Limthongchai and Speece (2003)
Cost	Tan (2010)
Observability	Chiu et al. (2017); Hussein (2009); Ramdani et al. (2009); Hussin and Noor (2005); Limthongchai and Speece (2003)

Complexity	Kandil et al. (2018); Chiu et al. (2017); Huy et al. (2012); Almoawi (2011); Hussein (2009); Ramdani et al. (2009); Hussin and Noor (2005)
Task Variety	Seyal, Awais, Shamail and Abbas (2004)
Perceived Benefits	Rahayu (2015); Ifinedo (2011); Teo, Lin and Lai (2009); Seyal et al. (2004); Raymond (2001)
Technology Integration	Zhu et al. (2006)
Technology Readiness	Hussain et al. (2021); Rahayu and Day (2017); Al-Somali, Gholami and Clegg (2011); Zhu et al. (2006)
IT resources	Wallace et al. (2020)
IT Policy	Wallace et al. (2020)
Perceived desirability	Ocloo et al. (2020)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

2.4.2 Organizational Factors

The organisational factors influencing technology adoption are outlined in table 3. Previous studies reported that exploring organisational factors is instrumental to successful technology adoption in the organisation (Lestari, Muhdaliha and Putra, 2020; Rahayu, 2015; Kurnia, Alzougool, Ali and Alhashmi, 2009; Wymer and Regan, 2005; Raymond, 2001). Organisational factors imply the characteristics of the organisation that relate to technology adoption decision (Lippert and Govindarajulu, 2006).

The literature indicates that the organisational characteristics that impact technology adoption include size of the firm, cost, availability and readiness of IT, financial resources, organisational culture, IT knowledge of the employees, organisational IT competence, firm scope, marketing capabilities, strategic orientation, business category, formalisation, and centralisation. Many researchers have reported firm size as one of the major determinants of e-commerce and technology adoption by businesses (Ramdani et al., 2009; Jeyaraj, Rottman and Lacity, 2006; Zhu et al., 2003; Thong, 1999). The IT knowledge of the employees is another widely acknowledged organisational characteristic in technology adoption literature. Lippert and Govindarajulu (2006, p. 152) refer to Employees IT knowledge as “the sum of technological expertise by all members of an organization and is reflected in the technological sophistication of their operations”. The employee's IT knowledge has been extensively acknowledged to be an important factor in e-commerce uptake by businesses (Religia, Surachman, Rohman and Indrawati, 2021; Ramdani et al., 2009; Scupola, 2009).

Another organisational characteristic that has been found to play a significant role in predicting e-commerce and technology adoption is the cost factor. This factor has been described with many terms in the literature. For instance, it has been referred to as financial barriers or financial cost (Rahayu and Day, 2015; Teo, et al., 2009; Tan and Eze, 2008) while some studies refer to it as financial resources (Alamro and Tarawneh, 2011; Ifinedo, 2011).

Also, variability of factors has been identified by researchers within the organisational context. For instance, Sparling et al. (2007) listed organisational factors to include size of firm, technological opportunism, and technological readiness. Huy et al. (2012) pointed out that organisational factors include organisational readiness, employees' e-commerce knowledge, firm size, firm strategic orientation, and globalization orientation of the firm. Another study by Ramdani et al. (2009), suggested that organisational factors include top management support, firm size, IS experience and organisational readiness.

In a study conducted by Zhu et al. (2003), on the uptake of e-business by SMEs in Europe using TOE, they identified the organisational factors to include the firm size and the firm scope. Likewise, in another study conducted by Ifinedo (2011), that focused on SMEs' e-commerce uptake in Canada using TOE, organisational factors were suggested to include organisational IT competence, management support and perceived benefits. Hung et al. (2011) among other studies identified factors within the organisational context to include formalisation, centralisation, organisational scale of industry and superiority complex. Table 3 summarises factors identified within the organisational context.

Table 3: Organisational factors discovered in previous studies

Organisational Factors	Author(s)
Firm size	Zainuddin et al. (2018); Alrousan (2014); Almoawi (2011); Xu et al. (2010); Ramdani et al. (2009); Hussein (2009); Teo et al. (2009); Salwani, Marthandan, Norzaidi and Choy (2009); Ramdani et al. (2009); Sparling et al. (2007).
Cost	Hussain et al. (2021); Apulu, Latham and Moreton (2011); Tan and Eze (2008); Harindranath, Dyerson and Barnes (2008); Migiro (2006); Heung (2003).

Top Management Support	Bryan and Zuva (2021); Hussain et al. (2021); Rawash (2021); Ocloo et al. (2020); Wallace et al. (2020); Kandil et al. (2018); Chiu et al. (2017)
Financial Resources	Musawa and Wahab (2012); Bazini, Qarri and Iliia. (2011); Kurnia et al. (2009); Scupola (2003); Iacovou et al. (1995).
IT Readiness and Availability	Rawash (2021); Aswar (2020); Huy et al. (2012); Kurnia et al. (2009); Ramdani et al. (2009); Sparling et al. (2007); Hussin and Noor (2005); Grandon and Pearson (2004); Scupola (2003)
Employees' IT Knowledge	Chiu et al. (2017); Alrousan (2014); Huy et al. (2012); Alam and Noor (2009); Hussein (2009); Mirchandani and Motwani (2001); Thong (1999)
Strategic Orientation	Abou-Shouk et al. (2013); Huy et al. (2012); Al-Somali et al. (2011); Grandon and Pearson (2004)
Organizational IT Competence	Ifinedo (2011)
Firm Scope	Huy et al. (2012); Sparling et al. (2007); Zhu et al. (2006); Zhu et al. (2003)
Training	Wallace et al. (2020)
Marketing Capabilities	Abou-Shouk et al. (2013); Hussein (2009)
Organizational Culture	Wallace et al. (2020); Seyal et al. (2004)
Absorptive capability	Chiu et al (2017)
Information Intensity	Chiu et al (2017)
Organisational Innovativeness	Lestari, Muhdaliha and Putra (2020)
Organisation's readiness	Ocloo et al. (2020)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

2.4.3 Managerial Factors

Managerial factors relate to high-ranking members of an organisation who play significant roles in their organisations' decision-making processes (Alrousan, 2014). The managerial factors identified in the literature include manager's experience, manager's attitude to technology uptake, top management support, strategy management, CEO's characteristics, managers attitude to change, manager's IT knowledge, CEO's innovativeness, CEO's commitment to change, uncertainty avoidance, response to risk and motivation to use e-

commerce. The information obtained from the literature shows that manager's characteristics have been addressed by many studies as a possible key factor in technology uptake. Rogers (2003) asserted that the decision of individuals to adopt innovation depends mostly on their knowledge about the innovation.

Many researchers found the IT knowledge of the managers to be an important determining variable in e-commerce and technology uptake (Ifinedo, 2011; Xu et al., 2010; Scupola, 2009; Heung, 2003). Other researchers like Ramdani et al. (2009) and Raymond (2001) identified manager's experience, while Almoawi (2011) and Ghobakhloo et al. (2011) identified CEO's innovativeness as an important variable in e-commerce uptake by SMEs. The Literature also reveals that technology adoption is significantly linked to top management support. Al-Somali et al. (2011) reported that top management support is required for successful adoption and integration of innovation into business processes and activities. Broadly speaking, poor management support and commitment may exacerbate e-commerce. Many studies have found that top management support significantly influence e-commerce uptake by business enterprises (Zainuddin et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015; Heung, 2003). Some other studies like Hussin and Noor (2005) found CEO's commitment to IT to be an important variable in e-commerce uptake by business organisations.

Previous studies further identified managers' characteristics as potential barrier to e-commerce adoption. For instance, Zhu et al. (2006) identified obstacle from management as an inhibitor of e-commerce uptake by SMEs. Also (Hussein, 2009) identified response to risk, while (Chen and McQueen, 2008) identified uncertainty which were both found to negatively correlate with technology adoption by SMEs.

Rogers (2003) maintained that technology adoption decision process substantially correlate with technology adoption, especially when decision makers could have positive or negative attitude towards adopting or rejecting innovation. Hence, manager's attitude plays a significant role in the uptake or rejection of a new technology. Many studies have equally investigated the impact of managers attitude on the uptake of e-commerce. For instance, Mpfungu et al. (2009), To and Ngai (2007) and Seyal and Rahman (2003) found that managers attitude towards the use of IT positively and significantly drive e-commerce uptake by SMEs. The managerial factors identified in the literature are summarised in table 4.

Table 4: Managerial factors influencing e-commerce uptake

Managerial Factors	Author(s)
Managers' Attitude to Technology Adoption	Alrousan (2014); Huy et al. (2012); Almoawi (2011); Hussein (2009); Mpofu et al. (2009); Teo et al. (2009); To and Ngai (2007); Ramsey and McCole (2005); Seyal and Rahman, (2003)
Top Management Support	Hoang, et al. (2021); Zainuddin et al. (2018); Alrousan (2014); Rahayu and Day (2015); Al-Weshah and Al-Zubi (2012); Alamro and Tarawneh (2011); Al-Somali et al. (2011); Ifinedo (2011); Xu et al. (2010); Hussein (2009); Ramdani et al. (2009)
Knowledge management process	Nasution, Rafiki, Lubis and Rossanty (2021)
Zeal to Use E-Commerce	Seyal et al. (2004)
Uncertainty Avoidance	Alrousan (2014); Almoawi (2011); Bao and Sun (2010); Kollmann, Kuckertz and Breugst (2009); Leidner and Kayworth (2006); Seyal and Rahman (2003)
Power Distance	Alrousan (2014); Almoawi (2011); Kollmann et al. (2009); Yoon (2009)
Experience of the Managers	Raymond (2001)
IT Knowledge of the Managers	Almoawi (2011); Ghobakhloo et al. (2011)
CEO's Characteristics	Sparling et al. (2007)
CEO's Innovativeness	Nasution et al. (2021); Almoawi (2011)
Strategic Orientation	Al-Somali et al. (2011); Heung (2003)
Response to Risk	Nasution et al. (2021); Hussein (2009)
Managerial Obstacles	Zhu et al. (2006)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

2.4.4 Environmental Factors

External variables that influence e-commerce uptake by organisations are referred to as environmental factors. Several environmental factors were identified from previous studies. These factors include government support, vendor support, competitive pressure, enabling conditions, pressure from customers, pressure from business partners, regulatory environment.

According to Scupola (2009), pressure from customers is the most influential environmental factor in the uptake of e-commerce. Other studies that found customer pressure significant in influencing e-commerce uptake include Sánchez-Torres et al. (2021), Muathe and Muraguri-Makau (2020), Ifinedo (2011), Al-Qirim (2006). Other widely reported environmental factors that affect e-commerce and technology uptake include government support (Muathe and Muraguri-Makau, 2020; Chiu et al., 2017; Alrousan, 2014; Huy et al., 2012), competitive pressure (Chiu et al., 2017; Ghobakhloo et al., 2011), and pressure from business partners (Muathe and Muraguri-Makau, 2020; Alrousan, 2014; Huy et al., 2012). The environmental factors identified in the literature are summarised in table 5.

Table 5: Environmental factors identified from previous studies

Environmental Factors	Author(s)
Competitive pressure	Hussain et al. (2021); Rawash (2021); Ocloo et al. (2020); Wallace et al. (2020); Kandil et al. (2018); Chiu et al. (2017); Alrousan (2014); Ghobakhloo et al. (2011)
Government support	Hussain et al. (2021); Rawash (2021); Muathe and Muraguri-Makau (2020); Ocloo et al. (2020); Chiu et al. (2017); Alrousan (2014); Huy et al. (2012)
Business partners pressure	Muathe and Muraguri-Makau, (2020); Ocloo et al. (2020); Kandil et al. (2018); Chiu et al. (2017); Alrousan (2014); Huy et al. (2012)
External support	Chiu et al. (2017)
Customer pressure	Sánchez-Torres et al. (2021); Muathe and Muraguri-Makau (2020); Wallace et al. (2020); Alrousan (2014); Ifinedo (2011); Scupola (2009); Al-Qirim (2006)
Telecommunication infrastructure	Wallace et al. (2020); Kandil et al. (2018)
Trading partner support	Kandil et al. (2018)
Internet service provider	Kandil et al. (2018)
Government regulations	Wallace et al. (2020)
Cyber threats	Wallace et al. (2020)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

2.5 Benefits of E-Commerce to Business Organisations

Many proactive reasons have been identified as the rationale for the adoption of e-commerce by business organisations. These include expansion of an organisation's marketplace into the national as well as the international markets (Kareem et al., 2014). A business organisation can easily get better suppliers, more customers, and most suitable partners globally with minimal capital structure (Sajuyigbe, 2012). In fact, e-commerce facilitates fast and cost-effective procurement of products and services from other business organisations with little or no distribution channel, and thereby reducing the cost of products and increasing the vendor's profit (Molla and Licker, 2005). Studies have also found that e-commerce facilitates sales of goods and services and speedy product promotion (Hasan and Mardhani, 2021). Others like Kareem et al., (2014) suggest that e-commerce improves the competitive power of smaller businesses against the larger ones and promotes specialised niche market.

The significance of e-commerce in attaining the stated objectives of business organizations cannot be overemphasized in the current global competitive environment. Electronic commerce has presented numerous benefits to business organisations including the provision of more efficient and effective means of conducting business transactions for both the vendors and the buyers. Alrawi (2007) stated that e-commerce enables instant information access to buyers and virtual testing of products, which would be time-consuming in a traditional market setting. He further stated that the way products are delivered has changed because of e-commerce, and transactions could be made any time during the day or night from any geographical location, with more product choices available to the consumers (Abid, Rahim and Scheepers, 2011). In addition to providing better access and feedback from customers which provides a better understanding of their needs to enable the business offer products that could deliver a better customer satisfaction, e-commerce enables consumers to shop whilst in the comfort of their homes resulting in less road traffic and reduced air pollution because of reduced road travelling (Allen and Fjermestad, 2001). Companies can equally expand their product line, providing further physical or interactive services around the core product. There is also evidence to suggest that e-commerce facilitates low inventories by promoting pull-type supply chain management which reduces cost of inventory and allows customization of products (Kareem et al., 2014). The impact of e-commerce adoption to business organisations according to different researchers are summarised in Table 6.

Table 6: Benefits of e-commerce uptake

Benefits	Description	Sources
Convenience	E-commerce makes shopping more convenient as customers can buy items and receive them at the comfort of their homes without a physical visit to shops.	Taher (2021)
Efficiency of operations	E-commerce leads to time saving, reliability, flexible platform and accuracy.	Taher (2021); Xu and Quaddus (2009); Alrawi (2007)
Customer Service Improvement	E-commerce leads to closeness and easy communication with customers and better understanding of customer needs.	Sajuyigbe (2012); Allen and Fjermestad (2001)
Cost savings	E-commerce reduces cost of inventory, reduces tasks, reduces material expenses.	Taher (2021); Kareem et al. (2014); Sajuyigbe (2012); Stockdale and Standing (2004)
Global market access	E-commerce enables business organisations to gain access to additional services, new customers and additional markets.	Taher (2021); Kareem et al. (2014); Sajuyigbe (2012)
Sales increase	E-commerce leads to increase in sales due to unrestricted transaction time and wider market reach.	Hasan and Mardhani (2021); Abid et al. (2011)
Better information access	E-commerce increases the ability to obtain information	Taher (2021); Sajuyigbe, (2012); Oh anderson and

	about suppliers and customers.	Cruickshank, (2012); Xu and Quaddus (2009)
Faster product promotion	E-commerce makes it easier and quicker to promote a product to the general public.	Hasan and Mardhani (2021)
Promotion of other business operations	E-commerce promotes other business operations like supply chain and logistics operations.	Bvepfepfe (2019)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

2.6 Shortcomings of E-commerce

Despite the benefits of e-commerce, it also has some shortcomings, just like every other business where there are ups and downs. Operating the e-commerce business model presents unique difficulties. However, being aware of such difficulties will enable those that manage the businesses prevent unfavourable consequences. Previous studies identified some shortfalls of e-commerce. Taher (2021) identified inability to test an item prior to purchase as one of the major limitations of online shopping. With online shopping, shoppers do not have the liberty of testing items before receiving them (AL-Abrow et al., 2020). Although some online marketers present professionally made images and videos of products in a convincing manner to promote the products, however, some consumers are still reluctant to purchase any item they have not physically felt or tested. This is because many shoppers do not perceive a genuine assurance of product quality (Taher, 2021).

Another shortcoming of e-commerce is that customers cannot engage in online purchasing without a web connection or other form of online access, and they also need internet-connected devices (Taher, 2021; Bhasin, 2019). This may not be an issue of concern in advanced countries; however, it can be a significant problem in many emerging nations as some customers may not have steady access to internet connectivity and internet connected devices. Further, security problem has equally been identified to be among the disadvantages of e-commerce. Due to attacks by cybercriminals and hackers, online portals have received a lot of media attention. It is a highly significant issue because customers' account could be compromised outright due to poor security, which could result in the loss of some or all the money in the account (Bhasin, 2019). Additionally, items purchased online could be damaged

during delivery (Taher, 2021). The shortcomings of e-commerce identified in previous studies are as illustrated in table 7.

Table 7: Shortcomings of e-commerce

Shortcomings of E-commerce	Sources
Inability to examine products in-person before purchase	Taher (2021); AL-Abrow et al. (2020); Bhasin (2019)
Need for internet connectivity and internet-connected devices	Taher (2021); Bhasin (2019)
Security problem	Taher (2021); Bhasin (2019)
credit card fraud	Taher (2021); Bhasin (2019)
Delayed delivery	Taher (2021); Bhasin (2019)
High technological cost	Bhasin (2019); MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005)
Removal of intermediaries in business dealings, resulting in displaced business partners	MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005)
High dependency on technology	Bhasin (2019); MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005)
Lack of human contact, which otherwise is comforting and encouraging in physical store	Taher (2021); Bhasin (2019)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

2.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented a conceptual and theoretical review of literature on e-commerce adoption. It discussed different types of e-commerce, factors affecting e-commerce uptake, as well as the benefits and shortcomings of e-commerce. It further reviewed the history and application of the most popular models and frameworks in technology adoption, and how the evaluation of their strengths and limitations led to the selection of TOE and DoI as the theories that underpinned this study. The conceptual framework, study hypotheses, and contextual evaluation of the literature are all presented in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 3: REVIEW OF E-COMMERCE WITHIN NIGERIAN CONTEXT

3.0 Introduction

This chapter presents a review of the literature with an interest on studies that focused more on e-commerce adoption in Nigerian which is the context of this study. It covers the overview of e-commerce in Nigeria, potential of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarkets, and challenges to e-commerce adoption by organisations Nigeria. It further presents the summary of literature review as well as the conceptual framework and development of the hypothesis.

3.1 E-Commerce in Nigeria

Although the use of e-commerce in Nigeria is gradually increasing, it is still relatively low compared to its use in developed countries. There is evidence demonstrating that e-commerce spending in Nigeria grew from N49.9 billion (\$121.4 million) in 2011 to N62.4 billion naira (\$151.9 million) in 2012 (Khan and Uwemi, 2018). Further, a more recent report from the International Trade Administration found that e-commerce in Nigeria is being strengthened by the increasing number of youths in the country, growing consumer power, and increased use of smartphones. The same report stipulates that e-commerce spending in Nigeria was estimated to be \$12 billion, and the e-commerce revenue rise is predicted to reach \$75 billion per year by 2025 (International Trade Administration, 2021).

E-commerce development and online trading in Nigeria is gradually improving with the boom of e-businesses like Jumia, Kongo, Buyam, Traclist, Dealday, among others. Some of these e-businesses have secured foreign capital funding to grow the business while others are struggling to stay in business due to low profits occasioned by high cost of bandwidth for internet access, and inadequate developed online contents that could propel the e-commerce (Khan and Uwemi, 2018; Omonaiye et al., 2015). For instance, Gloo.ng struggled with funding as they were not able to raise up to a million dollars in funding within six years of operation, and eventually shut down their e-commerce business operation in January 2019. Whereas Konga and Jumia that started nearly the same time with Gloo.ng were able to raise about \$850 million (Dada, 2019). Nonetheless, internet usage in Nigeria and other countries with developing economies have been growing since the beginning of GSM operations in these countries. However, the cost of internet service is still high, and a great proportion of the Nigerian population still do not have regular internet access which is required for e-commerce operations. Nonetheless, the government and Nigerians at large have begun to realise the

tremendous potentials of e-commerce. However, investors need an enabling environment to explore the potentials (Khan and Uwemi, 2018; Kareem et al., 2014).

3.2 Potential of E-Commerce in Nigerian Supermarkets

Considering the nature of Nigerian supermarket industry and its customers, e-commerce has a variety of favourable effects on organisational performance. To begin with, given the labour-intensive nature of the supermarket business and the number of transactions carried out daily, e-commerce can have a significant positive impact on their administration and day-to-day processes. The ability of e-commerce to automate the daily flow of information and communication within and between organisations can lower administration costs and improve efficiency of operation, allowing supermarkets to sell products and services to consumers at a low cost (Kurnia and Peng, 2018).

Secondly, management of inventory and coordination of supply chain is crucial for organisational performance in the supermarket industry. The supermarkets are expected to feature a range of products to meet the product search and price comparison habit of Nigerian consumers. The ability of e-commerce to enhance efficient and effective inventory management can offer a competitive advantage to the supermarkets in an industry where availability of wide range of products and low costs are the competitive points of parity. Hence, the supermarket industry can benefit from e-commerce in product and information flow streamlining within the chains to maintain reduced inventory level and increased product range. In this sense, e-commerce technologies enable advanced supply chain management techniques like cross-docking and Vendor Management Inventory (VMI) which can enhance the efficiency of product refill, improve quality and availability of products (Simchi-Levi, 2003).

Finally, the continuous-changing preferences and demands of Nigerian consumers have necessitated a quick response of Nigerian supermarkets to the evolving market demands. Through facilitation of real time communication of market needs among the stakeholders in the supply chain, better information will be provided by e-commerce to assist the supermarkets in their decision-making process. Hence, e-commerce will enhance the supermarkets' responsiveness to the market and environment (Kurnia and Peng, 2018).

3.3 Challenges to E-commerce Uptake by Nigerian Business Organizations

Kalakota and Robinson in Adewale, Ayo-Oyebiyi and Adebayo (2013) suggests that e-commerce adoption is an external pressure occasioned by recent customer value proposition of

their wants, how and when they want it and at the cheapest price. Oguntunde and Oyeyipo (2012) noted that a consumer's lack of adequate computer skills is a serious concern in the uptake of e-commerce. The resultant price to be paid for the product or service could be high or difficult to pay due to lack of access to the specified currency or specific e-payment system. Also, there is a fear that information exchanged with partners and strategic data could be accessed by competitors, and this poses a serious obstacle to e-commerce uptake by Nigerian businesses. Customers are also worried about their personal information and the security of the electronic payment system (Taher, 2021). Another notable barrier to the adoption of e-commerce is the reluctance to implement a new strategy by the top management.

Khalifa et al., (1999) also stated that legal, security, privacy and authentication issues are the main challenges associated with e-commerce. Kalakota and Robinson (2001) posited that the core problem that constitute a barrier to e-commerce adoption is the managers' unwillingness to take responsibility for technological change. In this vein, Sajuyigbe (2012), found that most Nigerian business organisations failed to embrace e-commerce due to such factors as inadequate knowledge on e-commerce technology, poor network infrastructure, management's lack of interest, security issues associated with e-commerce and capital requirement for e-commerce. Inadequate support from top managers has also been noted as one of the difficulties with e-commerce uptake in Nigeria. Alsaad, Mohamad and Ismail (2017) suggest that the extent of recognition of the need for e-commerce by the leadership of an organisation is determined by top management support. This is because their endorsement of e-commerce will guarantee the allocation of adequate financial and technological resources required for the adoption of IT innovations (Abid et al., 2011). Arendt (2008) points out that the most crucial factors affecting the adoption of e-commerce by business organisations are lack of skills and knowledge. Table 8 summarises the barriers to e-commerce adoption, as depicted in the literature.

Table 8: Barriers to adoption of e-commerce

Category	Barriers	Source
Management and strategy	Poor managerial e-commerce experience, poor awareness, deficient long-term business strategy, top management's resistance, poor innovative culture	Al-Tit (2020); Ocloo et al. (2018); Alsaad et al. (2017); Abid et al. (2011); Arendt (2008)
Cost and financing	High cost of connectivity, cost of technology, inadequate finance resources, high cost of resultant products, delayed return on investments,	Ezennia and Marimuthu (2022); Al-Tit (2020); Oguntunde and Oyeyipo (2012); Abid et al. (2011); Arendt (2008)
Skills and training	Low IT skills level, poor knowledge, and experience	Ezennia and Marimuthu (2022); Al-Tit (2020); Oh et al. (2012); Abid et al. (2011); Arendt (2008)
Technology Choices	High level of complexity, attitude to adoption of IT	Ocloo et al. (2018); Alsaad et al. (2017); Kurnia, Karnali and Rahim (2015)
Security and reliability	Security of financial data exchanged during transactions; security of information exchanged with partners	Ezennia and Marimuthu (2022); Al-Tit (2020); Oh et al. (2012); Abid et al. (2011); Arendt (2008)
External barriers	Legal obstacles, poor customer readiness, insufficient transactional trust, language barrier	Al-Tit (2020)

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

3.4 Summary of Literature Review

Chapters two and three presented a review of literature on e-commerce uptake. Chapter two has two sections. The first section discussed the seven theories relevant to e-commerce adoption which include "Theory of Reasoned Action", "Theory of Planned Behaviour",

“Technology Acceptance Model”, “Diffusion of Innovation theory”, “Technology-Organization-Environment framework”, “Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions theory”, and “Perceived e-Readiness Model”. The section further discussed the integration of these models and their applications in previous studies. The Technology-Organization-Environment framework integrated with Diffusion of Innovation was adopted by this study because recent studies have shown that single models do not satisfactorily describe the uptake of e-commerce in business organisations. The second section of Chapter Two presented a conceptual review of e-commerce adoption literature. It covered an overview of e-commerce, definition of e-commerce, types of e-commerce, and e-commerce perspectives (e-commerce in developed and developing countries), factors affecting e-commerce (technological, organisational, managerial, and environmental factors), and the benefits of e-commerce. Chapter Three presents the review of e-commerce adoption within Nigerian context. It covers an overview of e-commerce in Nigeria, the potential of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarkets, and challenges to e-commerce adoption by Nigerian business organisations.

The critical review of the body of knowledge revealed that only a few non-in-depth studies have been conducted on e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains. Kareem et al. (2014) explored the impact of e-commerce on business performance of selected 8 supermarkets in Ibadan, which is just one of numerous cities in Nigeria, examining only the impact of e-commerce on service operations, cost operation reductions, and profit levels. Two other related studies explored the determinants of consumers intention to use online shops in general, not focusing on the supermarkets, and from customers perspective, not owners’ perspective (Usman and Kumar, 2021; Omotayo and Omotope, 2018). This has necessitated the need for a comprehensive study of e-commerce application within the Nigerian supermarket chains, from the supermarkets’ perspectives. This study has set out to fill this knowledge gap by conducting a holistic study about e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains; investigating the extent of adoption and adoption benefits and exploring the factors affecting adoption levels; and measures to improve adoption and sustainability of e-commerce in the industry. Consequently, a conceptual framework and eight hypotheses were developed to help guide this study as discussed in the next section.

3.5 Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development

Figure 14 presents the conceptual framework for this study which was developed based on TOE and DoI models. In addition to the technological, organisational, and environmental aspects of the TOE framework, the managerial aspects of the factors that influence e-commerce adoption were also explored. As mentioned earlier, the addition of the managerial factors' context to the TOE framework in this study is to mitigate a limitation of the original TOE framework which has been criticised for its inability to fully explain managerial factors in innovation adoption. Although some researchers have studied managerial factors within the context of an organisation based on the reasoning that technology adoption success is important to organisation's decision makers (Bryan and Zuva, 2021; Hussain et al., 2021; Wallace et al., 2020; Kandil et al., 2018; Chiu et al., 2017; Alamro and Tarawneh, 2011), the current study aligns with the researchers that introduced a managerial context to the TOE framework to mitigate the limitation (Alrousan, 2014; Bao and Sun, 2010; Sarkar, 2008; Thong, 1999).

Figure 14: Conceptual framework for the study

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

The variables examined in the managerial factors context in this study include top management support, and the managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce. Technological factors examined in this study consist of relative advantage and compatibility, which are constructs from DoI theory's attributes of innovation. Hence, the technological factors context is also referred to as attributes of innovation in this study (Alrousan, 2014). Technology readiness and

financial barriers were considered in the organisational factors' context, while market environment pressure, government and vendor support were considered in the environmental factors' context. The hypotheses for this study were developed in the subsection that follows based on these factors. These factors are proposed to affect the adoption levels of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains.

Some previous studies have investigated the adoption levels of e-commerce using a multichotomous variable, evaluating at least three different adoption levels (Ocloo et al., 2020; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Alrousan 2014; Molla and Licker 2005) as opposed to studies that measured the dependent variable as a dichotomous variable. This study adapted the e-commerce maturity model developed by Molla and Licker (2005), which was used by Alrousan (2014) in evaluating the extent of e-commerce application. This involved categorising the extent of e-commerce application into five adoption levels which include the “non-adoption, the e-connectivity, the e-window, the e-interactivity, the e-transaction and the e-enterprise” levels of adoption (Alrousan 2014, p. 144). Non-adoption category includes those that do not make use of e-commerce technologies, while e-connectivity level includes those that employ basic e-commerce technologies like e-mail for communication. The e-window level includes those that enable one way communication with customers by only using a static website to present information. On the other hand, the e-interactivity level includes the use of an interactive website that enable 2-way communication to interact with customers, whilst the e-transaction level involves the use of advanced e-commerce technologies to facilitate transactions like online payments. Finally, the e-enterprise level enables an online activity for all business processes including accounting system and upgrading traditional businesses to electronic ones (Alrousan, 2014). The items used in measuring the constructs are outlined in the operationalisation of constructs table in Appendix A2.

3.5.1 Relative Advantage

According to Rogers (2003) relative advantage is the extent to which an innovation of interest is seen to be more beneficial than the one it is meant to replace. Technology wise, relative advantage involves profit increase, productivity increase, time and cost reduction, efficiency improvement, improved competitive advantage, improved customer services and customer satisfaction, and enhanced communication with business partners (Alrousan, 2014; Ashrafi and Murtaza, 2008). Many studies have found relative advantage to be a significant determinant in technology adoption (Zainuddin et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015; Alrousan, 2014; Abou-Shouk et al., 2013; Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2013; Mohammed, Almsafir and Alnaser, 2013;

Tan and Eze, 2008). These studies found relative advantage to have a positive and significant influence on the uptake of e-commerce and ICT. Nevertheless, few studies have found relative advantage to have an insignificant influence on e-commerce uptake (Almoawi and Mahmood, 2011; Seyal and Rahman, 2003). However, in accordance with most recent studies, this research hypothesises a positive correlation between relative advantage and e-commerce uptake. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Relative advantage has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.5.2 Compatibility

Compatibility has been defined as “the degree to which an innovation is perceived as consistent with the existing values, past experiences, and needs of potential adopters” (Rogers 2003, p. 240). In the context of e-commerce and ICTs, compatibility implies the degree to which the available technology infrastructure is consistent with the innovation level of interest (Alrousan, 2014). Many researchers discovered a strong and positive association between e-commerce adoption and compatibility (Zainuddin et al., 2018; El-Gohary, 2012; Alam et al, 2008; Sparling et al., 2007). However, some have found the relationship between compatibility and e-commerce adoption level to be insignificant (Rahayu and Day, 2015; Alrousan, 2014; Adewale et al., 2013; Almoawi and Mahmood, 2011). The current study follows most recent studies that found a positive relationship between compatibility and adoption level of e-commerce. Hence, the proposal of the hypothesis below:

H2: Compatibility has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.5.3 Technology Readiness

According to Zhu et al. (2006), technology readiness implies the level of availability of infrastructure for technology, appropriate system and technological skill required for e-commerce adoption. Similarly, Durga and Singla (2019) described technology readiness as the extent of a firm’s capability to make optimum use of its infrastructure and architecture for implementing a technological innovation. Ocloo et al. (2020) found that technology readiness was a significant factor that influences application levels of B2B e-commerce among manufacturing SMEs in Ghana. Similarly, Zhu et al. (2006) discovered that technology readiness was, not just a factor, but the key factor in the implementation of e-business by businesses in developing countries. Other studies that found technology readiness to have a significant positive influence on e-commerce uptake include Aswar (2020), Rahayu and Day

(2015), and Tiago and Maria (2010). In line with these studies, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Technology readiness has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.5.4 Financial Barrier

Previous studies have defined the term financial resources in terms of technology adoption as availability of funds to execute e-commerce activities without feeling financially burdened (Kurnia et al., 2009). IT studies found financial resources to be the major differentiating attributes between the large and small businesses (Ifinedo, 2011; Thong, 1999) as small businesses have been known to have limited financial resources (Ghobakhloo et al., 2011). Many studies have found a significant and positive relationship between financial resources availability and adoption of e-commerce and ICTs (Musawa and Wahab, 2012; Alamro and Tarawneh, 2011; Bazini et al., 2011). On the other hand, financial barriers or costs were found by other researchers to negatively impact e-commerce adoption (Alroushan, 2014; Ashrafi and Murtaza, 2008; Heung, 2003). However, Rahayu and Day (2015) found an insignificant relationship between financial cost and e-commerce adoption. The current study proposes a negative correlation between financial barrier and e-commerce uptake, hence, the hypothesis below.

H4: Financial barrier has a negative and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.5.5 Top Management Support

In an e-commerce context, top management refers to members of the organisation that have powers to make tactical decisions regarding e-commerce; as a result, they can create a well-defined vision and plan for e-commerce in the organisation (Alroushan, 2014). Top management support has been found to be an important factor with a positive influence on e-commerce adoption (Ocloo et al. 2020; Zainuddin et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015; Ifinedo, 2011; Ramdani et al., 2009; Teo et al., 2009). Although, few studies have found top management support to be an insignificant factor in e-commerce adoption (Alroushan, 2014; Levy et al., 2005), this study shall be in accordance with majority of the earlier studies which found a positive correlation between top management support and e-commerce uptake. Hence, it is hypothesised that:

H5: Top management support has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.5.6 Managers Knowledge and Attitude Towards E-commerce

Implementation of new technology or innovation often interferes with the existing system and the usual organisational practice, and some organisational members tend to oppose change due to the disruption to the status quo (Alrousan, 2014). Also, the knowledge of the managers regarding the innovation may affect their willingness to embrace the innovation. Hence, managers' knowledge and attitude play an important role in technology adoption. Many studies have found a significant positive relationship between managers' attitude and technology uptake (Mpofu et al., 2009; To and Ngai, 2007). Also, Zainuddin et al. (2018) found knowledge to have a strong positive association with e-commerce uptake. However, some studies found the relationship between managers attitude and e-commerce uptake to be insignificant (Alrousan, 2014; Chau and Jim, 2002). Nevertheless, the current study shall align with past research that found a strong positive link between managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed.

H6: Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.5.7 Market Environment Pressure

Pressure from the market environment has been found to influence the adoption of e-commerce. Such pressures include pressure from customers to adopt e-commerce; pressure from suppliers and business partners to adopt e-commerce; and pressure from competitors to adopt e-commerce. Previous studies have found that market environment pressure is an important predictor with a positive influence in the adoption of e-commerce (Hoang, Nguyen and Nguyen, 2021; Ocloo et al., 2020; Alsaad, Mohamad and Ismail, 2018; Alrousan, 2014; Ifinedo, 2011; Al-Qirim, 2006; Zhu et al., 2003). However, few studies have found this pressure to be insignificant in the adoption of e-commerce (Rahayu and Day, 2017; Al-Qirim, 2007). Nevertheless, the current study shall be in accordance with the findings of most previous studies which have found a favourable correlation between market environment pressure and the adoption of e-commerce. Hence, it is hypothesised that:

H7: Market environment pressure has a positive influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.5.8 Government and Vendor Support

The impact of government support on the uptake of e-commerce has been of interest to many researchers (Hoang, et al., 2021; Huang, Li and Zhang, 2021; Ocloo et al., 2020; Alrousan, 2014; Huy et al., 2012). Government support in the context of technology adoption includes legislation, policy making, provision of funds, and IT infrastructure (Alrousan 2014; Huy et

al., 2012). Previous studies found a significant favourable correlation between government support and e-commerce uptake (Hoang, et al., 2021; Huang, Li and Zhang, 2021; Ocloo et al., 2020; Alrousan 2014). Also, Rahayu and Day (2017) investigated the impact of external support which includes government and vendor support on e-commerce adoption. They found that government and vendor support had a significant positive impact on e-commerce uptake. Based on these findings, the current study proposes a significant positive impact by government and vendor support on e-commerce uptake in Nigerian supermarket chains. Therefore, it is hypothesised that:

H8: Government and vendor support has a significant and positive influence the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

3.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented a review of e-commerce literature within the Nigerian context. It covered an overview of e-commerce in Nigeria and explored the potentials and challenges of e-commerce in the country. It then presented a summary of the literature review, highlighting the knowledge gap that the study was intended to fill. Informed by knowledge from previous studies, the chapter further developed eight hypotheses and created a conceptual framework based on TOE and DoI theories to guide the current study.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.0 Introduction to Methodology

This chapter presents a discussion of the research methodology and research design. It starts with a discussion of the research philosophies justifies the adopted philosophy. It then discusses research approaches, and the selected approach. This is followed by a discussion of research methods, and a justification of the selected method. It further discusses sampling method, data collection, data analysis and quality criteria, which includes reliability and validity.

Since many researchers believe that the ideal methodology for a study is determined by the type of the research and the objectives of the study as well as the skills and resources available to the researcher, it is important to recap the objectives of this research which has been discussed earlier in chapter one. These objectives include:

- to examine the extent of application of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- to analyse the benefits of e-commerce adoption to Nigerian supermarket chains.
- to examine the factors that affect the extent of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- to develop measures to improve the adoption and sustainability of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains.

Drawing from the research objectives, this chapter explains how the understanding of different research methods, and different philosophical world views enabled the researcher to select a mixed research method and a pragmatic approach. This was the most suitable research method, the most relevant, and appropriate philosophical stance that aligned well with the research objectives.

4.1 Research Philosophy

The term research philosophy implies a system of assumptions and beliefs about knowledge development. It is about what one does when carrying out research: knowledge development in a particular field (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). According to Collis and Hussey (2003, cited in Adelola, 2017), research philosophy offers a context for exploring and analysing the relationships between research methods and data. Five key philosophies have been identified in business and management, and they include “positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism, and pragmatism” (Saunders et al., 2019, p. 144). However, the positivism, interpretivism and pragmatism are the most used among the five.

Positivism is a natural scientist's philosophical position that entails using observed reality in society to generate law-like generalisations. It is typically associated with quantitative research methods. In fact, positivists share the view that different researchers will produce a similar result when they investigate a societal problem if they use a similar process and carefully apply a statistical test with a large sample (Creswell, 2014). On the other hand, the critical realism philosophy focusses on explaining observations and experiences, regarding the fundamental reality and structures underpinning the observable events. The research is typically retrodictive in nature, with detailed historically fitting analysis of established structures and developing agency (Saunders et al., 2019). There is also interpretivism. In fact, interpretivism emphasises how humans differ from physical occurrences in that they generate meaning, which interpretivists investigate (Saunders et al., 2019). Interpretivism utilises a reasonable approach and strongly relies on data of a qualitative nature. However, improved precision could be achieved through combination with quantitative data (Lasisi, 2018). Postmodernism which emerged in the late twentieth century focusses on language and power relations roles, attempting to question widely accepted thinking pattern and endeavour to promote marginalised views. The ideal research method for post modernism is typically deconstructive, involving reading texts and realities against themselves, with far-reaching exploration of abnormalities, absences, and silences. The research can be carried out with different types of data, but qualitative method is ideal for the analysis (Saunders et al., 2019).

Pragmatism asserts that the relevance of concepts is only in their support of action (Kelemen and Rumens 2008). According to Conant and Zeglen (2012, cited in Lasisi, 2018), pragmatism may be described as a philosophic view that help researchers to deal with practical problems more effectively. Otherwise stated, it can be argued that as we are in touch with the real world, the best and most suitable approach can be applied to deal with issues (Lasisi, 2018). Saunders et al. (2019) asserts that pragmatists have a view that different types of methods and knowledge can be used to address a research problem. In other words, it is often possible and highly appropriate to apply different types of methods in one study. The pragmatists are of the opinion that diverse approaches to investigation and interpretation of the world exist, and that the entire picture can never be seen with a single point of view and that multiple realities are obtainable. However, this does not imply that a pragmatist always must apply several methods, instead they employ a method or combine methods that will facilitate the collection of well-founded, reliable, relevant, and credible data that enhance the research (Saunders et al., 2019; Kelemen and Rumens 2008). Hence, a range of methods: quantitative, qualitative, mixed, multiple or

action research, can be employed in pragmatist study depending on the problem the study intends to address and the research questions.

Considering the research problem and research questions set out for this study, the pragmatic philosophical position has been adopted in the study as the researcher combined methods that enable the collection of well-founded, reliable, relevant, and credible data to advance the research (Saunders et al., 2019; Kelemen and Rumens 2008). This is because pragmatists do not just focus on methods to fit with a particular worldview, rather they mix and match different methods that best examine and provide best understanding of a particular problem in research within social science (Tashakhkori and Teddlie, 1998). The flexibility of the adopted pragmatic philosophy allows the combination of methods and strategies which facilitates a far-reaching explanation of why things are the way they are, and explanation of the mechanisms and structures which shape the observable event without the constraints posed by using exclusively either interpretivism or positivism approaches (Igudia, 2015). According to Creswell (2014, p. 12):

“For mixed method researchers, pragmatism opens the door to multiple methods, different worldviews, and different assumptions, as well as different forms of data collection and analysis”

Therefore, the use of pragmatic paradigm in this study enabled the researcher to harness the combined strengths of both the quantitative and qualitative methods in the analysis process and to make up for each other’s weaknesses (Igudia, 2015). Also, the researcher was more interested in developing a framework to improve the adoption of e-commerce by supermarkets in Nigeria, a practicable outcome in a real-life situation. In this sense, a pragmatist approach was the ideal philosophy for this study.

4.2 Research Approach

Theories are used in research projects, which may or may not be evident in the research design. However, it is usually made evident in the findings presentation and conclusions writing. One of three types of research approaches could be applied in a study. These include inductive, deductive, and abductive reasoning (Saunders et al., 2019). Deductive research involves theory development which is subsequently tested rigorously using a series of propositions. Deduction is a scientific approach that places a strong focus on quantification, generalisation, structure, and testable hypothesis. Hence, it is more likely to be underpinned by positivism philosophy (Saunders et al., 2019). On the other hand, inductive approach which is employed mostly in

studies that are more concerned with the context of the idea preferably uses a modest number of subjects for sampling and typically uses qualitative data. It is more likely to be informed by philosophy of interpretivism (Saunders et al., 2019). Abductive approach combines deduction and abduction by navigating between data and theory (Suddaby 2006). Testable conclusions are generated using known premises. An abductive approach may be appropriate for a study issue with a lot of literature in one context but less in the one being studied, allowing for the modification of an established theory. Given its flexibility, researchers aligned with different research philosophies can use abductive approach. In fact, most management studies apply some elements of abduction as it is arguably nearly impossible to achieve a pure induction or pure deduction. Nevertheless, postmodernism or pragmatism are most likely to underpin a well-built abductive approach. However critical realism can also be used as a foundation (Saunders et al., 2019).

Since the researcher made a choice to adopt a pragmatic philosophy in this research, it was only ideal for the research to lend itself to abductive reasoning. Also, since the academic literature was available for adoption of e-commerce by supermarkets in some other countries, but limited studies were available in the Nigerian context, it was only reasonable to adopt abductive reasoning. This enabled the researcher to modify an already existing model or develop a new one to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains.

4.3 Research Methods

Three methodological approaches to investigation have been identified in social science research. These include the qualitative, the quantitative and the mixed method of research. Each of these methods is underpinned by a distinct paradigmatic philosophy, which is rooted in a separate set of philosophical assumptions, nevertheless, they can be employed in the investigation of the same subject matter and obtain similar result (Bryman, 2006). These three research methods are addressed in the subsections that follow.

4.3.1 Quantitative Research Method

Quantitative research, also referred to as empirical research can be described as a method of research that involves collecting and analysing numerical and statistical data. According to Creswell (2003), it is a method that involves the use of deductive approach in which certain aspects of phenomena which are numerically or statistically measured are employed in testing and verifying theories using variables. This method presents a broad phenomenal overview for

making generalisations and making sure that research is replicable. Quantitative research is underpinned by positivist philosophical views. The researchers therefore posit that reality can be objectively observed and so can be quantified (Igudia, 2015).

Bryman and Bell (2003) posited that quantitative method of research should not only be viewed from quantification perspective of social life but should equally be considered from epistemological position (philosophy of knowledge of things) and ontological point of view (philosophy of nature of things). This method of research is also ideal for investigation of sensitive subject matter that people may not be comfortable to talk about.

4.3.2 Qualitative Research Method

The qualitative method of research is inductive in nature and is underpinned by interpretivist philosophy. It trails a non-linear path using case studies in presenting social phenomena in their social and historical perspectives (Neuman, 2000). This method of research aims at understanding the phenomenal context of the study and examines the social construction of the meanings emanating from the phenomena's understanding and its context.

In contrast to the quantitative research that focuses on explanation of phenomena, qualitative method focuses on exploring the phenomena (Creswell, 2003). The researchers in qualitative research are key instruments as they personally collect data through examination of documents, interviewing the participants, or observation of behaviour. They may use instruments to collect data, but they gather the information themselves without relying on instruments or questionnaires developed by other researchers (Creswell, 2014). Qualitative research method differs from quantitative method and the mixed research method in many aspects as illustrated in table 9 which was adapted from Creswell (2014).

4.3.3 Mixed Research Method

Mixed research method is an inquiry approach that entails gathering and analysing both qualitative and quantitative data, integrating the data collected from both methods, and using different designs which may include theoretical frameworks and philosophical assumptions. Mixed research method form of inquiry is assumed to offer a more thorough knowledge of a research problem through the combination of both qualitative and quantitative approaches rather than using only one of the approaches (Creswell, 2014). This method of research is underpinned by the pragmatic research philosophy and is based on the assumption that diverse types of data can be collected to provide to a deeper knowledge of a research problem than using only either qualitative or quantitative data (Creswell, 2014). It has also been argued that

employing both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods (mixed methodology) offsets the limitations of one method with the other method's strength (Creswell, 2003).

In a mixed method research, quantitative and qualitative study may be used equally or unequally. In other words, the weight or priority given to either qualitative or quantitative study may be different in such a way that either of the methods plays a dominant role while the other plays a supporting role, based on the research purpose (Saunders et al., 2016). Also, qualitative and quantitative studies can be integrated in a mixed method research in a variety of ways including the simple concurrent forms (Figure 15) as well as the more complex sequential forms (Figure 16 and Figure 17) (Saunders et al., 2016).

In the concurrent design, both quantitative and qualitative data are gathered in a single phase and may be collected by using both close-ended and open-ended questions in a questionnaire but may also be collected separately in roughly the same time (Saunders et al., 2016; Creswell, 2014). The two sets of data are analysed separately, but the results are discussed together to provide a more compressive and richer response to the research questions than the use of either one of the methods only (Saunders et al., 2016; Igudia, 2015; Creswell, 2014). The concurrent mixed method is typically employed when the researcher's intent is to collect data efficiently, and it also saves time since both quantitative and qualitative data are usually gathered at nearly the same time, instead of at different times, which necessitates additional trips to the research site (Creswell, 2014). On the contrary, in the sequential mixed method, which can be explanatory or exploratory, the qualitative and quantitative sets of data are collected one after the other (Neuman, 2000), and the design's intent is to elaborate one method's finding with the other method as illustrated in figures 16 and 17, which were adapted from Creswell (2014). The researcher gathers and analyses quantitative data in the first phase of the explanatory sequential mixed approach and uses the result to build the qualitative phase. The researcher subsequently integrates the interpretation of the entire analysis. In this method, the researcher's overarching goal is to employ qualitative data to fully explain the initial quantitative result (Creswell, 2014). Conversely, in the exploratory sequential mixed method (figure 17), the researcher first explores with qualitative data and analysis, and employs the results in the quantitative study which is the second phase. The goal of this design is to enhance measurements using specific population samples to see if data acquired from a small number of people in the qualitative study can be generalised to a large population sample in the

quantitative investigation (Creswell, 2014). More attributes of mixed research method are presented in table 9.

Figure 15: Convergent parallel mixed method design

Source: Creswell (2014, p. 270)

Figure 16: Explanatory sequential mixed method

Source: Creswell (2014, p. 270)

Figure 17: Exploratory sequential mixed method

Source: Creswell (2014, p. 270)

Table 9: Attributes of various research methods

Qualitative Approaches	Quantitative Approaches	Mixed Method Approaches
Typically claims constructivist/transformative knowledge	Typically claims positivist knowledge philosophical assumptions	Typically claims pragmatic knowledge philosophical assumptions
Tend to employ grounded theory, phenomenology, case study, ethnography and narrative strategies of inquiry	Tend to employ surveys and experiments strategies of enquiry	Tend to employ concurrent, sequential or transormative strategy of enquiry
Ask open-ended questions	Use close-ended questions	Use both close- and open-ended questions
Use emerging approahes and use images or text data	Employ predetermined approaches	Use both predetermined and emerging approaches;
Interview data, audio-visual data, document data and observation data	Forms of data include performance data, census, observational data, and attitude data	Varying forms of data are gathered on every possibility.
Text and image analysis are employed	The nature of analysis is statistical	Both statistical and text analysis are employed
The researchers position themselves, collect participants' meanings, concentrate on a single phenomenon or concept, bring their persoonal beliefs into the research, study the participants' setting or context, validate finding's accuracy, interpret the data, develop a plan for reform or change	The Researchers evaluate or verify theories or explanations, identify variables to be researched, link variables in questions or hypotheses, apply validity and reliability standards, and monitor and quantify data numerically., assume replicability of data, employ approaches that are unbiased and use staitstical procedures	The researchers collect both qualitative and quantitative data, present a justification for using mixed method, integrate data at various stages of the investigation, give visual depictions of the study operations, and use both quantitative and qualitative research practices

Adapted from Creswell (2014, p. 47)

4.3.4 Research Method Employed

The choice of research method appropriate for a study is influenced by several factors which include the research problem or interest, research questions, research objectives, personal experience of the researcher, researcher's skills and trainings, the audience for the research report and resources at researcher's disposal (Saunders et al., 2019; Igudia, 2015; Creswell, 2014). Notwithstanding that most e-commerce studies employed a quantitative research method design as shown in table 9, this researcher among other reasons for choosing a mixed research method believes that it is vital to enhance the quantitative study findings with findings from qualitative study. Therefore, this study adopted a concurrent mixed method- quantitative dominant approach in which qualitative study was carried out to elaborate the findings from the quantitative study. Critical among the influencing factors on the choice of mixed research method for this study were the nature of the research problem and research questions; to broaden the scope of the research; to offset the limitations in each of the two methods; and to gain insight from diverse points of view.

The first criteria, which is the nature of the research questions and the research objectives, suggests that the use of mixed research method was necessary to satisfactorily address the research objectives outlined in chapter one and answer their prompting research questions. This was consistent with the belief that both quantitative and qualitative methods can be combined in one study, not only to provide a deeper understanding of the research problem (Creswell, 2014), but also to satisfactorily address the different research questions (Saunders et al., 2019; Bryman, 2006), as is the case in this study.

As earlier deliberated in chapter one, the research questions for this study are:

1. What is the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains?
2. How beneficial is e-commerce adoption to Nigerian supermarket chains?
3. What factors affect the extent of adoption of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains?
4. How can e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains be improved?

The first, second and third research questions with their corresponding objectives focus on explaining e-commerce adoption by supermarket chains in Nigeria, using theories developed in previous studies. Although such theories were primarily developed for technology adoption in different countries, insights that were drawn from them helped to curve a gap for the current study. Therefore, the first three questions concentrate on explaining if an established theory on

the adoption of e-commerce applies in a different context with an underlying intention of extending the theory into a new context. The quantitative method best suits explanation purposes (Creswell, 2003), and is mostly applied to research areas with existing understanding of theory, like in this case, would best serve the researcher's purpose of testing the suitability of the theory in a different context (Igudia, 2015). However, the fourth research question seeks to explore the measures for improving e-commerce adoption levels and sustainability of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains. The researcher therefore needs to gain a deep knowledge of the influencing factors on e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarkets and detailed views of the supermarkets operators on what could be done to promote sustainable high level of e-commerce application in the industry. Hence, the fourth research question was exploratory in nature, and utilised a qualitative approach (Creswell, 2003). Therefore, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods in this study provided better understanding of the research problem, and triangulated insights to answer the research questions (Creswell, 2014).

The second reason for using a mixed research methods approach was to broaden the scope of the research by deepening the investigation (Dawadi, Shrestha and Giri, 2021). This helped to, not only generalise the findings of the study, but also gain a deeper understanding of what the concepts meant to the study participants. Hence, the benefit of collecting quantitative data with close-ended questions and qualitative data with open-ended questions improved the comprehension of the research problem (Creswell, 2003). Collecting quantitative data with questionnaires broadened the study by enabling the researcher to collect data on various elements of the research concepts from different participants, while qualitative data from interviews provided an in-depth knowledge to the research inquiry (Dawadi et al., 2021).

The third reason for using a mixed research method was to offset the limitations in each of the two methods (quantitative and qualitative) as their features are complementary in some respects (Creswell, 2003). Therefore, combining the two methods added value as it allowed the combination of two sets of strengths while also accounting for the drawbacks of each method. Hence, using two data sets in answering the first three research questions resulted in more assurance and broader implications in the conclusion (Dawadi et al., 2021; Maxwell, 2016).

Finally, the fourth rationale for using a mixed research method was to gain insight and realise the benefits of triangulation. The researcher sought to gain a more accurate picture of e-commerce adoption by supermarkets chains in Nigeria. This was achieved by comparing the

findings from the qualitative study to the findings from the quantitative study. In fact, gathering different data sets provided more insights into the research problem. As a result, data triangulation in this study ensured a well-validated conclusion while simultaneously enhancing the trustworthiness of conclusions drawn from one method (Dawadi et al., 2021).

Based on the above explanations, the research method adopted was the concurrent mixed method- quantitative dominant as the researcher placed more emphasis on the quantitative study. In fact, previous studies on the adoption of e-commerce tended to use more of the quantitative approach, as illustrated in table 10.

Table 10: Selected e-commerce adoption studies

S/N	Author(s)	Aim	Location (context)	Method Employed	Sample Size
1	Al-Ayed (2022)	Exploration of e-commerce drivers impact on e-customer loyalty	Saudi Arabia	Quantitative (Online)	247
2	Van Droogenbroeck and Van Hove (2021)	Adoption and usage of e-grocery shopping	Belgium Supermarkets (customers)	Quantitative	560
3	Are, Abidemi, Shehu and Sirajo (2020)	Investigation of the impacts of e-commerce on business performance	SMEs in Kaduna Nigeria	Quantitative	208
4	Lestari, et al. (2020)	Evaluation of e-commerce performance considering innovativeness of the organization and management of knowledge	Indonesian Companies	Mixed	114
5	Omotayo and Omotope (2018)	Investigation of the factors that influence consumers to continue to use online shops	Nigeria	Quantitative	455
6	Yadav and Mahara (2018)	Investigation of the influencing factors on e-commerce uptake by SMEs of wooden handicrafts	India (Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh)	Quantitative (survey)	163

7	Rahayu and Day (2015)	Investigation of e-commerce uptake influencing factors in emerging countries	Indonesia	Quantitative (survey)	292
8	Kurnia et al. (2015)	Examination of the variables that impact SMEs' uptake of e-commerce	Malaysia	Quantitative (survey)	125
9	Kareem, Owomoyela and Oyebamiji (2014)	Exploration of the impacts of e-commerce uptake on supermarkets	Nigeria (Ibadan)	Quantitative	48
10	Adewale, Ayo-Oyebiyi and Adebayo (2013)	Investigation of the variables that impact e-commerce uptake by Nigerian businesses	Nigeria (Lagos)	Quantitative	70
11	Duan et al. (2012)	Exploration of the elements that influence e-market uptake in Australian SMEs	Australia	Quantitative (survey)	212
12	Johnson (2010)	Investigation of factors that affect e-business adoption by organisations	27 European Union member countries	Quantitative (survey)	2,459
13	Tan, Chong, Lin and Eze (2009)	Exploration of the factors that impact the uptake of internet commerce and other problems of e-commerce issues SMEs	Australia	Qualitative	23
14	Eikebrokk and Olsen (2007)	Investigation of factors that influence small businesses B2B trading exchange	Western Australia	Mixed method	211 quant and 7 qual

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

4.4 Research Strategy

A research strategy is an outline of the things the researcher intends to do to answer research question(s). There are eight research strategies that could be selected by a researcher for a study. These include “experiment, survey, archival and documentary research, case study, ethnography, action research, grounded theory and narrative inquiry” (Saunders et al., 2016, p. 178). The experimental and survey strategies are exclusively connected to quantitative studies,

while case study and archival and documentary strategies may be used in either quantitative, qualitative, or mixed method studies. However, a qualitative study can apply any of "action research, case study research, ethnography, grounded theory and narrative research" (Saunders et al., 2016, p. 169). The choice of strategy for a study is guided by the research questions and their corresponding objectives, the coherence with which these questions and objectives link to the research philosophy, research purpose and approach. Also, more pragmatic considerations such as the level of existing knowledge, time, and other resources available to the researcher, and access to prospective participants and other data sources inform the choice of research strategy. It should also be noted that the different strategies should not be considered mutually exclusive. For instance, the survey strategy can be used within a case study, and a few different strategies can be combined within a mixed method design (Saunders et al., 2016).

The survey strategy is the most applied strategy in business and management studies and is employed in this study due to its many advantages. It allows researchers to collect quantitative as well as qualitative data on numerous kinds of research questions (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). It is therefore suitable for this study as the study employed the mixed research method which involves collection of both quantitative and qualitative data. The use of survey strategy in this study will also enable the researcher to economically collect data from a large population, and it facilitates generalisable and replicable results due to its use of a very structured methodology (Rahayu, 2015; Nasco et al., 2008). It is suitable for testing relationship between variables and appropriate for answering the 'what', 'where', 'who', 'how many' and 'how much' questions (Saunders et al., 2016). Also, the current study is a cross sectional study which is carried out within a short period of time. It is, therefore, reasonable to apply the survey strategy as it facilitates collection of data from large population within a short period of time.

4.5. Research Design

Research design implies a researcher's comprehensive strategy for responding to research questions in his/her study (Saunders et al., 2009). It provides a connection between the research questions, data collection (Yin, 2003) and the probable conclusion (Saunders et al., 2009). The main components of the adopted research method are further discussed in the following sections.

The data for the quantitative and qualitative studies were collected concurrently, analysed separately, and integrated in the discussion. The quantitative design was used to answer the first, second and third research questions, while the qualitative design was used to answer the fourth research question and further elaborate the findings from the quantitative study.

4.6 Time Horizon

Time horizon in research can be generally classified into longitudinal research and cross-sectional research. Longitudinal research studies a phenomenon at different points (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). According to Saunders et al. (2019), longitudinal research studies a series of events over a given period and it allows a researcher to study change and development and may also provide a control measure to the researcher over some of the variables under investigation. In contrast, cross-sectional research studies a phenomenon (or phenomena) at a given time. Previous studies suggest that cross-sectional studies often a survey strategy but may also use a mixed method or qualitative strategies (Saunders et al., 2019). Longitudinal studies are more cost, time and effort demanding than cross-sectional studies (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). However, a researcher should not rely only on this in making a choice of time horizon, but also consider research purposes, research questions, research strategy and available time for the study (Rahayu, 2015; Saunders et al., 2009).

Considering the above discussions, this researcher adopted a cross-sectional time horizon. This is because a cross-sectional time horizon often applies to a survey strategy as adopted research by this research. This is consistent with Bryman (2012, p. 59), when he remarked that “the cross-sectional design is often called a survey design”. Furthermore, being academic research, this study was time constrained, hence, cross-sectional time horizon is more suitable (Saunders et al., 2009).

4.7 Sampling Design

Sampling is a technique that enables data to be collected from a subset of a population that represents a greater population. According to Saunders et al., (2012, cited in Alroushan, 2014, p. 179), five sequences that are considered for sampling design are “target population, sample frame, sample method, sample unit and sample size.”

4.7.1 Target Population

According to Creswell (2012, p.142), target population is “a group of individuals (or group of organisations) with some common defining characteristic that researcher can identify to study.” He argues that the researcher needs to determine the target population, which is the group that will be investigated. A subset of the target population, otherwise known as sample, would be chosen to represent the whole population. For this study, the target population were the supermarket chains in Nigeria.

4.7.2 Sample Frame

Sample frame is a list of the target population members from which sample can be drawn (Bruce, Stevens and Loudon, 2002). Sampling design is aimed at selecting research participants from the target population. Sample frames for studies are usually obtained from the internet, yellow pages, directory of phone numbers, governmental bodies or other reliable sources associated with the study's target population. Although an established list of Nigerian supermarket chains could not be found anywhere, the Wikipedia and Revolvly websites assessed on January 11, 2020, provided a list of 31 supermarket chains in Nigeria. However, a screening of the listed supermarket chains by the researcher brought the list down to 21 supermarket chains as some of the supermarket chains on the list had shut down, and some were excluded because of their size and mode of operation. Those excluded failed to meet the inclusion criteria. The screening was conducted following the researcher's background investigation on the listed supermarket chains and the results of the pilot study. Supermarkets that had less than N20 million asset per store and a maximum of three stores were excluded. However, multinational supermarket chains with only two stores in Nigeria were retained in the list. Screening was done to prevent data skewing which would otherwise have caused a problem in the statistical analysis of the quantitative data. Moreover, the excluded supermarket chains did not satisfactorily meet the Collins' Dictionary of Business definition of a chain store as a multibranch retail business "operating a network of stores each located strategically in catchment areas serving large populations" (Pass et al., 2005, n.p.).

4.7.3 Sampling Method

Sampling method is a measure employed to identify the unit of analysis and means of obtaining data from a sample of the target audience (Saunders et al., 2012). Two major sampling methods are available: probability sampling and non-probability sampling. Choosing an ideal method of sampling for a study requires consideration of certain factors which include: the nature of the study, samples availability as well as the availability of time and financial resources. Since there were only 21 supermarket chains from which data could be collected, this research considered the entire population for data collection in both the quantitative and qualitative studies.

4.7.4 Sampling Unit

Sampling unit is defined as "one of the units into which an aggregate is divided or regarded as divided for the purpose of sampling, each unit being regarded as individual and indivisible when the selection is made" (Dodge, 2003, p. 360). The managers of supermarket chains in

Nigeria were identified as the sampling unit. This was because the managers in the supermarkets were the ones that had sufficient knowledge in the e-commerce activities of the supermarkets.

4.7.5 Sample Size

In any empirical study, using the right sample size is critical, as using the wrong sample size might lead to poor results (Bartlett, Burton and Peim, 2001). However, many researchers opined that larger sample size reduces the probability of errors in findings generalisation; and a larger sample size would more likely produce normal distribution during data analysis (Alrousan, 2014; Creswell, 2012; Saunders et al., 2012). Since there are only 21 valid supermarket chains from which data could be collected, the entire population is considered for data collection in both the quantitative and qualitative study. In the quantitative study, 10 managers were chosen from the various stores of each of the 21 supermarket chains making a total of 210 respondents. Hence, the sample size for the quantitative study was 210 respondents.

For the qualitative study, Patton (1990) posited that the research objectives, available time, and available resources would determine the appropriate sample size. Morse (1994) recommended the use of a minimum of six participants in the sample for phenomenology research, while Creswell (1998) suggested the use of five to 25 participants for the same phenomenology research, but 20 to 30 participants for grounded theory. Bertaux (1981) opined that 15 is the minimum acceptable sample for every qualitative research. However, Mason (2010) maintained that the concept of saturation should be the guiding principle. However, saturation is often achieved with 15 to 16 interviews in most qualitative studies, although Medin and Ross (2005, cited in Mason, 2010) claimed to have reliably established a consensus with as little as ten informants in some of their studies. Since there were only 21 supermarket chains from which data could be collected, the researcher interviewed one manager from each of the supermarket chains. The researcher successfully interviewed 15 managers from different supermarket chains.

4.8 Data Collection

Data can be collected using different methods which include interviews, observations, questionnaires, and use of secondary data (Saunders et al., 2012; Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). The use of secondary data implies the researcher employs data obtained by another person or group or organisation for a different purpose. Therefore, secondary data was not considered a very good option for this study because of different limitations associated with secondary data.

For instance, the definitions and terms in secondary data may not be appropriate for certain studies, and the quality of data collected by other persons may not be guaranteed. Hence, this researcher considered that it was inappropriate to use secondary data for this study except for the purpose of the literature review. Observation method refers to data collection through monitoring, studying, documenting, as well as analysing and interpreting behaviour, action, or event, in a systematic way (Rahayu, 2015). The researcher considered the observation method unsuitable for this study because of its drawbacks with respect to time, financial costs, ethical issues, difficulty in gaining access, observation bias and data recording difficulty (Rahayu, 2015).

Other data collection techniques include the use of questionnaire and interview. The interview entails data collection by directly asking people specific questions about the topic of the research, paying attention to their responses, and documenting them (Saunders et al., 2012). The questionnaire relates to data collection using a “preformulated written set of questions to which respondents record their answers, usually within rather closely defined alternatives” (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013, p. 147). Based on the above explanations, the questionnaire can be viewed as being like the interview in terms of how data is collected, as they both gather data from participants using a set of questions. However, the interview involves direct interaction between the interviewer and the participant either face to face or by voice or video calls. Conversely, the questionnaire technique does not demand a direct interaction as it could be distributed by mail, e-mail, or the internet, and participants can complete the questionnaire without a direct interaction with the researcher. Both the questionnaire and interview techniques are good fit for explanatory and exploratory studies, and they are both frequently applied in a survey strategy (Rahayu, 2015). Moreover, Bryman (2012) remarked that the questionnaire and interview are the main modes for administering a survey strategy. Hence, the two techniques were deemed fit for this study with the questionnaire used for data collection in the quantitative study and the interview used in the qualitative study. These two techniques are further discussed in the sub-sections that follow.

4.8.1 Questionnaire

Sekaran and Bougie (2013, p. 147) defined questionnaire as “a preformulated written set of questions to which respondents record their answers, usually within rather closely defined alternatives.” In more general terms, Saunders et al. (2012) refers to a questionnaire as any data gathering procedure in which all participants must answer the very same series of questions in

a specific sequence. They also consider it to be among the key methods of information gathering in survey research strategy.

According to Saunders et al. (2012), questionnaires can be classified into two: self-completed questionnaires and interviewer-completed questionnaires, based on the way they are delivered, collected, or returned. Self-completed questionnaires are completed by the respondents and can be distributed and collected by post (mail/postal questionnaires); by electronic means using internet (internet-based questionnaires) or intranet (intranet-based questionnaires); or directly handed to the respondents and collected by hand from them (delivery and collection questionnaires). Interviewer-completed questionnaires are completed by the researcher based on the responses provided by the respondents. The responses may be obtained from the participants over the telephone or during a physical meeting with the participant (Rahayu, 2015).

The choice of questionnaire type to use in a study depend on several factors which include respondents' characteristics, types, and number of questions, required sample size and available time for collection (Rahayu, 2015; Saunders et al., 2012). The self-completed questionnaire was used by the current study. This is because the self-completed questionnaire was found to be less time demanding, cheaper, and more convenient for respondents than the interviewer-completed questionnaire. Further, the responses are not influenced by the interviewer effect or interviewer variability (Bryman, 2012). This method was selected because it is also the most widely used primary data gathering method in e-commerce studies (Rahayu, 2015).

As mentioned earlier, "self-completed questionnaire can be categorised in three ways: postal questionnaire, internet or intranet questionnaire or delivery and collection questionnaire" (Rahayu, 2015, p. 135). This study used the delivery and collection method. This is because the delivery and collection method yield higher response rate than postal questionnaire and provides for a better sample control and a clear understanding of the nature of non-response bias (Lovelock, Stiff, Cullwick and Kaufman, 1976).

4.8.1.1 Operationalisation of Constructs

According to Ary et al. (2002), operationalisation is assigning meaning to a construct through specification of operations that need to be performed by the researcher to manipulate or measure the construct. They added that researchers must find variables from a range of sources that best describe the research problem being addressed by the study. They equally pointed out

that operationalisation of constructs minimizes the disparity between the observable and the theoretical. The variables in this study were adopted from previous studies, as discussed in the literature review chapter. The ‘e-commerce adoption levels’ were identified as the dependent variables, while ‘Innovation attributes’ (technological factors), ‘organisational factors’, ‘managerial factors’ and ‘environmental (market environment) factors’ were pinpointed as the independent variables. Since these variables need to be defined in a measurable and meaningful manner, they are translated through operationalization.

Creswell (2012) suggested borrowing constructs if they have been measured in previous studies, as it is easier, faster, and even better to do so. The concepts as well as the operational definition and measurement of the constructs used in this study with their sources are presented in appendix A2.

4.8.1.2 Questionnaire Design and Measurement

Questionnaire design and measurement is a crucial part of part of research as a well-designed questionnaire improves the response rate, as well as the validity and reliability of the data collected (Saunders et al., 2012). Therefore, conscientiousness is needed in the designing, composition and revision of the questionnaire questions and its layout. A pilot study was conducted to test the survey instruments, and data analysis techniques. This also helped to ensure the appropriateness of the developed questionnaire’s format and ensure that the topic and questions were understood by the participants (Bruce et al., 2002).

The questionnaire as illustrated in appendix A1, had 17 questions which were grouped into three parts. The content of the questions, their lengths and clarity had a major impact on the response rate. The questions were meticulously constructed and reviewed to boost the rate of response. The questionnaires were dispatched with a cover letter that described the purpose of the study and researcher’s contact details. The cover letter also explained that participation was voluntary and that personal/organisational information as well as data provided would be treated with the strictest confidence and only used for the purpose of the study.

Since the participants were managers in supermarket chains, the questionnaire was designed to effectively harness the required data from them. Part 1 (Question 1 to Question 8) was designed to capture the company’s and respondent’s demographic profile. The first sub-part (Q1 to Q4) captures the company information such as years of operation, number of branches, number of employees and branch’s total asset, while the second sub-part (Q5 to Q8) captures the respondent’s profile such as level of education, age, active length of contract and gender. Part

2 (Q9) addresses the current e-commerce adoption level, which is a dependent variable that addresses the first research question. Part 1 and Part 2 questions were multichotomous and were measured using a nominal scale to facilitate classification and categorisation of the data being examined. Parts 3 and 4 addressed the independent variables. Part 3 (Q10) addressed the second research question by evaluating the respondents' views on the relative benefits of adopting e-commerce to their company. Part 4 (Q11 to Q18) addressed the third research question by enquiring on other factors that affect e-commerce adoption such as technological (attributes of innovation), organisational, managerial, and environmental (market environment) factors. The independent variables in parts 3 and 4 were measured using an interval scale, that is, a five-point Likert scale questions ranging from count 1 (which represents strongly disagree) to count 5 (which represents strongly agree).

The use of five-point Likert scale in measuring the independent variables was due to its suitability in measuring individual differences in perceptions and attitudes (Sekaran, 2003). Also, Likert scale is believed to be the most frequently used questioning structure for gathering data on opinions (Alrousan, 2014). Furthermore, it facilitated easy understanding and fast completion of the questionnaire by the respondents. The responses obtained with a Likert scale can be readily inputted and worked with in a variety of approaches and tools used in statistical analysis (Malhotra, 2010).

4.8.1.3 Questionnaire Administration

Data collection with the questionnaire started in February 2020 and lasted for one month. The qualitative data collection lasted up to five months due to the Covid 19 pandemic. Data collection with the questionnaires involved personal delivery of questionnaires to prospective participants, collection and follow ups. Hand delivery and collection method was used to save time and increase response rate (Saunders et al., 2012). Two hundred and ten questionnaires were distributed, but only 184 were returned. The forms that were returned were reviewed for completeness, and a total of 16 questionnaire forms were found unusable after data cleaning and screening, resulting in 168 useable forms, and a response rate of 80%.

4.8.2 Interview

As previously discussed, in addition to the self-completed questionnaire, this study also employed semi-structured interviews in data collection. The use of interviews helped the researcher to explore respondents' answers and gain a deeper understating of their opinions on e-commerce adoption by asking them specific questions on the subject matter.

The semi-structured interviews which are more commonly employed in explanatory research is instrumental in explaining the reason for a decision, an attitude, or an opinion about the emerging themes from the questionnaire. On the other hand, an in-depth interview which is more commonly employed in exploratory studies can be employed for a deep exploration of a contemporary or novel area of research interest (Saunders et al., 2012). Hence, the semi-structured interview was used.

According to Saunders et al. (2012), researchers can conduct a semi-structured interview in three ways which include the use of telephone, face to face, and intranet and internet mediated interviews. A face-to-face interview was originally intended for this study due to its facilitation of in-depth data collection and thorough understanding as the facial expression and body language of the interviewee are more clearly seen and empathised. However, because of the Covid-19 pandemic, the researcher could not conduct a face-to-face interview with some of the participants. A telephone interview method was used to collect data from six participants whom the researcher could not meet face to face due to the covid restrictions. The researcher had a face-to-face interview with the other nine participants.

4.8.2.1 Interview Sampling Method

Three major decisions are involved in interview sampling process. These include deciding the sampling frame, determining the appropriate sampling size, and selecting the samples. The sample size and sampling frame have been addressed in Section 4.7. In selecting the samples for the interview, the researcher considered the entire population, and intended to interview one manager from each of the 21 supermarket chains. However, only 15 managers were eventually interviewed since participation was voluntary. The participants in the interview were from different supermarket chains.

4.8.2.2 Conducting the Interview

Being a semi structured interview, standard questions were prepared but asked in different ways to different participants according to the progression of the interview. There were occasional digressions in the conversations based on the participants' responses to the interview questions. The conversations lasted for about 35 minutes on the average and the responses were either recorded or written down by the researcher based on the nature of consent obtained from the respective participants. The following questions were prepared for the semi-structured interview, and this served as an interview guide.

1. What is the background of your company (location, years of existence, number of branches, number of employees, total asset)?

2. What is your background (sex, age, position, years of experience, highest academic qualification)?
3. Does your company employ e-commerce in your business operations?
4. What is the current level of e-commerce application in your company?
5. Do you consider e-commerce beneficial to your company?
6. What benefits has your company enjoyed (or would likely enjoy) from e-commerce adoption?
7. Do you have challenges in your application of e-commerce?
8. What are the factors that influence your level of e-commerce application?
9. In your opinion, what do you think could be done to improve e-commerce application levels and ensure continued use of high-level e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains?

4.9 Data Analysis Method

The collected data for quantitative and qualitative studies were subjected to further analysis. For the quantitative study, three major data analysis were conducted. This included descriptive analysis, factor analysis, and regression (inferential) analysis. Following the coding of the data in SPSS, data cleansing and data quality checks were first performed before other data analysis procedures. This involved checking for missing data, checking for outliers, conducting normality test, and checking for multicollinearity. Following the data cleansing and data quality check, reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha value assessment method. Descriptive analysis was done systematically, according to the different research objectives. Factor analysis (Principal Component Analysis) was further performed on the factors affecting different adoption levels of e-commerce by the supermarkets, which was the third research objective. The factor analysis served for both dimension reduction and construct validity checks. Following the removal of some construct items in the factor analysis section, final reliability assessment was done using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability methods, before proceeding to multinomial logistic regression for inferential statistics where the proposed hypotheses were tested. SPSS was used to analyse the quantitative data set. Justification for the different analysis methods, and how they were conducted are discussed in the sub sections that follow.

For the qualitative study, thematic analysis was used. This helped to collaborate the assertions that emerged from the quantitative study. This study adapted the thematic analysis process described in Kiger and Varpio (2020, p. 1) which involved "familiarizing yourself with the

data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report". A repeated active reading of transcribed recordings was done to become familiar with the data. While reviewing each participant's transcript, words and phrases with comparable meanings (meaning units) were noted and given codes (Belotto, 2018; Graneheim and Lundman, 2004). Themes were identified by analysing the connections between these meaning units. This study employed the "structural coding" method in which passages are annotated with terms related to the research questions (Belotto, 2018, p. 2624). This was particularly important because the interview questions were structured, just like the questionnaires, to address the different research objectives. The results from the thematic analysis are presented in a tabular form in the findings chapter and compared with the findings from the quantitative study for each research objective. Both the quantitative study and qualitative study findings are integrated in the discussion chapter and compared with findings from previous studies.

4.9.1 Data Error Check Method

Data collected data need must be checked for errors before using them for further analysis. This was done using the SPSS software. The possible causes of data errors include data mistyping and wrong classification of data. These errors are detectable by the maximum and minimum values check to ensure they fall within the expected range for each variable, and by checking the total number of valid and missing values. This study used the maximum and minimum values as well as the total number of valid and missing cases in checking for any errors in the data.

4.9.2 Missing Data Check Method

Missing data occurs when a research participant fails to respond to either the entire question or some of the questions possibly due to unwillingness to provide sensitive information, time constraint, or poor understanding of the questions (Alrousan, 2014; Saunders et al., 2012). Some researchers have proposed a few approaches to address missing data. These include conditional means estimation, mean substitution, list-wise deletion, pair-wise deletion, imputation based on expectation maximization algorithm, multiple imputation, and imputation based on regression (Alrousan, 2014; Schlomer, Bauman and Card, 2010; Paul, 2005). In the current study, all the questionnaires with incomplete data were excluded to avoid problems associated with missing data.

4.9.3 Outliers Check Method

An outlier can be defined as “a case with such an extreme value on one variable (a univariate outlier) or such a strange combination of scores on two or more variables (a multivariate outlier) that it distorts statistics” (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013, p. 72). In fact, outliers are observations, not essentially errors, which are far off the main body of the data set and do not conform to the assumed model (Todorov, Templ and Filzmoser, 2010). Hence, outliers can negatively impact statistical analysis, lowering the study’s statistical power in several ways like raising the variance of error.

Univariate outliers can be detected from a data set either by visual inspection or by using a statistical approach. Visual inspection involves the use of the graphical approach such as histograms and box plots, while the statistical approach involves the calculation of the standard scores (Z-scores), for all the variables (Alrousan, 2104). In the current study, the statistical approach was used to assess the data set for univariate outliers by calculating the Z-scores for each variable. After univariate outliers’ detection, the data set was further examined for multivariate outliers. Unlike univariate outliers, the extremity of the multivariate outliers is not necessarily along a single coordinate. Their deviation could be away from the multivariate structure developed by the greater number of the observations (Todorov et al., 2010). This study used the Mahalanobis distance which measures an observations number of standard deviations from the mean of a data set distribution (Ghorbani, 2019), to examine the data set for multivariate outliers.

4.9.4 Normality Assessment Method

Normality test is used to check for normal distribution of the sampled data collected using the questionnaire. It is essential for further statistical analysis, especially in multivariate analysis which was conducted by the researcher. Normality assumes normal distribution of the independent variables and sampling distribution (Field 2009). Non-normality would significantly diminish statistical power in the regression analysis. Hence, a normality test was essential. Also, non-normality weakens the efficiency of standard errors, and may result in wrong deductions (Alrousan, 2014). Nevertheless, non-normality could be rectified by mathematical transformation approaches like square root, inverse, and logarithm. The deviation from normality can be checked graphically or statistically. Graphical assessment involves the use of histogram or normality plot, while statistical assessment, which was used in this study, involves the use of skewness and kurtosis (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019; Alrousan, 2014).

Different researchers have varied opinions on the acceptable absolute skewness and kurtosis index values. Islam, (2019) posited that the skewness of a normal distribution is zero, and the kurtosis is three. However, many researchers agreed that an absolute skewness index value higher than 3.0 is considered to be extremely skewed (Chou and Bentler, 1995; Kline, 1993). Also, Kline (1993) further suggests that an absolute kurtosis value greater than 10.0 is considered problematic and a value greater than 20.0 is considered an exceedingly serious glitch.

4.9.5 Multicollinearity and Singularity Assessment Method

Multicollinearity is the existence of high correlation between two or more explanatory variables, while singularity is the existence of perfect correlation between the independent variables. Multicollinearity in a data set causes problem in research as it makes it difficult to predict the specific explanatory variable responsible for a particular variation in the dependent variable. It can also increase the variance estimates of the parameters and lead to numerical complications in obtaining a regression solution (Alrousan 2014; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013; O'brien, 2007). Hence, it is recommended to check for the presence of multicollinearity in a data set before carrying out further analysis, particularly regression analysis.

There are three typical approaches for checking whether multicollinearity exists in a data set. The first method is by using correlation matrix to assess the correlation among the explanatory variables. A squared correlation value less than 0.90 is considered non problematic (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). The other two approaches for assessing multicollinearity regarding regression analysis involve assessing both the 'Tolerance Value' and the 'Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)' (Alrousan, 2014; Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson and Tatham 2010; O'brien, 2007).

The tolerance value denotes how much variation in an explanatory variable that is not influenced by another explanatory variable. Its value ranges from zero to one, with values lower than 0.10 indicating the occurrence of multicollinearity. On the other hand, the VIF is the multiplicative inverse of tolerance (Tolerance^{-1}). VIF values above 10 signifies the presence of multicollinearity (Alrousan, 2014; Hair et al., 2010). In the current study, the data was assessed for multicollinearity using the correlation matrix in addition to the tolerance value and variance inflation factor to ensure the dataset was free of multicollinearity.

4.9.6 Reliability Assessment Method

Reliability, according to Carmines and Zeller (2008), is the degree to which any measurement, test or experiment produces the same outcome on repeated trial. This implies stability and consistency of the measurement scale over time. Reliability check in research is essential to ensure a high research stability and consistency scores, and to eliminate measurement errors (Alrousan, 2014). The Cronbach's alpha method was used to check the reliability of the research data, as it is the most common practice applied in the assessment of scale homogeneity based on multiple items construct scale (Alrousan, 2014; Creswell, 2012), as was the case in the current study. According to Field (2009), the effect of deleting an item with poor internal consistency on Cronbach's alpha could be assessed by using the 'Cronbach's alpha if item deleted' concept. Squires, Estabrooks, Newburn-Cook and Gierl (2011) suggested dropping items if removing them can increase the Cronbach's alpha value substantially by up to 10%. Also, (Field, 2009) recommended using item-total correlation, in addition to Cronbach's alpha value, to assess the internal consistency if item is deleted. Nevertheless, Kline (1993) argued that the item-total correlation value is prone to bias since it is affected by the sample size and proposed calculating the corrected item-total correlation to mitigate the problem. The corrected item-total correlation reveals how a particular item correlates with the overall items score. This study additionally used composite reliability assessment to further verify the constructs' reliability.

4.9.7 Validity Assessment Method

Validity measures the extent to which the concept of study is captured by the measurement developed by the researcher (Bryman, 2012). A validity test also confirms the quality of a research. The validity of the current study was assessed by considering the content and the construct validity.

Content validity, according to Polit and Beck (2006, p. 490), is defined as "the degree to which set of items, taken together, constitute an adequate operational definition of a construct." To ensure the content validity of this study, the researcher conducted an extensive literature review prior to operationalisation of constructs whose measurements were adapted from similar studies in which reliability and validity had been considered. Furthermore, the researcher conducted a pilot study, and the outcome was used to improve the questions wording and the questionnaire layout.

Construct validity, on the other hand, relates to the extent and effectiveness of an instrument in measuring a theoretical construct, and it has two sub forms which are convergent and discriminate validities. Convergent validity is attained when two or more instruments measuring the same notion have a positive correlation, whereas discriminate validity applies when there is low correlation between two or more instruments that measure different ideas (Saunders et al., 2009). The researcher used factor analysis to assess both subtypes of construct validity. The constructs used in this study were adapted from earlier related research and were verified by factor analysis in those studies. Nevertheless, the current study had to conduct factor analysis again because its context differed from those of the earlier studies. Also, the confirmation of this study's validity with factor analysis enabled the generalisation of the research findings. The average variance extracted (AVE) value was computed for each construct to further assess the discriminant and convergent validity. Also, the use of two data collection methods promoted the construct validity as the result from the semi-structured interview was used to validate the result from the questionnaire findings.

4.9.8 Regression Analysis Method

The choice of logistic regression was based on several reasons. Firstly, logistic regression is used to forecast the outcome of a categorical dependent (discrete outcomes) with the use of one or more predictor variables. Secondly, logistic regression analysis is comparable to multiple regression, with their differences being that the dependent variable in logistic regression can be either continuous, categorical, or a mix, but multiple regression requires a continuous dependent variable (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013; Field, 2009). According to Berry (1993, cited in Field, 2009), there must be a linear relationship in the observed data for a valid linear regression model, and a categorical outcome variable violates this assumption. Hence, a linear regression cannot be applied in a data set when the dependent variable is categorical. However, the logistic regression equation overcomes the problem of violating linearity assumption by expressing the equation of the multiple linear regression in logarithmic terms known as logit (Field, 2009). Lastly, because logistic regression is robust, it allowed more flexibility than the alternative statistical tools like discriminant analysis.

Comparing logistic regression and discriminant analysis, Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) as referenced in Alrousan (2014) argued that the assumptions of the discriminant analysis necessitate normal distribution of data, and linearity or variance uniformity for the independent variables. Whereas logistic regression gives a valid result even with non-normally distributed data. Also, the independent variables are required to be continuous in discriminant analysis,

while logistic regression permits a mix of nominal, continuous and categorical independent variable. Furthermore, both logistic regression and discriminant analysis produce similar outcome when the sample size is 50 or more (Pohar, Blas and Turk, 2004). However, logistic regression is favoured if the dependent variable has three categories or less, while discriminant analysis is favoured when the dependent variable has categories exceeding three. Therefore, logistic regression was used instead of discriminant analysis as the data set met all the above discussed assumptions for logistic regression better than those of discriminant analysis. Logistic regression is of two types. The first type, binary logistic regression, is applied in analysis where the dependent variable consists of two categories. However, the second one, multinomial logistic regression, which is an extension of the first one is applied when more than two categories are involved in the dependent variable (Field, 2009). Since the current study's dependent variables had three valid categories (e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise) as evidenced in analysis/findings chapter, the study employed the multinomial logistic regression.

4.10 Pilot Study

Good research requires a pilot study as it enhances the effectiveness and precision of data collected, as well as the credibility of the research results. Previous studies suggest that a pilot study is also instrumental in assessing the validity of the questions in the questionnaire and the reliability of the collected data (Alrousan, 2014; Saunders et al., 2012). It further provides early warning indicators of any connected flaws in the intended research, such as the inadequacy of the employed method or instruments. According to Bell, Brooks and Prokopczuk (2013), pilot study provides feedback on the clarity of questionnaire's instructions, the level of difficulty of its questions, time needed to complete the questionnaire as well as other respondents' comments that could improve the questionnaire.

Researchers have different views on the minimum number of participants required for a pilot study. According to Fink (2003b, cited in Saunders et al., 2012), 10 or more target participants is adequate for a pilot study. Whereas Baker (1994, cited in Alrousan, 2014) suggested the use of 10-20 percent of the total sample size of the research. In this study, the pilot study was conducted with twelve participants for the quantitative study and two participants for the qualitative study. Consequent to the pilot study, minor corrections were made in terms of word rephrasing and sentence restructuring to make the questions simpler, more understandable and to reduce the time required to respond to the questions.

4.11 Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval is a prerequisite for any research study that requires direct/indirect human participation or elicits other ethical concerns owing to its potential social and/or environmental implications. Human participation is almost inevitable in business and management research, and ethical issues are most prominent in research that involve human participation regardless of whether it is a person-to-person conducted research or not (Saunders et al., 2016).

Although there was no personal/sensitive information required in the data that was collected, the research however enquired about business strategies and concerns which the participants may consider sensitive and confidential. Consequently, the researcher sought and obtained ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland before proceeding with the research. All data sets were collected and stored in accordance with agreed ethical research guidelines.

The researcher was careful not to cause, intentionally or unintentionally, psychological, financial, social or any other form of harm to the respondents during data collection and communication. The participant's information sheet was given to the respondents prior to data collection. This outlined the purpose of the research, what was expected of the participants, and equally described the nature of participation as voluntary, and the participant's right to withdraw their consent at any point. It also guaranteed the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants and their companies. It equally explained that the collected data would only be used for the purpose of the study and that the outcome of the research would be made available to them if they indicated their interest in it

4.12 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented the research methodology and the components therein. The chapter explained how the study and critical review of different philosophical views led to the selection of pragmatism as the most suitable philosophical approach. A mixed methods approach was the most appropriate method of research because it helped to satisfactorily answer all the research questions. Data was collected using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews for the quantitative and qualitative data collections, respectively. In addition to discussing the research methodology and research method, the chapter also discussed sampling design, data collection, data analysis method, pilot study and ethical consideration for this research. The next chapter presents the findings.

CHAPTER FIVE: RESEARCH FINDINGS

5.0 Introduction

The prior chapter detailed the methodology for this research. The current chapter presents the research findings from the quantitative and qualitative studies. It begins with pre-analysis data processing which involves checking for data errors, missing data, and outliers. It then moves to check for multicollinearity and assess normality. Cronbach's alpha was used to conduct the initial reliability test to measure the internal consistency of the items used in the research constructs.

Descriptive analysis was used to narrate the demographic profile as well as the quantitative and qualitative findings on the current adoption levels, benefits of e-commerce, factors affecting the extent of e-commerce adoption within supermarkets in Nigeria, and measures to improve e-commerce application levels and sustainability. Factor analysis (principal component analysis) was used as a dimension reduction technique, as well as an assessment tool for construct validity. A composite reliability test was then conducted to determine the final reliability assessment on items retained from the factor analysis. Finally, a multinomial logistic regression was conducted in inferential statistics to test the research hypothesis. The IBM statistical tool, SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 25 was used in the quantitative statistical analysis in this study.

5.1 Data Cleansing and Data Quality Check

Some of the target participants for this research were unwilling to take part in the study due to a lack of interest, time limitations, and reluctance to share 'sensitive' data for the company. Therefore, only 184 questionnaires were returned from the 210 targeted respondents in the quantitative part of the study. The questionnaires returned were reviewed for completeness. A total of 16 questionnaires were found to be unusable after data cleaning and screening, resulting in 168 useable questionnaires. Hence, the response rate was 80%. The data collected from the 168 usable questionnaires was further processed to ensure their accuracy, representability, and suitability for further data analysis. For the qualitative study, 15 top managers from 15 different supermarket chains were interviewed.

The pre-analysis data processing performed on the data set for cleansing purposes included checking for data error, missing data, and outliers. Other quality checks conducted before the major analysis included normality test, multicollinearity check, and reliability assessment.

5.1.1 Data Error and Missing Data Check

Data errors which may occur due to data mistyping or wrong classification of data type were checked by ensuring that the maximum and minimum values for each variable fell within the expected range, and by checking the total number of valid and missing cases. All the data set scores in this study were within the expected score ranges for the respective variables. Hence, the data set for this study is devoid of such errors. To avoid problems associated with missing data, all the questionnaires with incomplete data were excluded.

5.1.2 Outliers

A statistical approach for assessing the data set for univariate outliers by calculating the Z-scores for each variable was used. The literature suggests that a data entry with a Z-score greater than 3.29 or less than -3.29 may be considered an outlier (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). The minimum and maximum Z-score values result presented in table 11 illustrates that some outliers were present in variables RA5, RA6, RA7 and RA8, with the most negative Z-score value being -3.61091. The most positive Z-score value for the data set was 2.88552. However, the data point with this most positive value is not an outlier since the value is less than 3.29. On examining the Z-score values for the variables that contain the outliers, the outliers were found to exist in only entry 2. Hence, entry 2 was deleted to remove univariate outliers from the data set.

Table 11: Minimum and maximum Z-score values

	Minimum	Maximum		Minimum	Maximum
Z-score: RA1	-2.02216	1.27612	Z-score: FBR2	-1.52459	1.5429
Z-score: RA2	-2.83921	0.82992	Z-score: FBR3	-1.54466	1.2658
Z-score: RA3	-3.18225	0.79261	Z-score: FBR4	-1.58209	1.2657
Z-score: RA4	-3.16309	0.80257	Z-score: FBR5	-1.1806	1.8475
Z-score: RA5	-3.61091	0.63128	Z-score: TMS1	-2.10069	1.1976
Z-score: RA6	-3.43421	0.68684	Z-score: TMS2	-1.90205	1.2003
Z-score: RA7	-3.38215	0.70563	Z-score: TMS3	-1.95814	1.2513
Z-score: RA8	-3.30963	0.73414	Z-score: TMS4	-2.17264	1.2386
Z-score: RA9	-1.63021	1.17876	Z-score: TMS5	-2.15758	1.1079
Z-score: RA10	-2.48900	1.10029	Z-score: MKA1	-1.39132	0.7145
Z-score: RA11	-2.81789	1.11079	Z-score: MKA2	-1.30365	0.7625
Z-score: RA12	-2.56834	1.48948	Z-score: MKA3	-2.70530	1.6027
Z-score: RA13	-2.22688	1.02630	Z-score: MKA4	-3.08713	0.9886

Z-score: COMP1	-1.19425	0.83236	Z-score: MKA5	-2.53531	0.8586
Z-score: COMP2	-2.52496	0.93784	Z-score: MEP1	-2.42303	2.4230
Z-score: COMP3	-2.41520	0.93814	Z-score: MEP2	-1.88291	0.9541
Z-score: COMP4	-3.18112	0.97247	Z-score: MEP3	-1.56041	2.6678
Z-score: COMP5	-1.72366	1.04739	Z-score: MEP4	-1.52008	1.9078
Z-score: TECR1	-2.17021	0.97285	Z-score: MEP5	-1.42731	1.8131
Z-score: TECR2	-1.95936	0.97968	Z-score: GVS1	-2.01767	1.6937
Z-score: TECR3	-1.83717	1.32841	Z-score: GVS2	-2.41828	1.2639
Z-score: TECR4	-2.22688	1.02630	Z-score: GVS3	-0.7457	2.8855
Z-score: TECR5	-2.35398	0.95538	Z-score: GVS4	-1.72195	1.5468
Z-score: FBR1	-1.28671	1.5390	Z-score: GVS5	-1.89648	1.4052

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

After univariate outliers' detection, the data set was further examined for multivariate outliers. Mahalanobis distance was used to examine each respondent's entry for multivariate outliers. P value less than 0.001 indicates the presence of a multivariate outlier. The result of the Mahalanobis Distance X^2 calculation presented in Appendix B1 shows that only one entry (case 77) contained a multivariate outlier as its p value of 0.00015 was less than 0.001. Hence, entry 77 was removed from further analysis. Consequently, two entries (case 2 and case 77) were deleted from the data set for univariate and multivariate outliers before proceeding with further analysis. The remaining 166 entries were subjected to further quality checks before proceeding to the main data analysis.

5.1.3 Normality Test

A normality test was used to assess the normal distribution of the data set, by determining the skewness and kurtosis values for all the independent variables. The result of the normality test is presented in table 12, and this demonstrates that the skewness and kurtosis values fall within the normal range as they are all below 3 and greater than -3. The skewness lowest and highest values were -0.939 and 0.919 respectively, while the kurtosis lowest and highest values were -1.885 and -0.104, respectively. Hence, there is normal distribution of all items.

Table 12: Normality test result

Construct Name	Item Label	Skewness	Std. Error of Skewness	Kurtosis	Std. Error of Kurtosis	Construct Name	Item Label	Skewness	Std. Error of Skewness	Kurtosis	Std. Error of Kurtosis
Relative Advantage	RA1	-0.150	0.188	-0.490	0.375	Financial Barriers	FBR1	0.122	0.188	-0.989	0.375
	RA2	-0.608	0.188	-0.879	0.375		FBR2	0.006	0.188	-0.645	0.375
	RA3	-0.475	0.188	-1.797	0.375		FBR3	-0.322	0.188	-1.141	0.375
	RA4	-0.422	0.188	-1.844	0.375		FBR4	-0.311	0.188	-1.107	0.375
	RA5	-0.939	0.188	-1.133	0.375		FBR5	0.265	0.188	-0.720	0.375
	RA6	-0.782	0.188	-1.405	0.375	Management Support	TMS1	-0.196	0.188	-0.553	0.375
	RA7	-0.723	0.188	-1.495	0.375		TMS2	-0.240	0.188	-0.648	0.375
	RA8	-0.610	0.188	-1.648	0.375		TMS3	-0.180	0.188	-0.534	0.375
	RA9	-0.260	0.188	-0.960	0.375		TMS4	-0.127	0.188	-0.531	0.375
	RA10	-0.140	0.188	-0.935	0.375		TMS5	-0.296	0.188	-0.634	0.375
	RA11	0.106	0.188	-1.661	0.375	Knowledge & Attitude	MKA1	-0.666	0.188	-1.576	0.375
	RA12	0.065	0.188	-0.952	0.375		MKA2	-0.528	0.188	-1.743	0.375
	RA13	-0.402	0.188	-0.663	0.375		MKA3	0.770	0.188	-0.441	0.375
COMP1	-0.371	0.188	-1.885	0.375	MKA4		-0.760	0.188	-0.346	0.375	
COMP2	-0.481	0.188	-0.750	0.375	MKA5		-0.660	0.188	-0.535	0.375	
Compatibility	COMP3	-0.534	0.188	-0.634	0.375	Market Env. Pressure	MEV1	0.208	0.188	-0.289	0.375
	COMP4	-0.528	0.188	-0.828	0.375		MEV2	-0.561	0.188	-0.818	0.375
	COMP5	-0.424	0.188	-0.952	0.375		MEV3	-0.047	0.188	-0.763	0.375
	TECR1	-0.531	0.188	-0.635	0.375		MEV4	0.012	0.188	-0.104	0.375
	TECR2	-0.529	0.188	-0.771	0.375		MEV5	0.073	0.188	-0.353	0.375
Tech. Readiness	TECR3	-0.136	0.188	-0.547	0.375	Govt & Vendor Support	GVS1	-0.175	0.188	-0.357	0.375
	TECR4	-0.426	0.188	-0.647	0.375		GVS2	-0.264	0.188	-0.727	0.375
	TECR5	-0.545	0.188	-0.600	0.375		GVS3	0.914	0.188	-0.202	0.375
							GVS4	-0.025	0.188	-0.292	0.375
							GVS5	-0.076	0.188	-0.350	0.375

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

5.1.4 Multicollinearity and Singularity

Multicollinearity, which is the occurrence of strong correlation between two or more explanatory variables, was assessed using the Pearson correlation method. The VIF and Tolerance values were further determined to consolidate the result from the Pearson's correlation matrix. The Pearson correlation matrix in table 13, illustrates that there is no high correlation between any two variables as all the Pearson correlation values are below 0.9. Also, the VIF and Tolerance values result presented in table 14, illustrates that the Tolerance values ranged from 0.383 to 0.911, and the VIF ranged from 1.098 to 2.610. This collinearity results further confirmed the absence of multicollinearity in this study as the tolerance values are all greater than 0.10, and the VIF values are all less than 10. The constructs values were tabulated using SPSS before the multicollinearity check by computing the mean values of the respective items used in measuring the constructs.

Table 13: Pearson correlation result

	RA	COMP	TECR	FBR	TMS	MKA	MEP	GVS
RA	1	.582	.547	-.575	.631	.409	.260	.168
COMP	.582	1	.701	-.622	.652	.417	.192	.176
TECR	.547	.701	1	-.641	.618	.379	.230	.155
FBR	-.575	-.622	-.641	1	-.677	-.480	-.207	-.262
TMS	.631	.652	.618	-.677	1	.502	.211	.111
MKA	.409	.417	.379	-.480	.502	1	.199	.201
MEP	.260	.192	.230	-.207	.211	.199	1	.010
GVS	.168	.176	.155	-.262	.111	.201	.010	1

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 14: Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) results

Variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
RA	0.515	1.940
COMP	0.406	2.466
TECR	0.422	2.368
FBR	0.410	2.438
TMS	0.383	2.610
MKA	0.690	1.449
MEP	0.911	1.098
GVS	0.903	1.108

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

5.1.5 Initial Reliability Assessment

Reliability in research implies the precision of the instrument used in measuring the research constructs, and the stability of its result. That is, the repeatability of the result of a measuring instrument when applied under the same circumstances. Reliability assessment in a study is essential to certify that research data is of good quality (Alrousan, 2014). The current study used a multiple item scale in a survey to measure the research constructs. Therefore, the reliability of the study was assessed by using the internal consistency which was evaluated by assessing the inter-item correlations within a scale of a given construct. The internal reliability or consistency formed by a multiple item scale was measured using Cronbach's alpha (Alrousan, 2014; Creswell, 2012). Cronbach's alpha values range from zero to one, with higher values indicating greater reliability.

However, researchers have different opinions on the acceptable values of Cronbach's alpha. Some suggest that a Cronbach's value of 0.7 or above is very well acceptable (Taber, 2018; Ab Hamid, Sami and Mohmad Sidek, 2017; Pallant, 2013; Field, 2009). Berthoud (2000, cited in Bryman, 2012) argued that a value of 0.60 can be considered good for internal validity. Nevertheless, some other researchers posit that some values greater than 0.5 may be weak, but still admissible (Alrousan 2014; Bowling,1997). Table 15 illustrates a rule of thumb for the values from Cronbach's alpha test, that is often used by researchers (Namdeo and Rout, 2016).

Table 15: Cronbach's alpha rule of thumb

Cronbach's Alpha Value	Internal Consistency (Reliability)
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Source: Namdeo and Rout (2016)

Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the internal consistency for the eight independent variables involved in the study. The acceptable cut off value for the Cronbach's Alpha test result in this study was 0.70. Also, the corrected item-total correlation and Cronbach's alpha if item deleted values were computed for all constructs to further assess reliability. The corrected item-total correlation reveals how a specific item correlates with the overall score of the other

items. All items with corrected item-total correlation value less than 0.30 in the item total statistics table were deleted as recommended by many researchers (Field, 2009; Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994; Kline, 1993). Further, items whose Cronbach's alpha when item deleted value was significantly higher than the overall Cronbach's alpha value were considered for deletion. The results of the reliability assessment are presented in table 16, while the item-total statistics for all constructs is presented in table 17.

Table 16: Reliability assessment result

Variables	Number of Items	Initial Cronbach's Alpha	Initial Reliability Strength	Number of Items Removed	Resultant Cronbach's Alpha	Resultant Reliability Strength
Relative Advantage	13	0.832	Good	4	0.903	Excellent
Compatibility	5	0.894	Good	0	0.894	Good
Technological Readiness	5	0.864	Good	0	0.864	Good
Financial Barriers	5	0.853	Good	0	0.853	Good
Top Management Support	5	0.884	Good	0	0.884	Good
Manager's Knowledge and Attitude	5	0.615	Questionable	2	0.819	Good
Market Environment Pressure	5	0.580	Poor	2	0.838	Good
Government and Vendor Support	5	0.194	Unacceptable	3	0.861	Good

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 17: Item total statistics for all constructs

Constructs	Construct Items	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Relative Advantage	RA1	53.783	15.977	.160	.143	.845
	RA2	53.458	13.971	.716	.658	.803
	RA3	53.404	14.279	.703	.733	.806
	RA4	53.416	14.196	.722	.716	.804
	RA5	53.307	14.578	.669	.687	.809
	RA6	53.337	14.710	.608	.703	.813
	RA7	53.349	14.289	.727	.703	.805
	RA8	53.374	14.332	.700	.689	.806
	RA9	53.843	15.357	.227	.156	.844
	RA10	53.621	15.473	.309	.220	.832
	RA11	53.578	14.779	.528	.315	.817
	RA12	54.115	15.411	.198	.161	.849
	RA13	53.633	14.816	.419	.264	.825
Compatibility	COMP1	17.500	4.773	0.782	0.658	0.869
	COMP2	17.621	4.588	0.734	0.597	0.873
	COMP3	17.639	4.511	0.738	0.581	0.872
	COMP4	17.771	4.093	0.753	0.624	0.870
	COMP5	17.831	4.044	0.749	0.615	0.872
Technology Readiness	TECR1	17.283	4.035	0.815	0.710	0.801
	TECR2	17.331	4.053	0.732	0.585	0.822
	TECR3	17.506	5.051	0.379	0.165	0.906
	TECR4	17.295	4.149	0.797	0.739	0.807
	TECR5	17.235	4.314	0.733	0.626	0.823
Financial Barriers	FBR1	9.0783	8.557	0.573	0.371	0.845
	FBR2	9.000	8.521	0.649	0.456	0.832
	FBR3	8.349	6.059	0.800	0.730	0.787
	FBR4	8.331	6.077	0.811	0.741	0.782
	FBR5	9.217	8.728	0.589	0.386	0.844

Top Management Support	TMS1	17.072	4.334	0.644	0.483	0.876
	TMS2	17.108	4.073	0.714	0.550	0.861
	TMS3	17.102	3.971	0.810	0.690	0.837
	TMS4	17.054	4.100	0.801	0.727	0.841
	TMS5	17.012	4.339	0.641	0.594	0.877
Managers Knowledge and Attitude	MKA1	17.420	2.718	0.541	0.515	0.500
	MKA2	17.452	2.673	0.558	0.574	0.490
	MKA3	17.825	3.139	0.268	0.095	0.606
	MKA4	18.036	2.265	0.214	0.069	0.737
	MKA5	17.578	2.512	0.514	0.410	0.489
Market Environment Pressure	MEP1	10.181	3.143	0.164	0.097	0.612
	MEP2	9.355	3.237	0.065	0.126	0.676
	MEP3	11.584	2.317	0.494	0.399	0.423
	MEP4	11.807	2.496	0.576	0.647	0.399
	MEP5	11.819	2.561	0.492	0.630	0.440
Govt and Vendor Support	GVS1	9.590	1.843	0.125	0.574	0.113
	GVS2	9.253	1.996	0.046	0.597	0.216
	GVS3	11.831	2.359	0.046	0.152	0.197
	GVS4	11.193	2.193	0.097	0.582	0.153
	GVS5	11.096	2.148	0.128	0.577	0.124

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

The Cronbach's alpha results in table 16 indicates that the initial scores ranged from 0.194 for the government and vendor support variable to 0.896 for compatibility variable. Out of the eight variables, five had good reliability strengths, one had questionable reliability, one poor, and one unacceptable reliability strength. Notwithstanding that, all the variables' respective items confirmed acceptable reliabilities in past similar studies. However, the initial Cronbach's alpha values for this study revealed that market environment pressure, as well as government and vendor support had poor, and unacceptable internal consistencies, respectively.

The undesirable initial internal consistency strengths in some variables could result from several factors. According to Brown (1997), the three main factors that affect the reliability of surveys are the length of the survey (i.e., the number of questions), the questions' quality and suitability of the questions to the group being sampled. In the current study, the suitability of the questions for the group being sampled may have played a major role in the undesirable

internal consistency result obtained for the market environment pressure, and government and vendor support variables. This is because the target population was the managers of the supermarket chains, which are mostly large-scale enterprises, while the target population for the past similar studies were from small and medium scale enterprises. However, the corrected item-total correlation presented in table 17 was used to remove items responsible for poor internal consistency among the constructs. All the items in the compatibility, technology readiness, financial barrier, and top management support constructs had corrected item-total correlation above 0.3 and were all retained as the constructs equally had good Cronbach's alpha values.

In the relative advantages construct, the initial Cronbach's alpha value was 0.832, and the item-total statistics table shows that RA1, RA9 and RA12 had corrected item-total correlation less than 0.30. These items were removed, and the resultant Cronbach's alpha rose from 0.832 to 0.889, but the corrected item-total correlation for R10 dropped from 0.309 to 0.276 in the new reliability test. Therefore, R10 was subsequently removed before running a final reliability test on relative advantage construct. The resultant Cronbach's alpha value further increased from 0.889 to 0.903. Hence, four items (RA1, RA9, RA10 and RA12) in the relative advantage constructs were excluded from further analysis.

For the managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce construct, the corrected item-total correlation for MKA3 and MKA4 were below 0.30. Hence, they were excluded from further analysis, and the resultant Cronbach's alpha value after their deletion increased from 0.615 to 0.819. In the market environment pressure construct, the corrected item-total correlation for MEP1 and MEP2 were below 0.30. These two items were therefore excluded from further analysis and the resultant Cronbach's alpha value for the construct increased from 0.580 to 0.838.

Lastly, all the five items in the government and vendor support construct had corrected item-total correlation values below 0.30. However, removing GVS3, GVS4 and GVS5 substantially increased the Cronbach's alpha value from a very low value of 0.194 to 0.861 which depicted a good reliability strength. Also, the corrected item-total correlation for the remaining two items (GVS1 and GVS2) significantly increased to 0.756 each, which was above the cut-off score of 0.30. Hence, only GVS1 and GVS2 were retained in the government and vendor support construct for further analysis. It should be noted that GVS1, GVS2 and GVS3 were used in assessing the impact of government support, while GVS4 and GVS5 were used in

assessing vendor support. Since the items used in assessing vendor support (GVS4 and GVS5) were excluded from further analysis, and the remaining two items (GVS1 and GVS2) were used in measuring government support only. The government and vendor support (GVS) construct will, henceforth, be referred to as government support. Following the removal of items that impaired the internal reliability strength of the research constructs, the resultant Cronbach's alpha values for all the constructs are now greater than the cut-off score of 0.70. Hence, all the constructs had good reliability strength.

5.2 Profile of the Participants

Following the pre-analysis data processing for the quantitative data, a total of 166 entries were remaining for further analysis. The participants in this study are described by variables such as education level, age, years of experience and gender. Table 18 summarises the characteristics of the respondents from the quantitative study, while table 19 presents the characteristics of the participants from the qualitative study. In fact, characteristics of participants for the qualitative study included the roles of the of the participants, level of education, and the number of years they had worked for their respective supermarket chains.

Table 18: Characteristics of the Respondents - survey

Characteristics	Value as a percentage of N=166 (%)
Education Level	
Below Secondary School Certificate	0
Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE) / Ordinary National Diploma (OND)	0
Higher National Diploma (HND)	11.4
Bachelor's degree	74.7
Post graduate degree	13.9
Age	
Below 20 years	0
20-29 years	0
30-39 years	48.2
40-49 years	51.8
50 years and above	0

Years of Employment	
Less than one year	0
1 – 2 years	6.5
3-5 years	49.5
More than 5 years	44.0
Gender	
Male	62.0
Female	38.0
Others	0

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 19: Characteristics of the participants - interviews

Case Number	Study Code	Role of the Interviewee	Years of Employment	Education Level
1	I	Sales manager	4	Bachelor's degree
2	III	Store manager	7	Post graduate degree
3	VI	Store manager	8	Higher National Diploma
4	VII	Accountant	5	Post graduate degree
5	VIII	Store manager	4	Bachelor's degree
6	X	Store manager	3	Post graduate degree
7	XI	Sales manager	8	Bachelor's degree
8	XIII	ICT Manager	3	Higher National Diploma
9	XV	Human resource manager	4	Post graduate degree
10	XVI	Store manager	6	Bachelor's degree
11	XVII	Store manager	5	Bachelor's degree
12	XVIII	Overall Accountant	6	Higher National Diploma
13	XII	Store manager	3	Bachelor's degree
14	XX	Store manager	4	Post graduate degree
15	XXI	Sales manager	7	Bachelor's degree

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Considering the education level of the participants, table 18 indicates that most of them (74.7%) had a bachelor's degree, while 13.9% had attained a post graduate degree. A further 11.4% had attained a Higher National Diploma (HND). None of the respondents were found in the categories labelled Secondary School Certificate, and Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE) / Ordinary National Diploma (OND). However, this is not surprising since the research participants were managers from supermarket chains. Candidates with lower educational levels than a Higher National Diploma are less likely to occupy such managerial positions because of the skills levels needed to operate more effectively in these job roles.

In terms of age, 48.2 percent of the respondents were in the 30-39 years old age category, while the majority (51.8%) were in the 40-49 years old age category. There was no respondent for below 20 years, 20-29 years, and 50 years and above age categories. Concerning their years of experience, 6.5% of the respondents have worked with their supermarket chain for 1-2 years, 49.5% of them have worked for 3-5 years, while 44% have worked with their supermarket chain for more than 5 years. Therefore, most of the respondents had working experience of 3-5 years within their supermarket chains. Finally, table 18 further shows that 62% of the respondents were male while 38% were female. Hence, most of the participants were male.

For the qualitative study, table 19 shows that all the participants in the interview were in senior management positions, and presumably had sufficient knowledge about their respective supermarket chains and provided reliable information to the researcher. The roles of the participants included store manager, account manager, sales manager, ICT manager, and human resources manager. The years of employment for the participants ranged from three to eight years of active employment by their current respective supermarket chains. Further, 40% had working experience of more than 5 years in their respective supermarket chains. The rest had 3-5 years working experience in their supermarket chains. The highest education level attained by the participants included Higher National Diploma (3/15 participants), bachelor's degree (7/15 participants) and post graduate degree (5/15 participants).

5.3 Extent of E-commerce Application in Nigerian Supermarket Chains

This section seeks to present the research findings on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains, which is the first research objective of the study. As discussed earlier, there are six levels of e-commerce adoption in organisations. These levels include the 'non adopters' who do not apply e-commerce technologies in their business operations; the 'e-connectivity' level which include those that employ basic e-commerce technologies like e-mail

for communication; the ‘e-window’ level which include those that enable one way communication by only using a static website to present information; the ‘e-interactivity’ level which involve those that use an interactive website that enable 2-way communication to interact with their customers; the ‘e-transaction’ level which involve those that employ advanced e-commerce technologies to facilitate transactions like online payments; and the ‘e-enterprise’ level which enables an online conduction of all business processes including accounting system and upgrading traditional businesses to electronic ones (Alrousan, 2014).

5.3.1 Questionnaire Findings on the Extent of E-commerce Application

The participants were asked to choose from the six levels of e-commerce adoption, the one that best described the current e-commerce adoption level in their respective supermarkets. Their responses are illustrated in table 20, and this shows that all the supermarket chains that participated in the study are e-commerce adopters with a majority (72.3%) of the respondents indicating that their supermarkets are at e-interactivity stage. This implies that they use an interactive website that enable 2-way communication to interact with their customers. The next most adopted level is the e-transaction level adopters at 24.1%. These supermarkets employ advanced e-commerce technologies to facilitate transactions like online payments. Only a small fraction (3.6%) of the respondents indicated that their supermarkets are at the e-enterprise level. This is the highest level of e-commerce and enables online conduction of all business processes including the accounting system.

Table 20: Current levels of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarkets

E-commerce Adoption Levels	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Non adopters	0	0
E-connectivity	0	0
E-window	0	0
E-interactivity	120	72.3
E-transaction	40	24.1
E-enterprise	6	3.6
Total	166	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Data Analysis

5.3.2 Interview Findings on the Extent of E-commerce Application

In addition to the quantitative data collection, 15 managers from different supermarkets provided qualitative data through semi-structured interviews. The profiles of the interview participants' respective supermarkets and their adoption levels are as illustrated in table 21.

Table 21: Interview participants' supermarket profiles and e-commerce adoption levels

Case Number	Study Code	Years of Operation	Number of Stores in Nigeria	Adoption Level
1	I	12	45	e-transaction
2	III	56	2 stores in Nigeria (with stores in other countries)	e-transaction
3	VI	26	9	e-interactivity
4	VII	37	11	e-interactivity
5	VIII	15	5	e-enterprise
6	X	5	4	e-transaction
7	XI	21	9	e-interactivity
8	XIII	5	15	e-transaction
9	XV	7	2 stores in Nigeria (with stores in other countries)	e-interactivity
10	XVI	11	14	e-interactivity
11	XVII	11	5	e-interactivity
12	XVIII	15	25	e-interactivity
13	XII	3	3	e-interactivity
14	XX	9	3	e-interactivity
15	XXI	21	5	e-interactivity

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

It can be seen from table 21 that the 15 supermarkets that participated in the interview were at either e-interactivity, e-transaction, or e-enterprise level of e-commerce adoption. Ten of them (66.7%) were only at the e-interactivity level, while four (26.7%) were at the e-transaction level. Only one (6.7%) was at the e-enterprise level. Table 21 also illustrates that neither the size of the supermarket chain nor the number of years of operation in Nigeria had a significant impact on the adoption level. For instance, company VII (case 4) which has operated in Nigeria for 37 years, and had 11 operational stores in the country, was only at the e-interactivity level of e-commerce adoption. On the other hand, company X (case 6) that had four stores, and operated in Nigeria for only five years, is already at the e-transaction level. Further results reveal that the leading supermarket chain in Nigeria is only at the e-interactivity stage of e-commerce, without an option of online shopping for their customers. According to

the company's representative in the interview section when asked about the level of e-commerce adoption in their supermarket chain:

“We presently dwell so much on brick-and-mortar aspect of the business. What this means is that we do business majorly on the physical location. On e-commerce aspect, what we have that is a little bit relevant to that is our website. On the website, we present information about our products, new products or just to promote existing ones. We also give information about discounts, marked down items that are not moving well, and promos” (Case 12).

The participant further attributed their non-adoption of higher level of e-commerce to the organisation's culture and policies. He remarked that they only followed the guidelines from the organisations headquarter. Apparently, the headquarters of the parent company are located outside Nigeria.

5.3.3 Summary of Findings on the Extent of E-commerce Application

The findings from the quantitative study on the current level of e-commerce adoption is not much different from the findings from the qualitative study. The results revealed that findings from both studies show that e-interactivity is the minimum level of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains. For instance, the quantitative study found that 72.3% of the respondents indicated that their supermarkets were at the e-interactivity level of e-commerce adoption, while the qualitative study with 15 participants revealed that 66.7% of the supermarket chains are still at the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. Also, the quantitative study found that 24.1% of the respondents indicated that their supermarkets were at the e-transaction level of e-commerce adoption, while the qualitative study revealed that 26.7% of the supermarkets were at the e-transaction level. It was further found that 3.6% of the respondents in quantitative study reported that their supermarkets are already at the e-enterprise stage, which is the highest e-commerce adoption level. On the other hand, the qualitative study found that 6.7% of the supermarkets were at the e-enterprise level of e-commerce adoption. Since the findings from the qualitative study do not significantly deviate from that of the quantitative study, the qualitative study on the current level of e-commerce adoption supports the findings from the quantitative study. Therefore, most of the supermarket chains in Nigeria are still at the e-interactivity level of e-commerce adoption.

5.4 E-commerce Adoption Benefits in Nigerian Supermarket Chains

This section presents the research findings on the benefits of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarkets, which is the second research objective of the study.

5.4.1 Questionnaire Findings on the Benefits of E-commerce

Thirteen benefits identified from past similar studies were adopted in the investigation of the e-commerce adoption benefits study. All the 13 benefits were considered in the benefits analysis as the items had a good Cronbach's alpha value of 0.832, and the benefits of e-commerce adoption study was not subjected to a regression analysis. The participants opinion on these e-commerce benefits are as presented in the summary of their responses in table 22.

Table 22: Participants' responses on e-commerce adoption benefits

Benefits	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
Reduces operating cost	-	-	9.0	58.4	32.5
Increases market share	-	-	1.8	40.4	57.8
Increases customer base	-	-	-	38.6	61.4
Increases sales and revenue	-	-	-	39.8	60.2
Creates new channel for advertising	-	-	-	28.9	71.1
Enhances company's image	-	-	-	31.9	68.1
Enhances competitive advantage	-	-	-	33.1	66.9
Improves customer services and satisfaction	-	-	-	35.5	64.5
Improves business relationship with suppliers	-	-	17.5	47.6	34.9
Helps to perform jobs more quickly	-	-	3.0	54.2	42.8
Provides new opportunities	-	-	0.6	54.8	44.6
Reduces marketing cost	-	0.6	30.7	46.4	22.3
Helps to learn more about competitors	-	-	6.0	49.4	44.6

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

The top benefit of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarkets based on the participants responses is creating new channel for advertising which attained a score of 71.1% strongly agree and 28.9% agree responses. This was followed by enhancing company's image with 68.1% strongly agree and 31.9% agree. Enhancing competitive advantage received 66.9% strongly agree and 33.1% agree responses. Improving customer services and satisfaction received 64.5% strongly agree and 35.5% agree responses. Increasing customer base had 61.4% strongly agree and 38.6% agree responses; while increasing sales and revenue received 60.2% strongly agree and 39.8% agree responses. The above-mentioned benefits were the top six benefits of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains based on the quantitative study findings.

The data for e-commerce adoption benefits was further analysed to explore the perception of the benefits by participants in different e-commerce adoption levels. The mean scores for each benefit were then tabulated according to the e-commerce adoption level of the participants, as illustrated in table 23. The valid e-commerce adoption levels in this analysis are e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise.

Table 23: Mean scores for e-commerce benefits for various adoption levels

Benefits	E-commerce Adoption Levels							
	E-interactivity (N=120)		E-transaction (N=40)		E-enterprise (N=6)		Total (N=166)	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
a. Reduces operating cost	4.13	0.58	4.55	0.55	4.17	0.75	4.23	0.60
b. Increases market share	4.40	0.54	4.98	0.16	5.00	0.00	4.56	0.53
c. Increases customer base	4.48	0.50	4.98	0.16	5.00	0.00	4.61	0.49
d. Increases sales and revenues	4.47	0.50	4.95	0.22	5.00	0.00	4.60	0.49
e. Creates new channel for advertising	4.60	0.49	5.00	0.00	5.00	0.00	4.71	0.45
f. Enhances company's image	4.58	0.50	4.95	0.22	4.83	0.41	4.68	0.47

g. Enhances competitive advantage	4.55	0.50	4.98	0.16	5.00	0.00	4.67	0.47
h. Improves customer services and satisfaction	4.53	0.50	4.95	0.22	5.00	0.00	4.64	0.48
i. Improves business relationship with suppliers	4.02	0.70	4.53	0.55	5.00	0.00	4.17	0.70
j. Helps to perform job more quickly	4.28	0.53	4.70	0.46	4.83	0.41	4.40	0.55
k. Provides new opportunities	4.25	0.45	4.93	0.27	5.00	0.00	4.44	0.51
l. Reduces marketing cost	3.79	0.71	4.25	0.74	3.83	0.75	3.90	0.74
m. Helps to learn more about competitors	4.19	0.57	4.90	0.30	4.83	0.41	4.39	0.60

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Considering the benefits perceived by supermarkets in different adoption levels, four parameters in the e-interactivity category had mean scores above 4.50. These top four parameters were “creates new channel for advertising” with a mean score of 4.60; “enhances company’s image” with a mean score of 4.58; “enhances competitive advantage” with a mean score of 4.55; and “improves customer service and satisfaction” with a mean score of 4.53. The rest of the parameters had mean scores below 4.50, with the least mean score being 3.79 for “reduces marketing cost”.

For the e-transaction category, all the items in this category had mean scores above 4.50, except “reduces marking cost” which had a mean score of 4.25. The first top seven parameters had a mean score of 4.95 and above, with “creating new channel for advertising” topping the chart with a mean score of 5.00. The next top three parameters in this category all had a mean score of 4.98. These parameters include increases market share, increases customer base, and enhances competitive advantage. Furthermore, the following top three parameters had the same mean score of 4.95. These parameters included increases sales and revenue; enhances company’s image; and improves customer services and satisfaction.

In the e-enterprise category, all the parameters had mean scores above 4.50, except “reduces operating cost” that had a mean score of 4.17 and “reduces marketing cost” that had a mean score of 3.83. Eight out of the remaining eleven parameters scored the maximum obtainable mean value of 5.0, while the other three parameters had mean scores of 4.83 each. The top eight parameters that attained a mean value of 5.0 included increases market share; increases customer base; increases sales and revenue; creates new channel for advertising; enhances competitive advantage; improves customer service and satisfaction; improves business relationship with suppliers; and provides new opportunities. The other three parameters that attained a mean value of 4.83 included enhances company’s image; helps to perform jobs more quickly; and helps to learn more about competitors.

The total mean score ranged from 3.90 for reducing marketing cost, to 4.71 for creating new channel for advertising. Other benefits that had high total mean scores were enhancing company’s image with a mean score of 4.68, enhancing competitive advantage with a mean score of 4.67, improving customer services and satisfaction with a mean score of 4.64, increasing customer base with a mean score of 4.61, and increasing sales and revenue with a mean score of 4.60. Hence, this mean score table further reinforces the results in the percentage response table (table 22), which highlights the forementioned benefits as the top six benefits obtained from e-commerce adoption by Nigerian supermarket chains. Furthermore, the mean scores of the benefits appeared to increase as the e-commerce adoption levels of the supermarkets increased. For instance, the mean score for “increases market share” benefit increased from 4.40 at e-interactivity level, to 4.98 at e-transaction level, and to 5.0 at e-enterprise level. Similarly, “increases customer base” benefit increased from 4.48 to 4.98, and 5.0 in e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise categories, respectively. A similar pattern was observed in “increases sales and revenue”, “enhances competitive advantage”, “improves customer services and satisfaction”, “improves business relationship with suppliers”, helps to perform jobs more quickly”, and “provides new opportunities” benefits. Additionally, “creates new channel for advertising” increased from 4.60 in the e-interactive category to maximum obtainable mean score of 5.0 in the e-transactive category and maintaining this maximum score of 5.0 in the e-enterprise category. Also, eight out of the thirteen parameters in the e-enterprise category had the maximum obtainable mean score of 5.0 compared to only one item in the e-transaction category and none in the e-interactive category. This supported the hypothesis that higher ecommerce adoption levels result in greater or better perceptions of e-commerce benefits.

5.4.2 Interview Findings on the Benefits of E-commerce Adoption

The 15 interview participants were asked the benefits they realise from the use of e-commerce technology in their supermarkets. Their responses are summarised in table 24.

Table 24: Interview findings on e-commerce adoption benefits

Benefits	Number of times mentioned	Percentage (%)
Reduces operating cost	1	7
Increases market share	6	40
Increases customer base	5	33
Increases sales and revenue	6	40
Provides new channel for advertising	7	47
Enhances company's image	3	20
Enhances competitive advantage	6	40
Improves customer services and satisfaction	9	60
Improves business relationship with suppliers	-	-
Helps to perform jobs more quickly	1	7
Provides new opportunities	4	27
Reduces marketing cost	2	13
Helps to learn more about competitors	-	-
Others		
Improves customer loyalty	4	37
Improves publicity	4	27
Extends market reach	7	47

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Based on the analysis of the interview responses from the 15 participants, the most mentioned benefit derived from of e-commerce adoption by Nigerian supermarkets is improving customer services and satisfaction. This was selected by 9 out of the 15 participants (60%) as one of the benefits derived by their supermarket in using e-commerce technology. Other benefits that were mentioned often included providing a new channel for advertising (47%), extending market reach (47%), enhancing competitive advantage (40%), increasing sales and revenue (40%), and increasing market share (40%). Some responses on the benefits of e-commerce are presented below:

“Like I said earlier, we just started using e-commerce in our supermarket, so I can’t really say much about the benefits as we haven’t run it long enough to discover the many associated benefits, but I know it will definitely improve our customer services delivery because it will help us to get better feedback from our customers” (case 8).

“It gives our company publicity, people get to know about our company, the location of the company, and the things they can buy from the company” (case 3).

“E-commerce gives the business a competitive edge. It brings profit maximisation; e-commerce can help us to increase our profit margin. E-commerce will also help us to create bigger awareness. As our business is currently expanding, many people will try to know about our business. E-commerce will give us the avenue to achieve wider publicity, which ordinarily we could not do. E-commerce will be the vehicle by which this business will be projected to the world” (case 4).

5.4.3 Summary of Findings on E-commerce Adoption Benefits

Comparing the findings from the quantitative and qualitative studies on the benefits of ecommerce adoption, both findings reveal that the top benefits include creating new channel for advertising, enhancing competitive advantage, improving customer services and satisfaction, increasing customer base, and increasing sales and revenue. However, enhancing company’s image was among the top six benefits in the quantitative study, but not in the qualitative study. Furthermore, the qualitative study found extending market reach among the top six benefits of adopting e-commerce by Nigerian supermarket chains. However, this benefit was not tested in the quantitative study. Two other benefits emerged from the qualitative findings that were not tested in the quantitative study. These benefits include improving customers loyalty and improving publicity. Nevertheless, these new benefits are closely related to some of the other benefits tested in the quantitative study. For instance, improving customer loyalty is closely related to increase in customer base. Also, improving publicity is a direct result of providing new channels for advertising, and extending market reach directly leads to increase in customer base and market share. According to one of the qualitative study participants:

“E-commerce allows us to reach more people through our website and our presence in social media. As more people get to know about us, the number of our customer increases and so does our market share” (Case 15).

Therefore, these new benefits that emerged from the qualitative study are related to some of the benefits tested in the quantitative study. Testing these benefits in the quantitative study would have probably resulted in multicollinearity. Furthermore, the quantitative study found that perception of e-commerce adoption benefits increases with the level of e-commerce adoption. For instance, participants from supermarkets that had higher e-commerce adoption levels showed higher perception levels about the benefits of adopting e-commerce.

5.5 Factors Affecting the Extent of E-commerce Adoption in Nigerian Supermarket Chains

This section seeks to address the influencing factors on e-commerce application levels within Nigerian supermarket chains, which is the third research objective for this study.

5.5.1 Questionnaire Findings on the Factors Affecting the Extent of E-commerce Adoption

The quantitative analysis on the factors affecting e-commerce adoption in this study is comprised of both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The results from the descriptive analysis provided an overview of the factors influencing e-commerce adoption levels within the supermarkets in Nigeria. However, this descriptive analysis result is statistically insufficient to investigate the factors influencing e-commerce uptake and test the hypothesis. Hence, factor analysis (principal component analysis) as well as regression analysis (multinomial logistic regression) were further conducted. The choice of multinomial logistic regression in the regression analysis was because the dependent variable in this study was measured by categorical groups.

5.5.1.1 Descriptive Statistics for E-commerce Influencing Factors

All the constructs' items were measured with a 5-point Likert scale. The mean as well as the standard deviation of all items used to measure the constructs were tabulated in the descriptive statistics table (Table 25) according to the e-commerce adoption level of the respondents' supermarkets. Table 25 further presents the independent t-test results, which indicates the significance of the differences identified between the constructs in different e-commerce adoption levels within the supermarkets.

Table 25: Descriptive Statistics and T-Test results for influencing factors

E-commerce Adoption Levels		RA	COMP	TECR	FBR	TMS	MKA	MEP	GVS
E-interactivity	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
	Mean	4.5143	4.2150	4.1729	2.5200	4.0500	4.4583	1.9500	3.5917
	Std. Deviation	.41511	.46248	.52340	.42636	.38392	.44504	.56119	.65780
E-transaction	N	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
	Mean	4.9750	4.9500	4.9000	1.4050	4.8250	4.9500	2.0083	4.3625
	Std. Deviation	.06379	.14142	.19447	.46517	.30445	.12054	.52018	.63030
E-enterprise	N	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
	Mean	4.9279	4.9333	4.9583	1.0667	4.9000	4.9444	1.5556	4.7500
	Std. Deviation	.12106	0.16330	.10206	.16330	.10954	.13608	.50185	.61237
Total	N	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166
	Mean	4.6402	4.4181	4.3765	2.1988	4.2675	4.5944	1.9498	3.8193
	Std. Deviation	.40914	0.51772	.56189	.67635	.50287	.44206	.55246	.74703
E-interactivity vs E-transaction	Level of Significance (P-Value)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.563	0.000
E-interactivity vs E-enterprise	Level of Significance (P-Value)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.094	0.000
E-transaction vs E-enterprise	Level of Significance (P-Value)	0.390	0.793	0.478	0.003	0.556	0.918	0.052	0.166

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

5.5.1.1.1 Attributes of Innovation

The attributes of innovation dimension are comprised of two constructs which include relative advantage (RA) and compatibility (COMP). The mean score for relative advantage variable was 4.51 in the e-interactivity category, 4.98 in the e-transactive category, and 4.93 in the e-enterprise category, while the total mean score for the relative advantage is 4.64, as illustrated in table 25. The RA mean score in the e-interactive category is lower than its values in the e-transactive and e-enterprise categories which are not significantly different. Also, the independent t-test result indicates a significant difference between e-interactivity and e-transaction RA values ($P < 0.05$), and between e-interactivity and e-enterprise RA values ($P < 0.05$). However, the difference between e-transaction and e-enterprise RA values is not significant ($P > 0.05$). This indicates that supermarkets whose e-commerce adoption has progressed to involve online transactions are more aware of the technological advantages of e-commerce adoption than those at a lower level of adoption, and not involve online transactions.

Similarly, the mean score of the compatibility variable in the attributes of innovation dimension increased from 4.22 in the e-interactivity to 4.95 in the e-transaction category and down to 4.93 in the e-enterprise category. Once again, the COMP mean score in the e-interactivity category is lower than its values in the e-transaction and e-enterprise categories which are not much different from each other. Also, the independent t-test result shows that the COMP values in e-interactivity category are significantly different from those in e-transaction and those in e-enterprise categories ($P < 0.05$). On the other hand, the difference between the COMP values in e-transaction category and e-enterprise category are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). This indicates that the supermarkets in e-transaction and e-enterprise adoption levels are more in tune with the e-commerce technology because they have shown a higher level of compatibility with e-commerce technology than those in the e-interactive level of adoption.

5.5.1.1.2 Organisational Factors

Organisational factors involve two variables: technology readiness (TECR) and financial barriers (FBR). The TECR mean score, as illustrated in table 25, increased from 4.17 in the e-interactivity category to 4.90 in the e-transaction category, and 4.96 in the e-enterprise category. Once again, the increase in the mean score of technology readiness with the e-commerce adoption level is an indication that the organisations with advanced technological facilities like high bandwidth internet connectivity, well computerised local area network (LAN) and wide area network (WAN) systems, customisable systems, sufficient network based application experience, and IT support staff, are more inclined to use e-commerce at a greater

extent than the businesses with less such technological facilities. This hypothesis is further supported by the t-test result which indicates a significant difference in the TECR values between the e-interactivity and e-transaction categories ($P < 0.05$), and between e-interactivity and e-enterprise categories ($P < 0.05$), but not between e-transaction and e-interactivity categories ($P > 0.05$).

For the financial barrier construct, the mean score for the e-interactivity category (2.52) is greater than the mean scores for e-transaction and e-enterprise categories which are 1.41 and 1.01, respectively. This is an indication that the financial costs involved in e-commerce adoption such as setting up cost, maintenance cost, high speed internet access cost, staff training and additional IT support staff costs, were considered less of a problem by the supermarkets that adopted advanced e-commerce levels than those that adopted less advanced e-commerce levels. This is further supported by the t-test result which shows that significant difference exists between the three levels of adoption as ($P < 0.05$) in all the comparisons.

5.5.1.1.3 Managerial Factors

The variables in the managerial factors dimension include Top Management Support (TMS) and Managers Knowledge and Attitude towards e-commerce (MKA). The mean score of TMS was observed to increase with e-commerce adoption levels. It was 4.05 in the e-interactivity category but increased to 4.83 in the e-transaction category and 4.90 in the e-enterprise category. Also, the independent t-test result reveals a significant difference between the TMS values in e-interactivity and e-transaction categories ($P < 0.05$), and between e-interactivity category and e-enterprise categories ($P < 0.05$). However, the difference between the TMS values in e-transaction and e-enterprise categories was found to be insignificant ($P > 0.05$). This indicates that supermarket chains whose decision makers had an interest in e-commerce technology adopted higher levels of e-commerce than the ones whose decision makers had less interest in e-commerce.

For the Managers Knowledge and Attitude towards e-commerce variable, the mean value for the e-interaction category (4.46) is lower than the values for the e-transaction and e-enterprise categories which are 4.95 and 4.94, respectively. Also, the t-test result reveals a significant difference between the values in the e-interactivity and e-transaction category ($P < 0.05$), and between the values in the e-interactivity and e-transaction category ($P < 0.05$), but the difference between the values in the e-transaction and e-enterprise categories was found to be insignificant ($P > 0.05$). This suggests that managers who are knowledgeable in the use of ICT and display a positive attitude to technology adoption tend to support a higher level of e-commerce adoption

than those that are less knowledgeable and display a less positive attitude towards technology adoption.

5.5.1.1.4 Environmental Factors

There are two variables in the environmental factors dimension: market environment pressure (MEP) and government support (GVS). The MEP mean score did not increase or decrease in any order. It was 1.95 for the e-interactivity category, while the scores for e-transaction and e-enterprise categories were 2.01 and 1.56, respectively. Also, the t-test result shows that differences between the MEP values in the three categories are not significant ($P > 0.05$). This suggests that the MEP variable is similar across different adoption levels. It further suggests that market environment pressures have not influenced any of the supermarkets in adopting a higher or lower level of e-commerce.

In the Government Support construct, the mean score for e-interactivity group (3.59) was low compared to the scores in the e-transaction and e-enterprise groups which are 4.36 and 4.75, respectively. Furthermore, the independent t-test result indicated a significant difference between the GVS values in e-interactivity and e-transaction ($P < 0.05$), and between the GVS values in e-interactivity and e-enterprise groups ($P < 0.05$). However, an insignificant difference was found between the GVS values in e-transaction and GVS values in e-enterprise groups ($P > 0.05$). This suggests that government support has some level of influence in the adoption levels of e-commerce by supermarkets in Nigeria.

Considering the total mean scores for the different variables in factors affecting e-commerce adoption, five out of the eight variables have total mean scores above 4.0. These variables are RA (4.64), MKA (4.56), COMP (4.42), TECR (4.38) and TMS (4.27). All the other variables had total mean scores below 4.0 with MEP scoring lowest at 1.95. Hence, the most influencing factors on e-commerce adoption based on the descriptive analysis result are relative advantage, managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, compatibility, technology readiness and top management support.

5.5.1.2 Factor Analysis

According to Ather and Balasundaram (2009, p. 15), “factor analysis (FA) attempts to simplify complex and diverse relationships that exist among a set of observed variables by uncovering common dimensions or factors that link together the seemingly unrelated variables and consequently provides insight into the significance of underlying structure of the data”. Factor analysis can be conducted using different extraction methods. Principal component analysis

(PCA) and principal axis factoring (PAF) are the two most prevalent extraction methods. The PCA is considered more encompassing than PAF because PAF is only limited to common variance analysis, while PCA analyses the variances in all the variables (total variance), specific and common variance inclusive. Therefore, this study employed PCA to investigate the relationship between the variables.

5.5.1.2.1 Requirements for Principal Component Analysis

To conduct a PCA, this study had to meet three major requirements which included the sample size, inter-item correlation and sampling adequacy. With respect to the first requirement, researchers have varying opinions on the minimum sample requirement for PCA. Some recommended a minimum sample size of 100 respondents (Shaukat, Rao and Khan, 2016; Rattray and Jones (2007), while another set of researchers recommended a minimum of 150 respondents (Pallant 2013; Hutcheson and Sofroniou, 1999). Others suggested a rule of thumb that requires a minimum of five respondents per variable as the sufficient sample size for conducting PCA (Hatcher, 1994). Nevertheless, MacCallum, Widaman, Zhang and Hong (1999) suggested that the minimum sample size is subject to other aspects of sampling design rather than the rule of the thumb. In the current study, the data set had 166 valid entries for PCA and eight variables, which approximates to a ratio of 21:1. Therefore, the sample size in this study satisfactorily meets the first PCA requirement.

Regarding the second PCA requirement, an inter-item correlation above 0.3 is recommended to ensure a reliable analyses result, especially in the regression analysis (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013; Field, 2009). In the inter-item correlation assessment conducted in the previous section, items with less than 0.30 were excluded from further analysis. Hence, the second requirement for PCA conduction was met. Inter-item correlation was further assessed with Bartlett's test of sphericity.

The third prerequisite for PCA is sampling adequacy, and it is assessed using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity measures. The range of KMO values is between 0 and 1. According to Hutcheson and Sofroniou (1999, cited in Rahayu, 2015, p. 198) "if the KMO value is below 0.50, it will be considered as 'unacceptable'; the values between 0.50 - 0.70 are considered as 'mediocre'; values between 0.70 - 0.80 are 'good', values between 0.80 - 0.90 are 'great' and values above 0.90 are 'superb'." On the other hand, Hair (2010) remarked that Bartlett's Test of Sphericity reflects the level of inter-correlation between variables. A significant Bartlett's test result with a P-value less than 0.05 is required for the samples to be

adequate for factor analysis. The KMO and Bartlett's test results for this study, as illustrated in table 26, reveal that the data set had a good sampling adequacy test result with a great KMO value of 0.883, and a significant Bartlett's test of sphericity result (p -value <0.05). Therefore, the data set in this study was fit for PCA as the sample size, inter-item correlation and the sampling adequacy meet the requirements for conducting the PCA.

Table 26: KMO and Bartlett's test results

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.883
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4812.773
	df	666
	Sig.	.000

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

5.5.1.2.2 Principal Component Analysis

According to Jolliffe and Cadima (2016), principal component analysis (PCA) reduces the dimensionality of a large dataset and increases its interpretability with a minimal loss of information. To establish factor interpretation, factor rotation was used in conjunction with PCA to boost factor loading variance and reduce low variable loading with factor association. Rotation could be either orthogonal or oblique. Orthogonal rotation presumes a lack of correlation between factors and is applied when the factors in the study are assumed to be independent of each other. On the other hand, the oblique rotation presumes correlation of factors with each other and are somehow related among themselves. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2013, cited in Alrousan, 2014), types of orthogonal rotation include varimax, equamax and quartimax, while oblique rotation types include promax, oblimin and direct quartimin. The present research applied varimax orthogonal rotation to assess construct validity and detect high-level factors by increasing the factor loading variance.

Although researchers have different opinions on the cut-off value for significant loading, many suggested that a minimum value of 0.40 is required for adequate factor analysis interpretation and should only load on one factor. Others posited that a minimum loading factor of 0.30 is necessary for appropriate interpretation (Morgan, Leech, Gloeckner and Barrett., 2013; Hair et al., 2010). However, Anderson et al. (1998, cited in Alrousan, 2014) remarked that the minimum acceptable absolute value for significant factor loading is 0.30, but a 0.50 loading or more is deemed to be incredibly significant. The study used a 0.50 minimum factor loading for greater precision, removing all items that had a factor loading values below 0.50. The number of components retained for factor loading were decided using the eigenvalues and scree plot.

Previous researchers recommended using the Kaiser's criterion which stipulates retaining all factors whose eigenvalues are greater than or equal to 1 (Hair 2010; Field, 2009; Rattray and Jones, 2007). According to Field (2009). In fact, the Kaiser's principle was founded on the concept that the eigenvalues signify variation level attributed to a factor, and a value of 1 constitutes a significant variation level. Apart from Kaiser's criterion, scree plot was also used to graphically decide the number of factors to be retained. The scree plot is a plot of eigen values (Y axis) vs components (X axis). According to Field (2009), the point where the slope breaks is the cut-off point for determining the number of variables. He recommended keeping factors in the vertical half of the curve before the elbow point, where the plot line becomes horizontal (without counting the factor at the break point of the slope). Furthermore, communality which refers to the "total amount of variance an original value shares with all other variables included in the analysis" (Hair, 2010, p. 92), was assessed to ensure that the level of explanation of each item is acceptable. Although Hair (2010) recommended a communality of 0.5 and above for multiple constructs, Osborne, Costello and Kellow (2008) suggested that communalities above 0.4 are acceptable. The researcher analysed all the construct items that were in the study using eigenvalue greater than 1 on PCA with varimax rotation. Items with communalities value less than 0.40 were excluded from further analysis. The cross loaded items, that is, items that loaded in two factors, and items whose loading values were less than 0.50 were removed. The SPSS was set up to automatically suppress the coefficient of items whose absolute values were less than 0.50.

5.5.1.2.3 Assessing the Result of Principal Component Analysis

The initial communalities assessment presented in table B2.1, located in Appendix B-2 shows that all communality values were above 0.4. Hence, no item was excluded because of low communality value. The initial total variance explained table (see table B2.2) in Appendix B-2, shows that the items were extracted in eight factors based on the Kaiser's criterion as only eight factors had eigenvalues equal to or greater than 1.0. Also, the scree plot, as illustrated in figure B2.1 located in Appendix B-2, supports the result from Kaiser's criterion as it also identified eight factors for extraction. However, the initial rotated component matrix as illustrated in table 27, revealed that the only two items that loaded in Factor 8 column were TECR3 and FBR1 which are items from technology readiness and financial barrier constructs. Hence, Factor 8 was removed with the two items (TECR3 and FBR1). The remaining four items in the financial barrier construct (FBR2, FBR3, FBR4 and FBR5) loaded significantly on Factor 3, although negatively which only signified negative contribution as expected.

However, the two items in government support construct also loaded on the same Factor 3. Since, these two sets of items were used in measuring different unrelated constructs, one of the constructs had to be removed. Therefore, the author decided to remove the financial barrier construct because the findings from the interview revealed that government support was a more important factor than financial barrier, in the adoption of e-commerce among the supermarket chains. Furthermore, the last two items in the relative advantage (RA11 and RA13) were suppressed because of low loading values (less than 0.50) and were excluded from further analysis. Hence, a total of eight items (RA11, RA13, TECR3, FBR1, FBR2, FBR3, FBR4 AND FBR5) were excluded from further analysis. The rest of the items were used to run a second PCA with seven factors loading, using a varimax rotation method. All sets of items loaded cleanly according to the constructs they measure, except the last item in compatibility construct (COMP5) which loaded in both Factor 2 and Factor 3 columns (see table B2.3 in appendix B-2). Therefore, COMP5 was removed before running a third PCA. The communalities result for the third PCA in table 28 illustrates that all the items had acceptable communality values (above 0.40). The Kaiser's criterion identified seven factors for extraction based on the Total Variance Explained table (see table 29). The seven factors explained 76.684% of the total variance, with factors 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 explaining 36.276%, 11.356%, 8.490%, 7.290%, 4.912%, 4.495% and 3.865% of the variance, respectively. Furthermore, the third PCA scree plot as illustrated in figure B2.2 in appendix B-2 supports the result from Kaiser's criterion as it also identified seven factors for extraction.

The loading of items on the seven factors in the third PCA run is shown in the third (final) rotated component matrix result in table 30. All the items cleanly and significantly loaded according to their respective constructs, with relative advantage loading on Factor 1, top management support on Factor 2, technology readiness on Factor 3, compatibility on Factor 4, market environment pressure on Factor 5, managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce on Factor 6, and government support on Factor 7.

Table 27: Initial items loading

Rotated Component Matrix ^a								
	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
RA2	.720							
RA3	.803							
RA4	.834							
RA5	.837							
RA6	.834							
RA7	.806							
RA8	.822							
RA11								
RA13								
COMP1				.806				
COMP2				.793				
COMP3				.734				
COMP4				.606				
COMP5				.548				
TECR1					.738			
TECR2					.703			
TECR3								.871
TECR4					.769			
TECR5					.808			
FBR1								-.857
FBR2			-.581					
FBR3			-.544					
FBR4			-.583					
FBR5			-.646					
TMS1		.579						
TMS2		.707						
TMS3		.686						
TMS4		.789						
TMS5		.706						
MKA1							.822	
MKA2							.854	
MKA5							.707	
MEP3						.797		
MEP4						.891		
MEP5						.901		
GVS1			.772					
GVS2			.794					

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 28: Third (final) communalities result

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
RA2	1.00	.675
RA3	1.00	.759
RA4	1.00	.769
RA5	1.00	.753
RA6	1.00	.753
RA7	1.00	.770
RA8	1.00	.734
COMP1	1.00	.823
COMP2	1.00	.785
COMP3	1.00	.747
COMP4	1.00	.660
TECR1	1.00	.801
TECR2	1.00	.738
TECR4	1.00	.853
TECR5	1.00	.792
TMS1	1.00	.642
TMS2	1.00	.713
TMS3	1.00	.821
TMS4	1.00	.814
TMS5	1.00	.701
MKA1	1.00	.736
MKA2	1.00	.825
MKA5	1.00	.753
MEP3	1.00	.666
MEP4	1.00	.838
MEP5	1.00	.821
GVS1	1.00	.859
GVS2	1.00	.871

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 29: Third (final) result for Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	10.157	36.276	36.276	5.278	18.850	18.850
2	3.180	11.356	47.632	3.526	12.595	31.445
3	2.377	8.490	56.122	3.062	10.936	42.380
4	2.041	7.290	63.412	2.988	10.671	53.051
5	1.375	4.912	68.324	2.418	8.634	61.685
6	1.259	4.495	72.819	2.367	8.455	70.140
7	1.082	3.865	76.684	1.832	6.544	76.684
8	.728	2.600	79.284			
9	.630	2.248	81.533			
10	.543	1.939	83.471			
11	.501	1.789	85.261			
12	.440	1.570	86.831			
13	.368	1.314	88.145			
14	.356	1.271	89.416			
15	.338	1.207	90.624			
16	.312	1.113	91.736			
17	.296	1.056	92.792			
18	.274	.978	93.770			
19	.248	.887	94.657			
20	.237	.845	95.502			
21	.201	.717	96.220			
22	.193	.691	96.911			
23	.182	.650	97.561			
24	.172	.614	98.175			
25	.146	.520	98.695			
26	.135	.482	99.177			
27	.124	.443	99.620			
28	.106	.380	100.000			

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 30: Third (final) items loading

Rotated Component Matrix							
	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
RA2	.724						
RA3	.806						
RA4	.833						
RA5	.837						
RA6	.841						
RA7	.812						
RA8	.821						
COMP1				.821			
COMP2				.808			
COMP3				.739			
COMP4				.578			
TECR1			.758				
TECR2			.711				
TECR4			.797				
TECR5			.828				
TMS1		.654					
TMS2		.736					
TMS3		.747					
TMS4		.805					
TMS5		.711					
MKA1						.821	
MKA2						.872	
MKA5						.746	
MEP3					.802		
MEP4					.894		
MEP5					.901		
GVS1							.865
GVS2							.847
Factor Labels: F1= Relative Advantage; F2= Top Management Support; F3= Technology Readiness; F4= Compatibility; F5= Market Environment Pressure; F6= Managers Knowledge and Attitude; F7= Government Support							

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

The findings of the factor analysis revealed a significant loading of most of the items on the anticipated factors. This indicates that each construct was unidimensional. Also, the few cross loaded items and the ones with low loading values as well as the financial barrier construct items that loaded on the same factor with government support construct were excluded. Hence, the financial barrier construct was excluded from further analysis. Since the number of cross loaded items was less than the number of items that significantly loaded on the same factor, the discriminant validity of the constructs was confirmed (Alrousan 2014; El-Gohary, 2012). Nevertheless, the average variance extracted (AVE) value was computed for each construct to further assess the discriminant and convergent validity (Abou-Shouk et al., 2013; Fornell and Larcker, 1981). AVE values of 0.5 and above are deemed adequate and acceptable for convergent validity (Ab Hamid et al., 2017; Alrousan 2014). The AVE values in table 31 ranged from 0.536 to 0.751 showing that all the retained constructs had acceptable AVE values, which confirmed convergent validity.

Table 31: Average Variance Extracted

Constructs	AVE
Relative Advantage	0.658
Compatibility	0.552
Technological Readiness	0.600
Top Management Support	0.536
Managers Knowledge and Attitude	0.664
Market Environment Pressure	0.751
Government Support	0.733

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

To ascertain discriminant validity, the square root of each construct's AVE value is required to be higher than the constructs' correlations with the other construct (Alrousan, 2014; Fornell and Larcker, 1981). The comparison in table 32 reveals that each construct's AVE square root was higher than its correlations with other components, which further confirmed discriminant validity. Therefore, the constructs in this study were reliable to produce quality data since they met the criteria for discriminant and convergent validity.

Table 32: AVE square root compared with constructs correlations

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix							
	RA	COMP	TECR	TMS	MKA	MEP	GVS
RA	0.811						
COMP	.476	0.743					
TECR	.457	.651	0.775				
TMS	.438	.596	.584	0.732			
MKA	.302	.370	.234	.418	0.815		
MEP	.063	-.017	.022	-.069	-.054	0.751	
GVS	.226	.359	.326	.449	.364	-.125	0.856

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

5.5.1.3 Final Reliability Assessment

Even though Cronbach's alpha value is widely used in reliability assessment, some researchers argue that composite reliability is a better assessment technique (Casaló et al., 2011; Chin et al., 2003). In the current study, composite reliability was used in addition to Cronbach's alpha to verify the reliability of the items retained in the constructs (Alrousan 2014; Ifinedo, 2011). According to Hair et al. (2014, cited in Ab Hamid et al., 2017), a minimum Cronbach's alpha/composite reliability value of 0.60 is adequate for exploratory research, while a minimum value of 0.70 is required in more advanced research. Therefore, a minimum value of 0.70 is considered acceptable for both the Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability test in this study.

The Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability results in table 33 reveal that the values for both tests in each construct exceeded the minimum acceptable value of 0.7, demonstrating acceptable reliability for all the research constructs. The extremely good Cronbach's alpha scores in all the research constructs in this study could be attributed to two major reasons. First is that all the items used in measuring the research constructs were adapted from similar studies where they proved valid and reliable. The second reason is that the corrected item-total correlation and Cronbach's alpha if item deleted techniques were applied in the initial reliability test to remove the items that impaired the Cronbach's alpha scores of the constructs. Regarding the high composite reliability scores, since the items that impaired the reliability of the constructs were removed during the initial reliability assessment, prior to factor analysis, from which the values used for composite reliability computation were derived, the resultant composite reliability values were subsequently found to be extremely good. Furthermore, the

overall Cronbach's alpha value for the combined constructs using the mean values of the construct items was 0.719 which indicated a good reliability.

Table 33: Retained constructs' Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values

Variables	Number of Items	Number of Items Deleted	Number of Items Retained	Cronbach's Alpha Value	Composite Reliability
Relative Advantage	9	2	7	0.933	0.930865
Compatibility	5	1	4	0.872	0.828789
Technological Readiness	5	1	4	0.906	0.856863
Top Management Support	5	0	5	0.884	0.851946
Managers Knowledge and Attitude	3	0	3	0.819	0.854974
Market Environment Pressure	3	0	3	0.838	0.900435
Government Support	2	0	2	0.861	0.845796

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

5.5.1.4 New Hypothesis

Following the elimination of the financial barrier construct in the factor analysis section, the hypotheses to be examined in the following sections have been reorganised as shown below.

H1: Relative advantage has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H2: Compatibility has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H3: Technology readiness has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H4: Top management support has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H5: Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H6: Market environment pressure has a positive influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains

H7: Government and vendor support has a significant and positive influence on the extent of e-commerce application of in Nigerian supermarket chains

5.5.1.5 Multinomial Logistic Regression for the Adoption Levels of E-commerce

Multinomial logistic regression was used to determine the predictive variables that had a significant influence on the adoption levels of e-commerce among the supermarket chains in Nigeria. The choice of multinomial logistic regression was because the dependent variable was categorical, while multiple linear regression requires a continuous dependent variable (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013; Field, 2009). Other justifications for applying logistic regression are discussed in the data analysis method section of the methodology chapter.

According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2013), it is important to test for multicollinearity prior to multinomial logistic regression analysis to prevent inaccurate regression coefficient estimates. The collinearity assessment results in section 5.1.5 revealed that there was no high correlation among independent variables which indicated that there was no reasonable proof of multicollinearity issues present among the variables. Also, there should be no outliers in the data set for multinomial logistic regression. Outliers in this study's data set were eliminated in the data cleaning and data quality check in section 5.1.

Multinomial logistic regression was used to analyse seven predictor variables to assess their influence on the e-commerce adoption levels in Nigerian supermarket chains. The adoption levels include three valid categories: e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise. The multinomial logistic regression model as presented in Alrousan (2014) can be described as follows:

$$\text{Predicted logit } (Y) = \alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \dots + \beta_nx_n$$

Where:

- Y denotes dependent variable
- α denotes equation constant
- β denotes regression coefficient
- x denotes independent variable (predictor).

5.5.1.5.1 Assessing the Result of Multinomial Logistic Regression

The outcome variable in the multinomial logistic regression analysis is broken down into sets of comparisons between two groups (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). Consequently, a category to be compared with other groups is chosen as the reference category. E-interactivity level was selected as the reference category to be compared with the parameter estimates of the other two categories (e-transaction and e-enterprise).

Table 34 presents the model fitting information featuring the model fitting criteria using -2 Log Likelihood (-2LL), and the likelihood ratio tests using the chi-square test statistics. The log-likelihood measures the amount of unexplained variance in the data set, while the chi-square test assesses the reduction in unexplained variance from the baseline model (231.570) to the final one (56.479), which was obtained by subtracting 56.479 from 231.570 to get 175.092. This change was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), which implies that the final model was a better fit than the original (null) model (Field, 2009). It was found that a strong association existed between the outcome variable (adoption level) and the independent variables in the study.

Table 34: Fitting information for the model

Model	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	231.570			
Final	56.479	175.092	14	.000

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 35 presents the goodness of fit result which assesses the fitness of the model to the data set. According to Field (2009), both the Pearson and Deviance statistics test the significance of the differences between the predicted values and the observed values. The model is a good fit if the difference between the predicted values and observed values is not significant ($P > 0.05$). Since the Pearson and Deviance statistics p values are greater than 0.05, indicating non-significant difference between the predicted and observed values in the data set, the model was confirmed a good fit for the data by both the Pearson and Deviance tests.

Table 35: Goodness-of-fit

	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	206.343	306	1.000
Deviance	56.479	306	1.000

Source: Researcher’s data analysis

Table 36 presents the Pseudo R-Square results which depict the percentage of variance explainable by the model. Table 36 reveal that there are three measures of Pseudo R-Square. The Cox and Snell value was 0.652 (65.2%), while Nagelkerke value was 0.866 (86.6%) and McFadden value was 0.756 (75.6%). The high R-Square values indicate that the model was appropriate and fits the data as a reasonable proportion of the variance can be explained by the model which implies that the dependent and the independent variables had a strong relationship.

Table 36: Pseudo R-Square

Cox and Snell	.652
Nagelkerke	.866
McFadden	.756

Source: Researcher’s Data Analysis

The classification, as illustrated in table 37, reveal that the number of observed that were correctly predicted by the regression model. The accurate predictions appear in the cells on the diagonal, while the inaccurate predictions appear in the cells off the diagonal. The table shows that 117 of the 120 respondents in the e-interactivity level were classified correctly, while 37 of the 40 respondents in the e-transaction category, and 2 of the 6 respondents in the e-enterprise category were correctly classified. In general, 94.0% of the cases were correctly classified. This further confirms the suitability of the model as it has shown to give a good prediction across the e-commerce adoption levels, except for the e-enterprise level, which has only 6 respondents.

Table 37: Classification table

Observed	Predicted			
	E-interactivity	E-transaction	E-enterprise	Percent Correct
E-interactivity	117	2	1	97.5%
E-transaction	3	37	0	92.5%
E-enterprise	0	4	2	33.3%
Overall Percentage	72.3%	25.9%	1.8%	94.0%

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table 38 presents the likelihood ratio tests which are used to establish the significance of each of the predictors to the model (Field, 2009). When compared to the whole model, this test demonstrates the significance of each predictor's impact on the model. A P-value less than 0.05 indicates that the predictor is significant, while a P-value greater than 0.05 indicates non significance. The values, as illustrated in table 38, reveal that all the variables are significant predictors in the model as their P-values were less than 0.05.

Table 38: Likelihood ratio tests result

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	217.819	161.340	2	.000
Relative Advantage	91.200	34.722	2	.000
Compatibility	96.662	40.183	2	.000
Technology Readiness	78.510	22.031	2	.000
Top Management Support	115.352	58.873	2	.000
Managers Knowledge and Attitude	96.913	40.434	2	.000
Market Environment Pressure	63.967	7.488	2	.024
Government Support	77.945	21.466	2	.000

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

As mentioned earlier, the multinomial logistic regression analysis was conducted using e-interactivity as the reference category to compare with the e-transaction and e-enterprise groups. Table 39 presents the parameter estimates which shows each predictor's impact on the

model. Each predictor in the equation of multinomial logistic regression is estimated by the value of its regression coefficient (β). Parameters with negative coefficients that are significant, reduces the response category's likelihood with respect to the reference category, while parameters that have positive coefficients raises the response category's likelihood (Field 2009). Also, the table shows the exponentiated beta ($\text{Exp}(\beta)$) values also known as the odds ratios. According to Field (2009), $\text{Exp}(\beta)$ values less than 1 indicate that the predictor will have a lower likelihood of contributing to the response category's outcome than the reference category, whereas $\text{Exp}(\beta)$ values greater than 1 indicate that the predictor will have a higher likelihood of contributing to the response category's outcome than the reference category. The Wald statistics is an essential part of parameter estimates since it was used to determine the statistically significant predictors in the outcome (Field, 2009). Predictors with P-value less than 0.05 were accepted, while those with P-values above 0.05 were rejected. Two different multinomial logistic regression equations were applicable as follows:

First multinomial logistic regression equation:

$$\text{Logit (e-transaction/e-interactivity}_{\text{reference}}) = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Relative Advantage} + \beta_2 \text{Compatibility} + \beta_3 \text{Technology Readiness} + \beta_4 \text{Top Management Support} + \beta_5 \text{Managers Knowledge and Attitude} + \beta_6 \text{Market Environment Pressure} + \beta_7 \text{Government Support.}$$

Second multinomial logistic regression equation:

$$\text{Logit (e-enterprise/e-interactivity}_{\text{reference}}) = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Relative Advantage} + \beta_2 \text{Compatibility} + \beta_3 \text{Technology Readiness} + \beta_4 \text{Top Management Support} + \beta_5 \text{Managers Knowledge and Attitude} + \beta_6 \text{Market Environment Pressure} + \beta_7 \text{Government Support.}$$

Table 39: Parameter estimates with e-interactivity as reference category

E-commerce Adoption Levels ^a		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
E-transaction	Intercept	-11.645	3.431	11.517	1	0.001	
	RA	8.644	2.881	8.999	1	0.003	5675.792
	COMP	5.970	1.875	10.143	1	0.001	391.565
	TECR	3.725	1.205	9.547	1	0.002	41.461
	TMS	4.783	1.338	12.781	1	0.000	119.414

	MKA	4.933	1.526	10.444	1	0.001	138.758
	MEP	1.455	0.786	3.433	1	0.064	4.287
	GVS	1.956	0.641	9.302	1	0.002	7.069
E-enterprise	Intercept	-14.207	5.261	7.292	1	0.007	
	RA	6.577	3.827	2.953	1	0.086	718.236
	COMP	4.471	2.488	3.228	1	0.072	87.412
	TECR	5.283	2.853	3.428	1	0.064	196.901
	TMS	5.585	2.015	7.682	1	0.006	266.321
	MKA	3.780	2.085	3.286	1	0.070	43.799
	MEP	0.355	0.959	0.137	1	0.711	1.426
	GVS	3.391	1.272	7.109	1	0.008	29.682

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

In the first regression equation (e-transaction versus e-interactivity) result, as illustrated in table 39, it was found that six of the seven predictors had p-values less than 0.05 making their contribution to the first regression equation statistically significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity. Market environment pressure (MEP) was the only predictor that was insignificant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity. This is because it was the only one with a p-value greater than 0.05. Relative advantage (RA) had a positive influence on the likelihood of the supermarket's decision to adopt e-transaction rather than e-interactivity level of e-commerce. The positive β value and odd ratio result show that participants who had shown a better appreciation of the relative advantages of e-commerce uptake were more probable to operate at the e-transaction than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. Similarly, compatibility (COMP) had a positive influence on the likelihood of the participant's supermarket to adopt the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. The positive β value and odd ratio result show that supermarkets whose participants were more optimistic that e-commerce was compatible with their businesses were more likely to adopt the e-transaction than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. Technology readiness (TECR) also had a positive influence on the likelihood of the supermarket's decision to adopt the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. The positive β value and

odd ratio result show that supermarkets whose participants believed that they had the technical resources required for high level e-commerce uptake were more inclined to operate at the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. Top management support (TMS) had a positive effect on the likelihood of the participant's supermarket to adopt the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. The positive β value and odd ratio result show that supermarkets whose top managers were willing to support the implementation of e-commerce in their supermarkets were more inclined to operate at the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce had a positive effect on the likelihood of the participant's supermarket to adopt the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. The positive β value and odd ratio result show that supermarkets whose managers had a better knowledge of ICT and a positive attitude towards e-commerce were more inclined to operate at the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. Also, government support had a positive influence on the likelihood of the participant's supermarket to adopt the e-transaction rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. The positive β value and odd ratio result show that supermarkets whose participants gave a positive response on the government support were more inclined to operate at the e-transaction instead of the e-interactivity level of e-commerce.

In the second regression equation (e-enterprise vs e-interactivity) result, only top management support, and government support significantly predicted whether a respondent's supermarket adopts an e-enterprise instead of an e-interactivity level of e-commerce. This is because they were the only predictors with p-values less than 0.05 in the e-enterprise vs e-interactivity result. Both predictors had positive influence on the likelihood of the participant's supermarket to adopt the e-enterprise rather than the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. The positive β value and odd ratio result for top management support show that supermarkets whose participants gave a positive response on the willingness of the top managers to support e-commerce implementation were more inclined to operate at the e-enterprise instead of the e-interactivity level of e-commerce based on the positive β value. Also, the positive β value and odd ratio result for government support show that supermarkets whose participants gave a positive response on government support were more inclined to operate at the e-enterprise instead of the e-interactivity level of e-commerce. Other predictors did not significantly predict whether participant's supermarket adopted the e-enterprise instead of the e-interactivity level of e-commerce since their p-values were above 0.05.

5.5.1.6 Hypotheses Results Based on Regression Analysis

Table 40 summarizes the findings of multinomial logistic regression analysis on the given assumptions over the two models based on the three valid e-commerce adoption levels (e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise). It is worthy to note that the hypothesis results differ between the two models. In the first model (e-transaction vs e-interactivity), H1, H2, H3, H4, H5 and H7 were supported as they were found significant with p-values of 0.003, 0.001, 0.002, 0.000, 0.001 and 0.002, respectively. All the factors in the model, except market environment pressure were significant predictors. Hence, relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support, managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, and government support were predicted to have a positive influence on the supermarkets decision to adopt the e-transaction instead of the e-interactivity level of e-commerce in accordance with the hypotheses.

For the second model (e-enterprise vs e-interactivity), only hypothesis H4 and H7 were supported as their predictors (top management support and government support, respectively) were found to be significant with p-values of 0.006 and 0.008, respectively, and they correlated with the adoption level of e-commerce. Alternatively said, the factors in H4 (top management support) and H6 (government support) were predicted to have influenced the supermarkets to adopt the e-enterprise level of e-commerce instead of the e-interactivity level. The rest of the hypothesis were not supported as they were found to be insignificant and a poor fit for the model.

In conclusion, H1 (relative advantage), H2 (compatibility), H3 (technology readiness), H4 (top management support), H5 (managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce) and H7 (government support) were significant in predicting the uptake of a specific level of e-commerce over another by the Nigerian supermarket chains. On the other hand, H6 (market environment pressure) was not significant and found to be a weak predictor of the different e-commerce adoption levels amongst the supermarkets.

Table 40: Hypothesis result

Proposed Hypothesis	Hypotheses Results	
	Model 1	Model 2
	E-transaction vs E-interactivity	E-enterprise vs E-interactivity
H1: Relative advantage has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.	Proposed hypothesis was supported as relative advantage was found to be positive and significant in predicting the model, $\beta=8.664$, $p=0.003<0.05$	Proposed hypothesis was rejected as relative advantage was found to be insignificant, $\beta=6.577$, $p=0.086>0.05$
H2: Compatibility has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets	Proposed hypothesis was supported as compatibility was found to be positive and significant, $\beta=5.970$, $p=0.001<0.05$	Proposed hypothesis was rejected as compatibility was found to be insignificant, $\beta=4.471$, $p=0.072>0.05$
H3: Technology Readiness has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets	Proposed hypothesis was supported as technology readiness was found to be positive and significant, $\beta=3.725$, $p=0.002>0.05$	Proposed hypothesis was not supported as technology readiness was found to be insignificant, $\beta=5.283$, $p=0.064>0.05$
H4: Top management support has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets	Proposed hypothesis was supported as top management support was found to be positive and significant, $\beta=4.783$, $p=0.000<0.05$	Proposed hypothesis was supported as top management support was found to be positive and significant, $\beta=5.585$, $p=0.006<0.05$
H5: Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-	Proposed hypothesis was supported as managers' knowledge and attitude was found to be positive	Proposed hypothesis was rejected as managers' knowledge and attitude was found to be insignificant, $\beta=3.780$, $p=0.070>0.05$

commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets	and significant, $\beta=4.933$, $p=0.001<0.05$	
H6: Market environment pressure has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets	Proposed hypothesis was rejected as market environment pressure was found to be insignificant, $\beta=1.455$, $p=0.064>0.05$	Proposed hypothesis was rejected as market environment pressure was found to be insignificant, $\beta=0.355$, $p=0.711>0.05$
H7: Government support has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets	Proposed hypothesis was supported as government support was found to be positive and significant, $\beta=1.956$, $p=0.002<0.05$	Proposed hypothesis was supported as government support was found to be positive and significant, $\beta=3.391$, $p=0.008<0.05$

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

5.5.2 Interview Findings on the Factors Affecting the Extent of E-commerce Adoption

The fifteen participants that took part in the interviews during qualitative data collection were asked among other questions to describe the factors that influence their e-commerce adoption levels. Their responses were analysed to determine the number of times each factor was mentioned. Table 41 presents the summary of the findings about the factors influencing the uptake of e-commerce among the supermarket chains in Nigeria.

Table 41: Interview results on influencing factors on e-commerce adoption

Influencing Factors	Number of mentions	Percentage (%)
perceived benefits (relative advantage)	7	47
Compatibility	3	20
Technology readiness	5	33
Financial barriers (cost)	0	0
Top management support	5	33
Managers Knowledge and Attitude	1	7
Market environment (competitive) Pressure	0	0
External (including government) Support	4	27
Others		

Cybersecurity	4	27
Damage control	1	7
Logistics (poor home and street addressing system and poor road network)	4	27

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

The interview results, as illustrated in table 41, reveals that seven of the fifteen interview participants (47%) reported perceived benefits to be one of the variables that influence their e-commerce adoption decisions. Other influencing factors that were reported included compatibility (20%), technology readiness (33%), top management support (33%), managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce (7%), and damage control (7%). Further, external (including government) support (27%), cybersecurity (27%), and inefficient logistics due to poor home and street addressing system and poor road network in some places (27%) were reported by the participants as the influencing factors. Some of the responses given by participants as factors affecting e-commerce adoption are presented below:

“We adopted a higher level of e-commerce to help us improve customer services, and to enjoy other associated benefits like widening the market reach, improving competitive advantage, improving customer satisfaction” (Case 2).

“One of the challenges involved in our adopting a higher level of e-commerce is logistics challenges regarding the delivery system due to poor home addressing system. The poor addressing system, which is sometimes complicated with poor road network, makes it difficult to locate some homes or address of some of our customers that have placed an order online” (Case 6).

“We adopted e-commerce that supports online transaction because we want to be able to sell our products online to make it easier for people from different parts of the city to buy from us even without coming to the shop” (Case 1).

“We run a model that is similar or the same to what is obtainable in every country where our business is present. So anywhere we operate, whether in Rwanda, Angola, or South Africa, whatever you see here should be what you will get there. So, if there will be any advancement in e-commerce, it has to cascade down from the home office to us” (Case 12).

Internet security is a major concern among online shoppers in Nigeria. Government regulations through the use of anti-graft agencies like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), and Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) which fight cybercrime gave us some level of confidence to adopt e-commerce that involve online transactions (Case 5).

5.5.3 Summary of Findings on Factors Affecting the Extent of E-commerce Adoption

Comparing the quantitative and qualitative findings on factors affecting e-commerce adoption by supermarket chains in Nigeria, both studies found relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support, managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, and government support to be variables that influence e-commerce uptake. Additionally, the qualitative study found cybersecurity, damage control and logistic problems occasioned by poor infrastructure to also affect the extent of e-commerce use in the industry. Financial barrier was excluded from further examination following the principal component analysis (factor analysis), which reduced the proposed hypotheses from eight to seven. Multinomial logistic regression analysis results found that six of the seven variables were significant in predicting the adoption levels of e-commerce. These six significant variables included relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support, managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, and government support. Market environment pressure was the only insignificant factor in predicting the adoption level of e-commerce by the supermarkets.

5.6 Findings on Measures to Improve E-commerce Adoption and Sustainability

Research participants were asked, only in interview sections, to suggest what could be done to improve the adoption levels and sustainability of e-commerce by supermarkets in Nigeria. Their responses were used to help develop a framework for improving the e-commerce adoption and sustainability by Nigerian supermarket chains. The findings are summarised in table 42. Some of the measures identified are grouped in themes according to their similarities.

Table 42: Participants' opinions on measures to improve e-commerce adoption

Measures to Improve E-commerce Adoption	Number of Mentions	Percentage
Internet security	6	40
Promoting good shopping experience	4	27
Addressing infrastructure and logistics problems	4	27

Training and sensitisation	4	27
Secure customers trust and loyalty	3	20
Availability of reliable internet services	3	20
User friendly websites	2	13

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Among the suggested means to improve e-commerce adoption levels, internet security was the most suggested means to improve e-commerce adoption by Nigerian supermarkets, as it was suggested by 6 of 15 participants (40%). It was found that promoting good shopping experience, training and sensitisation, and addressing infrastructure and logistics problems were suggested by 27% of the participants. Three of fifteen participants (20%) suggested improved customers' trust and loyalty, and reliable internet service. Further, 2 of 15 participants (13%) mentioned recommended a user-friendly website as another means of improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability. Some of the participants responses are presented below.

"I personally believe that whatever will guarantee the customer's trust in your products, in your business, and whatever will ensure efficient customer service should be put in place to help improve e-commerce" (Case 12).

"Reliability of the items purchased online promotes good shopping experience. Many customers are sceptical about online products due to fear of receiving a substandard or damaged items" (Case 14).

5.7 Framework for E-commerce Adoption in Nigerian Supermarket Chains

Drawing from the findings of this study and the body of knowledge, the framework in Figure 18 has been developed to enhance the adoption and sustainability of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains.

Figure 18: Framework for e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains

Source: Researcher's Own Construction

The findings revealed that the valid e-commerce adoption levels in the supermarket chains are e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise adoption levels. The factors that were found to be significant in differentiating between these three adoption levels included relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, and government support. Relative advantage and compatibility were constructs used in the study of the technological factors dimension of the TOE and are equally constructs from the DoI theory. Technology readiness was from the organisational factors dimension of the TOE. Top management support, and managers' knowledge and attitude are from the managerial factors dimension which is an extension of the organisational arm of the TOE. The government support was from the environmental factors dimension of the TOE framework. The TOE framework and DoI theory thus serve as the foundation for the developed research framework.

The proposed managerial actions that are depicted in the framework are based on the findings of this study on the factors affecting e-commerce adoption levels and measures to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability, as well as knowledge from previous studies. The

supermarket decision-makers need to collaborate with the government or public policymakers (particularly anti-graft agencies like EFCC and ICPC) and other stakeholders (including the IT consultants and web vendors; other supermarket chains; and other e-commerce players in the country) to address cybersecurity and privacy issues surrounding e-commerce. People will feel safer and better protected in the online world as a result, which will assist to establish an atmosphere that is conducive to the expansion of e-commerce in Nigeria. The need for addressing this issue cannot be overemphasised as this study and many other previous studies (Usman and Kumar, 2021; Amornkitvikai and Lee, 2020; Adelola, Dawson and Batmaz, 2014) have found poor internet security and fears regarding online privacy as a one of the key obstacles to e-commerce growth. Artificial intelligence methods particularly deep learning and machine learning can be employed to enhance cybersecurity measures (Zeadally, Adi, Baig and Khan, 2020). Data science can also be applied with AI to improve cybersecurity (Humayun et al., 2021). AuthorCAAT “(Author Cyber Analysis & Advisement Tool)” which was developed to help users secure their online privacy by using adversarial authorship to help them modify their writing style can also be used to improve online privacy and cybersecurity (Packer, Seals and Dozier, 2022, p. 194). Other measures that could be used to improve cybersecurity include establishing basic central contacts for guidance and advice; training the employees to recognise cybersecurity warning signs; regular software update; implementing multi-factor authentication; and regular system vulnerability audit (Green, 2021).

Secondly, the decision makers must create a plan for advancing e-commerce in their supermarket chains. This could involve reviewing their current e-commerce application level, assessing the prospects for a higher adoption level, and creating a road map for improving their adoption levels for greater benefits if necessary. The findings revealed that supermarket chains that have a clear strategy for e-commerce adoption were more likely to adopt higher levels of e-commerce than those that do not have any strategy.

To increase user experience and user interface, product and process enhancement is the third suggested managerial action. This involves improving the quality of products and services (including product packaging, delivery processes, and customer support) delivered to online customers. The intention is to improve the shopping experience and online customer satisfaction which is reflected by the number or repurchases made by customers (Alavi and Ahuja, 2021). The user interface (UI) can be improved by using user-friendly (simple and easy to use) websites for the e-commerce activities. The proposal of this managerial action is in line with Davis (1989) Technology Acceptance model which postulates that perceived ease of use

influences attitude towards the use of an innovation. This also agrees with the findings of Lee and Zubir (2022), Sudiana et al. (2021), and Omotayo and Omotope (2018), who reported that a well-designed website and ease of use positively influenced the adoption and acceptance of e-commerce.

The framework further proposes capacity building, including human and technological capacities as one of the managerial actions necessary to enhance e-commerce adoption and sustainability by Nigerian supermarket chains. This involves continuous development of human capacity (particularly through staff training and active employment of IT support personnel) and ICT resources needed for effective implementation of an advanced e-commerce application level. This is in line with Maryama and Suhongb (2022) who recommended capacity building as a means of improving ICT adoption among SMEs in Nigeria.

The framework also proposes infrastructural development as one of the measures that can be adopted to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability. This is particularly significant since, according to the study's findings, one way to increase the acceptance and sustainability of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains is to address the infrastructural and logistics issues that surround it. In addition to regular power supply, high speed internet access, good road networks and good house and street addressing systems are essential for effective and sustainable implementation of high e-commerce adoption levels. The government must play an important role in the provision of these infrastructures.

Finally, this study also proposes public sensitisation in the framework for improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability by Nigerian supermarket chains. The findings revealed that awareness of the benefits of e-commerce is one of the important determinants of the extent of application of e-commerce. Amornkitvikai and Lee (2020) also found that poor customers' awareness of e-commerce is one of the biggest obstacles to e-commerce uptake. Also, some Nigerians that live in communities with no proper house and street addressing systems are unaware of delivery options available to them and are therefore discouraged from online shopping. Therefore, the government, the supermarket managers, and policymakers must sensitise the public more on the benefits of e-commerce and the delivery options available to them.

5.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented the findings from both the quantitative and qualitative data sets. It started with a pre-analysis data processing. This involved checking for data errors, missing

data, and checking for outliers. These were used to ensure the accuracy of the data set and its suitability for further analysis. A normal distribution pattern of the data was confirmed. Multicollinearity was assessed and found to be acceptable, and this helped to avoid statistical anomalies that may arise during regression analysis. Descriptive analysis was then used to present the findings from both quantitative and qualitative data for each of the research objectives. On the current level of e-commerce, which was the first research objective, only the last three of the six known e-commerce adoption levels were found to be adopted by the supermarket chains. These valid adoption levels included e-interactivity level (involve the use an interactive website that enable 2-way communication to interact with their customers); e-transaction level (involve the use of advanced e-commerce technologies to facilitate transactions like online payments); and e-enterprise level (enables an online conduction of all business processes including accounting system and upgrading traditional businesses to electronic ones). E-interactivity was found to be the most dominant level of adoption (72.3% in quantitative study, and 66.7% in qualitative study) followed by e-transaction level (24.1% in quantitative study, and 26.7% in qualitative study) and lastly e-enterprise level (3.6% in quantitative study, and 6.7% in qualitative study). None of the participating supermarkets was found to be adopting the first three levels of e-commerce which included non-adopters (no application of any e-commerce technology), e-connectivity level (use of basic technologies like e-mail for communication), and e-window level (use of a static website that enable one way communication to present information). On the benefits of e-commerce adoption, which was the second research objective, both the quantitative and qualitative data sets found the top benefits of e-commerce adoption to include creating new channel for advertising, increasing sales and revenue, improving customer service and satisfaction, and increasing market share. Other benefits included reducing operating cost, increasing customer base, enhancing company's image, enhancing competitive advantage, improving business relationship with suppliers, helping to perform jobs more quickly, providing new opportunities, reducing marketing cost, helping to learn more about competitors, improving customer loyalty, improving publicity, and extending market reach. The researcher then compared the mean scores for e-commerce benefits for different e-commerce adoption levels, and it was found that the perception of e-commerce adoption benefits by the participants increased with e-commerce adoption level.

A t-test was conducted for the independent variables to help establish initial understanding of the variables that affect the adoption levels of e-commerce. Factor analysis (Principal

Component Analysis) was used as both a dimension reduction technique, and for construct validity assessment. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values were computed for all constructs to further assess the construct validity. The number of factors for further examination, as well as the number of hypotheses dropped from eight to seven. This was necessary because financial barrier as a factor, was excluded during the factor analysis. A multinomial logistic regression was used to test the suggested hypotheses on the remaining seven factors influencing the adoption of e-commerce. The result of the multinomial regression revealed that the model fitted the data well. The Likelihood Ratio Test found that all the independent variables contributed significantly to the model. However, only six of the seven variables were significant in predicting the choice of the supermarkets in adopting a specific level of e-commerce over another. These six variables included relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support, managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce and government support. Market environment pressure was found to be insignificant and poor predictor of the likelihood of a supermarket to adopt a specific level of e-commerce over another.

Lastly, the qualitative study findings on the fourth research objective indicated that the possible ways to improve e-commerce adoption levels by Nigerian supermarket chains include improving cybersecurity, promoting good shopping experience, addressing infrastructure and logistics problems, training, and sensitisation, securing customers trust and loyalty, availability of reliable internet services, and use of user-friendly websites. Drawing from the findings of this study and information from the body of knowledge, this study developed a framework to enhance e-commerce adoption and sustainability by Nigerian supermarket chains.

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION

6.0 Introduction

This chapter expands on study findings presented in the preceding chapter and compares the results with previous studies. It begins with a description of the profile of the research participants in the first section. The succeeding sections present the analysis of the research findings according to the research objectives. Hence, the second section presents the discussion of the research findings on the extent of e-commerce application by supermarket chains in Nigeria, which is the first research objective. The third section presents the discussion of the findings on the benefits of e-commerce adoption, which is the second research objective. The fourth section presents the discussion of the research findings on the factors that affect the extent of e-commerce adoption by supermarket chains in Nigeria, which is the third research objective. The fifth section presents the discussion of the findings focusing more on how to improve the adoption and sustainability of e-commerce by supermarket chains in Nigeria, which is the fourth research objective. Finally, the last section presents the chapter summary.

6.1 Characteristics of the Respondents

Considering the education level attained by the respondents, it was found that most of the participants in the quantitative study (74.7%) had a bachelor's degree as their maximum academic qualification, while 23% of them had a post graduate degree. A small number of the participants (19%) had Higher National Diploma (HND). The participants in the qualitative study were in senior management roles and had high academic qualifications with bachelor's degree as the dominant academic qualification (47%). This was followed by post graduate degree (33%), and Higher National Diploma (20%). Although both the questionnaire respondents and the interview participants were in managerial positions, all the interview participants were in senior management positions. It was found that participants in the qualitative study had overall higher academic qualification as 33% of them had a post graduate degree compared to the 23% for the survey respondents. Also, the qualitative findings revealed that some of the managers had additional training and professional certifications. For instance, when asked about his highest academic qualification, the participant for case 12 responded:

"I have HND in Accountancy, and I am as well a Chartered Accountant. I'm a member of ICAN (Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria) which is a professional accountancy body with a regulatory authority in Nigeria" (Case 12).

It is not surprising that almost all the managers were well educated. This is due to the high rate of unemployment and underemployment among Nigerian educated labour force. According to Babalobi (2019) as published in Vanguard, a Nigerian newspaper, the figures from the national bureau of statistics (NBS) shows that 33.4% of the Nigerian labour force were unemployed, and that 38.1% of the unemployed were educated beyond the secondary school education. He further stated that 32.26% of recent graduates in Nigeria were unemployed, and many others were wrongly employed or underemployed. Given the high level of unemployment and underemployment among Nigerian graduates, it is unlikely that a candidate with less education qualification than a higher national diploma (HND) can occupy a managerial position in big enterprises. Hence, the high level of education qualification among the managers that participated in the research is justifiable. Also, this high level of education qualification among the participants implies that they were knowledgeable and could be trusted to provide reliable responses to the questions posed to them in both the survey and the qualitative interviews.

Regarding the age of the participants, it was found that all the participants' ages were between 30 and 49 years old, with those aged 40 – 49 years old (51.8%) being a little higher than those aged 30 – 39 years old (48.2%). There were no participants below 30 years or above 49 years. A possible explanation for these age characteristics is that the minimum age for admission into most universities in Nigeria is 16 years (Tolani, 2022), and it takes a minimum of 4 years to complete a bachelor's degree or a higher national diploma (HND) in higher institutions of learning. Another one year is spent by the graduates on the compulsory National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) programme. Therefore, young Nigerian graduates start their first graduate role between the ages of 21 and 26 years, and they may need 4 to 7 years of working experience to ascend to a managerial role. Also, the statutory retirement age in Nigeria is 60 years old (Adetunde, Derby and Imhonopi, 2018). However, most employees working in non-governmental organisations tend to resign from their jobs much earlier than the employees working in governmental organisations because of the better retirement benefits in governmental organisations compared to non-governmental organisations. Therefore, it is not surprising that the managers that participated in the research fall between 30 and 49 years of age category.

Regarding the years of experience, it was found that most of the survey respondents (49.5%) had worked in their supermarkets for 3 to 5 years, while 44% had worked in their supermarkets for more than 5 years. Only 6.5% had worked in their supermarket chains for less than 3 years. For the interview participants, their years of employment ranged from 3 to 8 years with 40%

being actively employed by their supermarket chains for over 5 years. This shows that the research participants had worked in their supermarkets long enough to understand the impact of e-commerce in their supermarkets and the factors that influence the adoption level of e-commerce in their supermarkets.

Concerning the gender distribution of the participants, 62% of them were male, while the other 38% were female. Hence, most of the participants were male. The high proportion of male managers compared to female is not only common to supermarkets in Nigeria. A study by Rahayu (2015) on e-commerce adoption by SMEs in Indonesia found that 72.4% of the participants were male, while only 27.6% were female. A more recent study by Weber and Haseki (2021) on engaging clients in the sales process using social media found that 64% of the participants were male and 36% were female. Therefore, the gender distribution of the participants in this study was not out of order.

6.2 First Research Objective: Investigation of the Extent of E-commerce Application in Nigerian Supermarkets

This section presents the discussion of the research findings on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains, which is the first research objective. The extent of e-commerce application in organisations can be categorised into six different levels. These levels include: “non-adoption, e-connectivity, e-window, e-interactivity, e-transaction and e-enterprise” (Alrousan, 2014, p. 285). Non adopters involve those that do not make use of e-commerce technologies, whilst e-connectivity level involve those that employ basic e-commerce technologies like e-mail for communication. The e-window level includes those that enable one way communication with customers by only using a static website to present information, whilst the e-interactivity level involves the use an interactive website that enable 2-way communication to interact with customers. The e-transaction level involves the use of advanced e-commerce technologies to facilitate transactions like online payments, while the e-enterprise level enables an online conduction of all business processes including accounting system and upgrading traditional businesses to electronic ones (Alrousan, 2014).

These findings reveal that the minimum e-commerce adoption level among Nigerian supermarket chains was e-interactivity level, while the maximum adoption level was the e-enterprise level. Most of the supermarkets were at the e-interactivity level. For instance, the quantitative study findings revealed that 72.3% of the respondents’ supermarkets were still at

the e-interactivity level, while the qualitative findings show that 66.7% are still at the e-interactivity level. The second most adopted level of e-commerce among the supermarkets was the e-transaction level. For example, the quantitative study found that 24.1% of the respondents' supermarkets were currently at this level of adoption, while the qualitative study findings show that 26.7% of the supermarkets are at this level of adoption. Only a few supermarkets were found to be at the e-enterprise level, which is the highest level of e-commerce adoption. The quantitative study found the proportion of participants whose supermarkets were at the e-enterprise adoption level to be only 6 of 166 (3.6%), while the qualitative study findings show that only 1 of 15 (6.7%) supermarkets are at this highest level of adoption. Although the findings from both the quantitative and qualitative studies found that the predominant e-commerce level was the e-interactivity level, which is the use of interactive website to present information about the company and its products, nearly all the supermarkets used barcode scanners at checkout. Most of them had social media pages for advertisement, information dissemination and feedback purposes. According to one of the interviewees whose supermarket was still at the e-interactivity level:

“Besides the website, we are also on social media- Facebook and Instagram. So, people normally visit our website and social media platforms. They make comments on their expectations from our organisation and let us know what they feel about us. We equally get criticism from there which help us to know what we are not doing right that we need to improve on. We use all these information to further develop the business” (Case 12).

In addition to using the social media for information dissemination and advertisement purposes, many supermarkets at different e-commerce application levels also used the social media to engage and interact with the customers. Some of them were also found to be taking orders from customers through the social media and over the phone at the beginning of Covid-19 pandemic, even when they did not have a transactive website at that point. According to one of the participants:

“Although our website is yet to be transactive, we have a dedicated line for taking orders and we also take orders from social media, and some of our customers have been using them to place orders since this covid pandemic” (Case 13).

Comparing these findings to previous studies, Hasan and Mardhani (2021) found a low level of e-commerce application among SMEs in Indonesia. They reported that most firms sold goods and services in the traditional ways. Also, Ocloo et al. (2020) found a low application level of e-commerce among the Ghanaian manufacturing SMEs. Furthermore, a study conducted in Saudi Arabia by Al-Somali, Gholami and Clegg (2015) found that the adoption level of e-commerce in large and small businesses was still low. Among the 201 businesses (67.3% large and 32.7% small businesses) that participated in the study, 19.8% were still at the e-connectivity level, 16.8% at the e-window level, 32.7% at e-interactivity level, 6.4% at e-transaction level, and 24.3% at e-enterprise level. In another research on e-commerce adoption by Indonesian SMEs, Rahayu (2015) found mostly low adoption levels among the businesses as 22.9% of the participating businesses were at the e-connectivity level. Further, 35.7% were at e-window level, 26.6% were at e-interactivity level, 14.3% were at e-transaction level, while only 0.7% were at e-enterprise level. Therefore, there is generally low level of e-commerce adoption among the businesses in the developing countries.

6.3 Second Research Objective: Analysing the Benefits of E-commerce Adoption by Supermarket Chains in Nigeria

This section aims to discuss the benefits of adopting e-commerce by supermarkets in Nigeria, which is the second research objective in this study. It was found that the top six benefits of adopting e-commerce were creating new channel for advertising, enhancing competitive advantage, improving customer services and satisfaction, increasing customer base, increasing sales and revenue, and enhancing company's image. The mean scores of the benefits for different e-commerce adoption levels were found to increase with the adoption levels, indicating that higher adoption level results in better perception of e-commerce. In the qualitative study, enhancing the company's image was displaced by extending market reach, in the list of top six benefits. However, the quantitative study did not assess the extending market reach benefit. Other new benefits that emerged from the qualitative study included improving customers loyalty and improving publicity. Nevertheless, these new benefits were closely related to some of the other benefits tested in the quantitative study. For instance, improving customer loyalty was closely related to increase in customer base. Also, improving publicity was a direct result of providing new channels for advertising. Further, extending market reach directly leads to increase in customer base and market share. According to one of the qualitative study participants:

“E-commerce allows us to reach more people through our website and our presence in social media. As more people get to know about us, the number of our customer increases and so does our market share” (Case 15).

Extending market reach was found to be a popular benefit among the supermarkets based on the participants responses. According to one of the participants,

“E-commerce has enabled us to reach customers from various locations in the city. Ordinarily, our regular customers would have been people that live in this locality. Nonetheless, we have customers that live far away from this neighbourhood that regularly buy our products online” (Case 6).

The above statement agrees with Taher (2021, p. 1) who reported “no geographical limitations” as one of the many e-commerce benefits to business organisations. Other e-commerce benefits to organisations reported by Taher (2021, p. 1) include “lower operational cost”, “increasing efficiency of companies”, “laser targeting market”, “higher ad returns” and business process simplification. The findings of this study on the benefits of e-commerce adoption are consistent with the stage of growth model put forward by Prananto, McKay and Marshall (2003). According to this model, e-commerce benefits realized by businesses are subject to their e-commerce adoption levels. Higher adoption levels require advanced technological infrastructures and yield greater benefits. The findings also agree with the findings of Kraemer, Dedrick and Dunkle (2002, p. 2) which revealed that the greatest impact of e-commerce based on the survey of 2,139 businesses across different countries were “improved customer service, more efficient internal processes, and widened sales area, each mentioned by 30-35% of respondents”. However, more efficient internal process was not assessed in the current work’s quantitative study, neither was it mentioned by any of the participants during the interviews in the qualitative study. Other reported impacts of e-commerce in Kraemer et al. (2002, p. 16) study include “more efficient internal processes; increased staff productivity; increased sales; widened sales area; improved customer service; increased international sales; decreased procurement costs; decreased inventory costs; improved coordination with suppliers; and improved competitive position”. Increase in sale of goods and services was also reported by Hasan and Mardhani (2021), in addition to speedy product promotion. Another study by Rahayu and Day (2017, p. 1) reported that the top six benefits of e-commerce based on the survey of 292 SMEs in Indonesia include “extending market reach, increased sales, improved external communication, improved company image, improved speed of processing, and

increased employee productivity”. Other reported benefits in the study include reduction in operation cost, reduction in procurement and purchasing costs, increase in customer loyalty/retention, reduction in clients complain, improved relationship with suppliers, improved competitive advantage, improvement in speed of processing, improvement in external communication, improvement in internal communication, and increase in employee’s satisfaction. The study also reported that SMEs at higher adoption levels of e-commerce experienced more benefits than those at lower levels. Another study by Tan and Ouyang (2004) discovered that the most significant reported e-commerce benefits among 102 Chinese firms across different cities in the country were extended market reach, improved competitive advantage, and enhanced customer service. They found that benefits associated with efficiency in internal processes and procurement costs reduction were less significant. The findings of Tan and Ouyang (2004) was re-echoed in Kartiwi et al. (2018) who found the major benefits of e-commerce among Malaysian SMEs to include improved customer service, improved customer retention (loyalty), and improved coordination with suppliers and business partners.

However, a study conducted by Molla and Heeks (2007) on the e-commerce benefits in emerging countries based on a survey of 92 South African businesses which have all advanced beyond e-commerce adoption basic stage indicated that e-commerce benefits to most of those South African businesses were still limited to improved communication within and outside the organisations. More tactical benefits relating to cost savings, customer/supplier linking, or wider market access were not found in over 80% of the surveyed organisations. This further limit the probability of more encompassing benefits such as improved competitiveness, disintermediation, and global chains incorporation. Nevertheless, a later study by Abou-Shouk et al. (2013) identified several benefits of e-commerce adoption among Egyptian SMEs, which is another developing country. They categorised the benefits into essential benefits, marketing and competition benefits, and internal business efficiency benefits. The essential benefits include profit, revenue, and sales growth; effective re-intermediation support; attraction of new investment/services; and collaboration enablement and facilitation. Marketing and competition benefits include improved customer satisfaction; customisation of services to suit customer needs; improved competitive advantage; global market reputation establishment; and improved channels of distribution. Internal business efficiency benefits include improved accountability, improved relationship with partners, enhanced satisfaction among staff; easier transaction process; improved knowledge flow within the organisation; and provision of support for

tactical decisions. The authors further remarked that these three categories of benefits positively impact higher level of e-commerce adoption decisions.

6.4 Third Research Objective: Investigating the Factors that Affect the Adoption Levels of E-commerce in Nigerian Supermarkets

This section discusses the factors that affect the extent of e-commerce adoption by supermarkets in Nigeria, and the hypotheses testing relating to these factors. Eight factors were initially proposed in this study, and they are categorised into four dimensions. The attributes of innovation dimension include relative advantages and compatibility variables, whilst the organisational factors dimension consist of technology readiness and financial barrier. The managerial factors dimension consists of top management support, managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, whilst the environmental factors dimension consists of market environment pressure and government support. However, financial barrier was eliminated during the factor analysis and the remaining seven factors were considered in further analysis.

The suggested hypotheses were tested across different levels of e-commerce adoption using multinomial logistic regression. The valid e-commerce levels included e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise. None of the sampled supermarkets was still at the e-connectivity or e-window level of adoption. This is understandable as supermarket chains considered in this study were not small businesses, and many businesses in the recent years now have websites. The likelihood ratio test found that the seven factors considered in the regression analysis significantly contribute to the model. However, the summary of hypotheses results in table 43 reveal that six of the seven factors in the suggested hypotheses were found significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity. These six factors are relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support, managers knowledge, attitude towards e-commerce, and government support. However, only two factors were significant in differentiating between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. These two factors are top management support and government support. Hence, top management support and government support are the most influential factors in the adoption of e-commerce by Nigerian supermarket chains. More details about the proposed hypothesis and how they compare with findings from previous studies are provided in the following subsections.

Table 43: Summary of hypothesis test result

Dimension	Factors	Model 1 (E-transaction vs E-interactivity)	Model 2 (E-enterprise vs E-interactivity)
Attributes of innovation	Relative advantage	Sig (+)	N.S
	Compatibility	Sig (+)	N.S
Organisational factors	Technology readiness	Sig (+)	N.S
Managerial Factors	Top management support	Sig (+)	Sig (+)
	Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce	Sig (+)	N.S
Environmental factors	Market environment pressure	N.S	N.S
	Government support	Sig (+)	Sig (+)

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

6.4.1 Attributes of Innovation

The attributes of innovation dimension include two variables which were used in developing the first two hypotheses as shown below:

H1: Relative advantage has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.

H2: Compatibility has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.

6.4.1.1 Relative Advantage

Relative advantage which refers to the scope of benefits realised from adopting new technology, is one of the most extensively used attributes of innovation within studies that focus on technology adoption (Sparling et al., 2007). The findings of this study shows that relative advantage is one of the important factors that influence Nigerian supermarkets to adopt a higher e-commerce level as it was positive and significant in predicting the participants decision to adopt an e-transaction level of e-commerce against the e-interactivity level. However, relative advantage was not significant in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity levels. The findings from the qualitative study also agree with this quantitative study finding as 47% of the participants interviewed in this study mentioned some of the associated benefits of e-commerce as motivation for their adoption of e-commerce in their

businesses. For instance, a participants mentioned that they adopted a higher e-commerce level to widen their market reach and to harness other potentials of e-commerce. According to the participant:

“We adopted a higher level of e-commerce to help us improve customer services, and to enjoy other associated benefits like widening the market reach, improving competitive advantage, and improving customer satisfaction” (Case 2).

Another participant mentioned that they adopted e-commerce to have a competitive advantage. According to the participant,

“Another reason why we adopted e-commerce is because we believe it will increase our sales and give us a competitive advantage” (Case 5).

This finding agrees with the diffusion of innovation theory which asserts that relative advantage is among the characteristics of innovation that determine their adoption level (Rogers, 1983). Comparing the finding of this study with those of previous studies, the finding agrees with Rawash (2021) who found that relative advantage was a positive and significant determinant in the uptake of e-commerce among Jordanian SMEs. Rahayu and Day (2015) also found that relative advantage (perceived benefits) was one of the factors that influence the adoption of e-commerce among Indonesian businesses. Alrousan (2014) found that relative advantage had a significant and positive influence in distinguishing between e-connectivity and e-window, as well as between e-connectivity and e-interactivity in adoption of e-commerce among travel agencies in Jordan. Many other studies have found relative advantage to positively influence the uptake of e-commerce (Zainuddin et al., 2018; Abou-Shouk et al., 2013; Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2013; Mohammed, Almsafir and Alnaser, 2013; Tan and Eze, 2008).

6.4.1.2 Compatibility

Compatibility was found to be positive and significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity, but not significant in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. The findings from the qualitative study revealed that three of the fifteen interviewees indicated that compatibility was an influencing factor in their level of e-commerce uptake. According to one of the participants,

“It wasn’t very difficult for us to upgrade our e-commerce level to involve online transactions. We had a good interactive website and good ICT infrastructure prior to the upgrade” (Case 8).

The above statement indicates that having compatible ICT systems that can be upgraded to better serve customers' needs is instrumental in adoption of higher e-commerce application levels. Comparing this result to previous studies, Hoang et al. (2021) found that compatibility has a positive impact on e-commerce uptake by SMEs in Vietnam. Many other researchers have found a significant and positive association between compatibility and adoption of e-commerce (Usman and Kumar, 2021; Zainuddin et al., 2018; El-Gohary, 2012; Alam et al., 2008; Sparling et al., 2007). However, this result is contrary to the findings of some previous studies which found insignificant relationship between compatibility and e-commerce adoption level (Rawash, 2021; Rahayu and Day, 2015; Alrousan, 2014; Adewale et al., 2013; Almoawi and Mahmood, 2011).

6.4.2 Organisational Factors

The organisational factors dimension initially consisted of two variables (technology readiness and financial barrier), but the financial barrier variable was eliminated in the factor analysis. Hence, the organisational factor dimension subsequently consists of only technology readiness which was used in developing the third hypothesis shown below.

H3: Technology Readiness has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.

6.4.2.1 Technology Readiness

The resultant items that were used in the measurement of the technology readiness construct following reliability test and factor analysis were sufficient experience with network-based application; high bandwidth connectivity to the internet; existing systems can be customised to customers' need; and availability of IT support staff in the company. Therefore, technology readiness in this study related to both technological and human resources. The result of the multinomial logistic regression revealed that technology readiness was positive and significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity, but not significant in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. The findings from the interview also supported this result as five of fifteen interview participants mentioned issues relating to technology readiness as factors that influenced their e-commerce adoption. One of the participants made the following remark.

“We don't have that capacity yet to manage all the e-commerce-related issues when they occur. That's why we prefer that you come to the store, you can come back to the store if you have any issue, because if you order from our site, it can be sent from any of the stores” (Case 12).

The above statement made by one of the participants when addressing the factors that affect their level of e-commerce adoption shows that he is of the opinion that their supermarket chain is not yet technologically ready to implement e-commerce application level that involves online transaction and home delivery. This further confirms the finding from the quantitative study which indicate that technology readiness is an important factor that significantly influence the e-commerce application level in Nigerian supermarkets. This result agrees with Rawash (2021) who found technology readiness to have positively and significantly influenced the uptake of e-commerce among SMEs in Jordan. Ocloo et al. (2020) also found organisation's readiness to positively influence e-commerce adoption by Ghanaian's manufacturing SMEs. Zhu et al. (2006) also found that technology readiness was, not just a factor, but the most important factor in the adoption of e-business by businesses in developing countries. The result also agrees with many other previous studies which include Aswar (2020), Rahayu and Day (2015), and Tiago and Maria (2010). According to Tiago and Maria (2010), businesses with sufficient technological infrastructures and IT skills would be better positioned to deal with the uncertainty concerning IT adoption than those that lack such capabilities.

6.4.3 Managerial Factors

The managerial factors dimension involves two constructs which were used in developing the fourth and fifth hypotheses shown below.

H4: Top management support has a positive and significant influence the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.

H5: Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.

6.4.3.1 Top Management Support

Top management support was measured by the level of interest expressed by the managers to use e-commerce in the company's business operations; top management's readiness to make available the required resources for implementation of e-commerce; having a mapped strategy for e-commerce infrastructure; willingness to take the risks and accept the changes associated with e-commerce adoption; and the level of CEO involvement in e-commerce adoption and implementation.

The findings reveal that top management support is positive and significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity and differentiating between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. Hence, the finding supports the proposed hypotheses on top management support.

This outcome is also supported by the interview results as five of fifteen participants indicated that top management support affected their ecommerce adoption level. According to one of the interviewees whose supermarket is headquartered abroad, the extent of application of e-commerce in their supermarket chain across the country was based on the top management directive from the headquarters. In his words,

“If there will be any migration or any incursion made by us to the e-commerce itself, it has to cascade down from the home office to us. So anywhere we operate, whether you go to Rwanda, or you go to Angola, or you go to South Africa itself, whatever you see here should be what you will get there” (Case 12).

In comparison to previous studies, this finding agrees with Rawash (2021) who found a positive and significant correlation between management support and e-commerce uptake among Jordanian SMEs. It also agrees with Zainuddin et al. (2018) who found top management support to have significant positive impact on the uptake of e-commerce by SMEs in Klang Valley, Malaysia. The result equally agrees with the findings from many other previous studies which found positive relationship between top management support and e-commerce uptake (Hoang, et al., 2021; Ocloo et al., 2020; Rahayu and Day, 2015; Ramdani et al., 2009; Teo et al., 2009). However, the result disagrees with Alrousan (2014) who found top management support to be insignificant in determining the e-commerce adoption levels among travel agencies in Jordan. The result also disagrees with Levy et al. (2005) and Seyal et al. (2004) as they both found top management support to be statistically insignificant in SMEs adoption of e-commerce.

6.4.3.2 Managers Knowledge and Attitude Towards E-commerce

The proposed hypothesis was supported as the managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce was found to be positive and significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity. However, it was not significant in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. The interview result didn't really portray managers knowledge and attitude as an important factor in the adoption of e-commerce among Nigerian supermarket chains as only one of fifteen interviewees referred to it as an influencing factor in their e-commerce adoption. According to the participant:

“Although we use many e-commerce technologies, the policymakers in our supermarket chain have not felt the need for us to upgrade our e-commerce level to include online transactions” (Case 4).

Some previous studies also found managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce as an important factor in e-commerce uptake (Huy et al., 2012; Xu et al., 2010; Teo et al., 2009). Also, Nasution et al. (2021) found knowledge management process to be an important variable of e-commerce application by SMEs in Indonesia. Furthermore, Zainuddin et al. (2018) found knowledge to have positive and strong significant relationship with e-commerce adoption. Nevertheless, a few previous studies did not find managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce to be correlated with e-commerce adoption (Alrousan, 2014; Chau and Jim, 2002). Also, Hussein (2009) discovered that managers' attitudes towards e-commerce were only important in distinguishing between adopters and non-adopters, but insignificant in differentiating between lower and higher adoption levels.

6.4.4 Environmental Factors

The environmental factors dimension includes two constructs which were used in developing the sixth and seventh hypotheses shown below.

H6: Market environment pressure has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.

H7: Government support has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarkets.

6.4.4.1 Market Environment Pressure

The items used in measuring market environment pressure included pressure from customers, pressure from suppliers and pressure from partners to use e-commerce. The proposed hypothesis was not supported as market environment pressure was not significant in differentiating between e-transaction and e-interactivity and differentiating between e-enterprise and e-interactivity levels of e-commerce adoption among the supermarket chains. The interview result supports this finding as none of the interviewees indicated that market environment pressure has influenced their level of e-commerce adoption. This is probably because e-commerce had not been thriving in Nigeria before the 2020 Covid pandemic. According to Dada (2019, p. 1), "Nigeria does not seem to be ready for e-commerce as we know it." This statement was made following an interview with Olumide Olusanya, the then CEO of Gloo.ng, one of the pioneer e-commerce businesses in Nigeria, shortly after the news of planned closure of the company's e-commerce business activities emerged on 14 January 2019. To justify the statement, the author further mentioned that Nigerians had seen similar e-commerce related businesses like OLX Nigeria, DealDey, and Efritrin bleed to death (Dada,

2019). The finding of this study is consistent with Rahayu and Day (2017) who found that customers/suppliers pressure was not an important determinant in e-commerce uptake among SMEs in Indonesia. The result also agrees with the findings of Rawash (2021) and supports the findings of Al-Qirim (2007), but disagrees with some studies (Hoang, et al., 2021; Alsaad et al., 2018; Alrousan 2014; Ifinedo, 2011; Al-Qirim, 2006; Chong, 2008).

6.4.4.2 Government Support

The government support construct was measured by availability of e-commerce related and cybercrime-discouraging government regulations, and availability of e-commerce encouraging telecommunication infrastructure and internet technology. Government support was found to be an important factor in the uptake of e-commerce among Nigerian supermarket chains as it was found to be positive and significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity, and in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. Hence, the proposed hypothesis was fully supported. The interview results also support this finding as 27% of the participants indicated that government support plays important role in their adoption level of e-commerce. One of the interview participants who remarked that internet security was a major concern among online shoppers, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, further stated:

“Government’s anti-graft regulatory bodies like the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC), and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) which combat cybercrime encouraged us to adopt higher level of e-commerce that involve online transactions” (Case 5).

According to another participant,

“Availability of infrastructures such as good road network, regular power supply, and good house and street addressing systems are essential for application of advanced level e-commerce and the government plays a major role in providing these infrastructures” (Case 10).

The above statements indicate that the government plays a significant role in the effective application of different levels of e-commerce within Nigerian supermarket chains and across various business organisations in the country. This is because the government plays a significant role in providing infrastructures required for e-commerce operations including safe internet technology, energy (electricity), good quality road network and good home and street addressing systems which are instrumental to e-commerce logistics operations. According to Adewole (2019, p. 21), “poor inland road quality” is among the basic considerable logistical challenges while attempting to conduct business in Africa's markets.

This finding is consistent with Rawash (2021) who found a positive and significant association between government support and e-commerce uptake among Jordanian SMEs. It also agrees with Rahayu and Day (2017) who found that external support, such as government and IT vendor supports, was positive and significant in determining the adoption level of e-commerce among Indonesian SMEs. Alrousan (2014) also discovered that government support was positive and significant in distinguishing between e-window and e-connectivity, as well as distinguishing between e-interactivity and e-connectivity, but not significant in distinguishing between e-interactivity and e-window. Furthermore, Gibbs and Kraemer (2004) reported that government support was an important factor in e-commerce implementation by firms across ten countries which include United States, Germany, France, Japan, Mexico, China, Singapore, Denmark, Taiwan, and Brazil. The result is also consistent with many other studies which include Huang et al. (2021), Huy et al. (2012), Hung et al. (2011), and Zhu and Kraemer (2005).

6.5 Fourth Research Objective: Measures to Improve E-commerce Adoption and Sustainability

This section discusses the findings on the means of improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains, based on participants' responses in the interviews. A framework for enhancing e-commerce adoption and sustainability was developed in the findings chapter based on the research findings. Recommendations based on the developed framework will be presented in the next chapter. Participants' responses on how to improve e-commerce adoption reveal that internet security is essential for improved e-commerce adoption as 40% of the interview participants suggested it to improve e-commerce adoption. Other suggested means to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains include promoting good shopping experience (27%), training and sensitisation (27%), securing customers trust and loyalty (20%), reliable internet service (20%), user-friendly websites (13%), and improving house and street addressing system and other infrastructures (13%). These suggested measures are further discussed in the following sub-sections.

6.5.1 Internet Security

Six of fifteen participants (40%) suggested that improving internet security was one of the means of improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability. This is probably because higher levels of e-commerce adoption involve online transactions, and customers intending to carry out online transactions that involve online payment may be worried that internet fraudsters

could gain access to their banking details which could result in losing money to the fraudsters, due to high level of cybercrime in the country. According to one of the research participants, *“Some customers are really worried about the security of online transactions in the country due to the activities of internet fraudsters, as their bank details could be compromised resulting in loss of savings. Therefore, it is important that the EFCC (Economic and Financial Crime Commission) should step up their game in tackling the cybercrime”* (Case 6).

Comparing the findings of this study to previous studies, Amornkitvikai and Lee (2020) found that poor internet security and customers' awareness of e-commerce are the two biggest obstacles to e-commerce uptake. Usman and Kumar (2021) also found that cybersecurity and online privacy are among the key determinants of consumers intention to use online shops in Nigeria. Also, Adelola et al. (2014) remarked that lack of trust and fears regarding privacy remained the greatest obstacle to e-commerce growth. Furthermore, Niranjanamurthy and Chahar (2013, cited in Adelola, 2017, p. 1) remarked that “security and privacy has become a major concern for consumers with the rise of identity theft and impersonation, and any concern for consumers must be treated as a major concern for e-commerce providers.” Although an anti-cybercrime legislation, CYBERCRIMES (PROHIBITION, PREVENTION, ETC) ACT, 2015, exists in Nigeria, the government, financial institutions, and the supermarkets need to do more to improve cybersecurity and increase customers confidence on internet privacy and security.

6.5.2 Promoting Good Shopping Experience

Four of fifteen participants (27%) mentioned that good shopping experience is important for improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability. This result was not surprising as bad shopping experience would discourage customers from using the online services. Good shopping experience depends on several factors which include product reliability, and excellent customer service among others. According to one of the interviewees, reliability of the items purchased online matters to the customers. Many customers are sceptical about online products due to the fear of receiving a substandard or damaged product. Also, a good customer service goes a long way in promoting good shopping experience. For, instance prompt response to customers queries and quick resolution of issues surrounding online orders will boost customers confidence in the services they receive and increase the chances of their continued use of the online services. According to one of the participants:

“I personally believe that whatever will guarantee the customer’s trust in your products, in your business, and whatever will ensure efficient customer service should be put in place to help improve e-commerce” (Case 12).

Another participant believed that improving the reliability of items sold online can help to improve customers satisfaction and improve sustainability of high-level e-commerce application. According to the participant,

“Reliability of the items purchased online promotes good shopping experience. Many customers are sceptical about online products due to fear of receiving a substandard or damaged items” (Case 14).

This finding is in line with Usman and Kumar (2021) who found that perceived service quality influences consumers intention to use online shops. It also agrees with Omotayo and Omotope (2018, p. 2) who found that “perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, subjective norms, perceived enjoyment, perceived site quality, convenience, prior experience, shopping habit and trust” are determinants of students’ intention to continue to use online shops in Nigeria.

6.5.3 Sensitisation and Training

Four of fifteen participants suggested concepts relating to sensitisation and training as means of improving e-commerce adoption and continued use. According to one of the participants, many customers still do not know they could buy groceries and other supermarket items online. In his words:

“Although e-commerce is gaining increasing acceptance among Nigerians, many Nigerians still lack sufficient knowledge of e-commerce and how it works. Many of our customers make payments with their bank cards at our checkout points using the POS, but majority of them may not have done online transactions before. So, there is need for public sensitisation” (Case 6).

This an indication that majority of Nigerians have not really ordered any item online, and do not really know how they could use their bank cards and make payments online as they are used to paying for products and services with cash. Although, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) introduced the cashless policy in 2012, cash remains the main mode of payment for majority of Nigerians (Elechi and Anthony, 2016). Therefore, Umar and Ogbonnaya (2020) recommended a continued aggressive sensitisation of the public by the Apex bank, to improve

the acceptability and implementation of the cashless policy. Also, in previous research by Ibam et al. (2018) on e-commerce in Africa, using Nigeria as a case study, they recommended proper sensitisation of the public on the use of electronic payment systems and their effectiveness to help boost public confidence on the system. Nevertheless, supermarkets can also improve awareness of their e-commerce activities through adverts on news and social media.

6.5.4 Securing Customers Trust and Loyalty

Three of fifteen participants suggested securing customers trust and loyalty as means of improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability. Customers trust in supermarkets ability to keep online transaction secure, and confidence in their product as well as good shopping experience often lead to customers loyalty. According to Ibam et al. (2018), lack of trust is a serious challenge to e-commerce in Africa. In 2015, the Nigerian inter-Bank Settlement System reported that 8.8% of online transactions in the country were fraudulent (Ibam et al., 2018). No wonder Nigerian shoppers are not eager to embrace e-commerce. According to one of the research participants, anything that will guarantee the customer's trust in the products and in the business and ensure efficient customer service will help to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability. Besides trust, other factors that have been reported to improve customer loyalty include listed price, products variety, as well as membership and promotion activities (Alsulami, 2021).

6.5.5 Reliable Internet Services

Three of fifteen interviewees suggested improving the availability of reliable internet services across the country as means of improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability. E-commerce activities take place over the internet. A reliable internet service is required to run e-commerce technologies, and internet is not affordably available to many Nigerians. According to one of the research participants:

“High level e-commerce technologies are run with reliable internet service which unfortunately is not affordably available to many Nigerians. Making reliable internet service readily available and affordable to both organisations and customers can help to improve e-commerce adoption and continued use” (Case 4).

This finding agrees with Ibam et al. (2018) who suggested making internet and other ICT infrastructure affordably available in every part of the country to improve adoption of e-commerce.

6.5.6 User Friendly Websites

Two of fifteen participants recommended making supermarkets websites for online shopping friendly as a means of improving e-commerce adoption. This will enable customers to easily find products on the websites, chose items of interest and make payment without difficulty. It will also help to improve shopping experience and promote sustainability of high level of e-commerce. As Alavi and Ahuja (2021) remarked, repurchases made by customers directly reflects good shopping experience, otherwise known as online customer satisfaction. According to one of the participants:

“I believe that having a user-friendly website can help to sustain a high level of e-commerce, because it will enable customers to easily connect and navigate through the website and search for items they want to buy, and equally make payments on the website with ease” (Case 4).

This result is in line with Davis (1989) Technology Acceptance model which postulates that perceived ease of use influences attitude towards the use of an innovation. This is also in agreement with Lee and Zubir (2022) who found that women who believe that technology is simple to use are more likely to use e-commerce in their businesses. Furthermore, Omotayo and Omotope (2018) found that ease of use is among the factors that influence Nigerian students to use online shops. Sudiana, Chandra and Angela (2021) also found that a well-designed website could improve online shoppers’ user experience.

6.5.7 Addressing the Infrastructure and Logistics Problems

Four of the fifteen interview participants (27%) recommended addressing the infrastructure and logistic problems in Nigeria to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains. In addition to regular power supply, good road network and good house and street addressing system are essential for e-commerce as they are vital for efficient delivery systems. As one of the interviewees rightly remarked,

“Improving house and street addressing system will help to increase the number of people that make online purchases. The current house and street addressing system is very poor as many streets do not have names and many houses do not have numbers” (Case 3).

This participant’s opinion also agrees with a Guardian news on the document obtained from Nigerian Ministry of Communications in 2017 which shows that the poor addressing system in

Nigeria results in only 20% of Nigerians receiving mail at home. It further revealed that 79% of businesses and homes were not able to receive deliveries, while the other 1% received their mails through one of the 478,000 post office boxes across the nation (Adepetun, 2017). The then Minister of Communications, Adebayo Shittu, recognised poor infrastructure with respect to postal addresses, roads, and utilities as some of the challenges to e-commerce development in the country (Ogunfuwa, 2018). However, the Nigeria Postal Services (NIPOST) was reported to be making effort to improve e-commerce services using its new addressing system, what3words (Ogunfuwa, 2018; Adepetun, 2017). What3words uses three random words to create a geocoding system and has been found to work well in Nigerian locations with non-standardised addressing system (Stewart et al., 2020). Nevertheless, many Nigerians are ignorant of this innovation. Conversely, recent literature suggests there is improvement in delivery services across the nation as many businesses adopted online sales due to Covid-19 pandemic as people around the region were compelled to stay away from crowded public spaces like shopping malls because of the pandemic (Goel, 2022). For instance, a bicycle-based delivery business, Errand360, had recently partnered strategically with Jumia Food Nigeria to provide last-mile delivery services to Jumia's customers (Nnamani, 2022). Jumia Technology, the pan-African e-commerce platform, has also been reported to have recently partnered with United Parcel Service (UPS) to increase Jumia's delivery options for customers and businesses within the continent (THISDAY, 2022).

6.6 Chapter Summary

The findings on the four research objectives were discussed in this chapter. The findings from the interviews were integrated with the findings from the questionnaire in the discussion. With respect to the first research objective, majority of the supermarket chains in Nigeria remain at the e-interactivity adoption level of e-commerce, which involves the use of an interactive website that doesn't support online transactions.

The chapter's second section discussed the findings on the benefits of e-commerce adoption among Nigerian supermarket chains. In this study, the top six e-commerce adoption benefits include creating new channel for advertising, enhancing competitive advantage, improving customer services and satisfaction, increasing customer base, increasing sales and revenue, and extending the market reach.

The third part of this chapter discussed the findings on the influencing factors of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains and the hypotheses associated with them. Six of the

seven considered factors significantly influenced the adoption of e-commerce. The six factors include relative advantage, compatibility, technology readiness, top management support, managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, and government support. Market environment pressure was found to be insignificant in influencing the adoption level of e-commerce among the supermarkets. All the six significant factors were positive in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity. However, only two of them (top management support and government support) were significant in differentiating between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. Therefore, the most influencing factors in e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains are top management support and government support.

This chapter also discussed the findings on the measures for improving e-commerce uptake and sustainability in Nigerian supermarkets based on the responses of the interview participants. Improving internet security was the most suggested means of improving e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains. Other suggested means include promoting good shopping experience, addressing infrastructure and logistics problems, sensitisation and training, securing customers trust and loyalty, reliable internet services, and user-friendly websites. The next chapter presents the conclusions, contributions, and recommendations.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the study's conclusion according to the findings from the previous chapters. It further presents implications and recommendations to different stakeholders, as well as the study's contributions and its limitations.

7.1 Research Summary

The aim of this research was to study the adoption of e-commerce by supermarket chains in Nigeria with the objective of understanding the factors influencing the adoption levels, the current state of the adoption, the adoption benefits, and devising a framework for improving the adoption and sustainability of e-commerce in the industry. Following an extensive review of literature, eight hypotheses were developed for testing in the study. Data was collected using questionnaires as well as semi-structured interviews. 166 of 188 returned questionnaires supplied the data used for the descriptive analysis and multinomial logistic regression analysis in the quantitative analysis, while data from semi structured interviews with 15 managers provided support to the findings of the quantitative study.

The following sections presents the summary of the study objectives and theory, the chosen approach, hypotheses, key findings, implications and recommendations, the study's contributions, limitations and suggestions for future studies, and the chapters' summary.

7.2 Summary of Theory and Developed Hypotheses

As discusses in chapter one, the four objectives set out for this study are as follows:

1. To examine the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains
2. To analyse the benefits of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains
3. To examine the factors that affect the extent of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains
4. To develop measures to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains.

The literature review was categorised into three sections: theoretical, conceptual, and contextual reviews. The relevant theories in e-commerce adoption and the concept of e-commerce were presented in chapter two, while the contextual review (e-commerce in Nigeria) was done in chapter three. Although seven theories and integrated models were discussed in theoretical review, the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework, and the

Diffusion of Innovation (DoI) theory most influenced the development of this study's framework. Following an extensive literature review, eight hypotheses associated with the factors affecting e-commerce adoption were proposed for examination in the study. However, the hypothesis associated with the financial barrier factor was dropped following the elimination of the financial barrier during the dimension reduction process in the principal component analysis (factor analysis). Hence, only the seven hypotheses outlined below were examined using multinomial logistic regression analysis.

- H1: Relative advantage has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- H2: Compatibility has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- H3: Technology readiness has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- H4: Top management has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- H5: Managers' knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce has a positive and significant influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- H6: Market environment pressure has a positive influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.
- H7: Government and vendor support has a significant and positive influence on the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

The methodology adopted in this study was explained in chapter four. The mixed research method was adopted because it helped to answer the research questions more comprehensively. The questionnaire was chosen for quantitative data collection, while semi-structured interview was chosen for qualitative data collection. The research findings were presented and analysed in chapter. A framework for improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability in Nigerian supermarket chains was equally developed in chapter 5 based on the research findings, while chapter six discussed the research findings. Descriptive analysis and multinomial logistic regression analysis were used to analyse the data in the quantitative study, while thematic

analysis was used to analyse the data in the qualitative study. Findings from both studies were integrated in the discussion.

7.3 Summary of Key Findings

This section presents the summary of key findings regarding the four objectives of this study: extent of e-commerce application, benefits of e-commerce, factors affecting the extent of e-commerce adoption, and measures to improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability by supermarket chains in Nigeria.

7.3.1 Extent of E-commerce Application in Nigerian Supermarket chains

E-interactivity, which is the use of interactive website that does not allow online transactions was found to be the minimum and the most common e-commerce adoption level among the supermarket chains in Nigeria. For instance, 72.3% of the of the respondents in the quantitative study indicated that their supermarkets were still at this level of e-commerce adoption. However, the qualitative study found that proportion to be 66.7% which was not much different from the findings in the quantitative study. Also, the quantitative study found that the supermarkets for 24.1 % of the participants were currently at the e-transaction level of adoption which permits online transactions, while only 3.6% were at the e-enterprise level, which is the highest adoption level. The e-enterprise level involves online conduction of all business processes including accounting system and upgrading traditional businesses to electronic ones. None of the supermarket chains were still at the lower levels of e-commerce adoption which are e-connectivity (use of basic e-commerce technology like e-mails for communication), and e-window (use of static website that allow only one way communication to present information). The adoption of e-interactivity level of e-commerce by most of the supermarkets implies that e-commerce adoption by the supermarket chains in Nigeria is still relatively low compared to those in developed countries which are mostly adopting the e-transaction and e-enterprise levels.

7.3.2 Benefits of E-commerce Adoption to Nigerian Supermarket Chains

The top six e-commerce adoption benefits in the quantitative study are creating new channel for advertising, enhancing competitive advantage, improving customer services and satisfaction, increasing customer base, increasing sales and revenue, and enhancing company's image. In the qualitative study, enhancing company's image was displaced by extending market reach, in the list of top six benefits. However, the extending market reach was not explored in the quantitative study. The mean scores of the benefits for different ecommerce adoption levels

were found to increase with the adoption levels, indicating that higher adoption level results in better perception of e-commerce benefits.

7.3.3 Factors Affecting the Extent of E-commerce Adoption in Nigerian Supermarkets

Eight factors categorised into four dimensions including innovation attributes, organisational components, managerial components, and market environment components were proposed for study in this research. The dimension of innovation attributes involves relative advantages and compatibility. The organisational factors dimension consists of technology readiness and financial barrier. The managerial factors dimension consists of top management support and managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce, while the environmental factors dimension consists of market environment pressure and government support. However, financial barrier was eliminated during the factor analysis and the remaining seven factors were considered in the multinomial logistic regression for hypothesis testing.

In the attributes of innovation dimension, both relative advantage and compatibility were found to be positive and significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity adoption levels, but inconsequential in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. In the organisational factors dimension, technology readiness was found positive in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity levels of e-commerce, but not significant in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. In the managerial factors dimension, top management support, as well as managers' knowledge and attitude toward e-commerce, were both positive and significant in distinguishing between the e-transaction and e-interactivity levels of e-commerce, but only top management support was found significant in distinguishing between e-enterprise and e-interactivity. In the environmental factors dimension, both market environment pressure and government support were found positive and significant in distinguishing between e-transaction and e-interactivity levels of e-commerce, but only government support was found significant in differentiating between e-enterprise and e-interactivity levels. Therefore, this study found top management support and government support as the most influential factors in e-commerce adoption among Nigerian supermarket chains.

7.3.4 Measures to Improve E-commerce Adoption and Sustainability Amongst Supermarkets in Nigeria

Addressing security concerns regarding online transactions is the most suggested measure for improving e-commerce adoption levels and sustainability in Nigerian supermarkets. Other

suggested measures include promoting good shopping experience, training, and sensitisation, securing customers trust and loyalty, reliable internet service, use of user-friendly websites, and improving house and street addressing system.

7.4 Recommendations

This study has some recommendations for the Nigerian government (policymakers), IT vendors, and the supermarket owners. The recommendations made to these stakeholders are based on the findings from the previous chapters, especially findings on the factors that influence e-commerce adoption, and findings on measures for improving e-commerce adoption and sustainability, which are respectively the third and fourth objectives of this study.

7.4.1 Recommendations for Nigerian Government

The findings of this study have shown that government support is one of the most influential factors in the adoption of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains. Government support can positively impact e-commerce through legislation and policy making, enforcing compliance to laws and regulations relating to cyber security, provision of training and sensitisation programmes, provision of infrastructure needed for improved e-commerce such as improving internet infrastructure across the nation, good road network, and improving house and street addressing system among others.

Although anti cybercrime legislation, CYBERCRIMES (PROHIBITION, PREVENTION, ETC) ACT, 2015, exists in Nigeria, the government needs to do more to improve cybersecurity and increase customers confidence on internet privacy and security as these two have been identified as a major concern for consumers and potential online shoppers due to a rise in identity theft and impersonation in the country. The anti-graft regulatory bodies like the “Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission” (ICPC), and “Economic and Financial Crimes Commission” (EFCC), that are used in fighting cybercrime need to step up their game in cramping down and prosecuting regulation defaulters. Also, the government could set up a similar agency with more defined roles surrounding e-commerce and data security-associated crimes if the existing bodies are too occupied with other anti-graft activities. In a nutshell, the government needs to design a robust regulatory framework to strengthen e-commerce and protect customers and businesses against internet fraud. On sensitisation and training, the government should use agencies like the National Orientation Agency (NOA) to sensitise the public as well as the supermarkets on the benefits of e-

commerce as perceived benefit was found in this study to be an important factor in e-commerce adoption. This sensitisation and training can be done through workshops and seminars.

Concerning e-commerce related infrastructure, good road network, availability of reliable and affordable internet services that spans throughout the regions in the country, and good house and street addressing system have been found to play a significant role in the adoption of e-commerce. The government should therefore address the shortcomings in these regards to better position the country on the path for massive adoption and sustainable implementation of advanced levels of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains and other industries in the country.

7.4.2 Recommendations for the Supermarkets

The findings of this study provide a useful framework for Nigerian supermarket chains owners and top managers to improve their e-commerce adoption decisions. It is recommended that the decision makers should assess their current adoption level and decide the most beneficial level for their supermarkets, and use the knowledge provided by this study to develop strategies and roadmap for improving their e-commerce adoption to reap more benefit should they be interested in doing so. This study also revealed the factors that influence adoption of e-commerce. The supermarkets can therefore employ the findings of this study on the influential factors of e-commerce adoption in their strategy development.

As this study identified top management support as one of the two most influential factors of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains, the top managers and the decision makers in the supermarkets should know that improving e-commerce adoption in their organisations largely depend on them. They should therefore review their current level of adoption and the benefits they derive from it as well as the potential benefits for higher level of adoption as the findings of this study showed that greater perception of e-commerce benefits results in higher level of adoption. They should also develop a clear vision on the use of e-commerce technologies in their supermarkets, allocate the required resources for their e-commerce improvement and be willing to accept the changes associated with e-commerce.

Since this study also identified compatibility, technology readiness and managers knowledge and attitude towards e-commerce as significantly influencing factors of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains, the supermarkets top managers and decision makers should ensure that they invest in adequate technology infrastructure that will make them compatible

and technologically ready for a level of e-commerce that befits their business. Adequate IT training should also be provided to employees to make them efficient in the use of e-commerce technologies.

For the supermarkets that have already adopted a higher level of e-commerce adoption that involve online transactions, the top managers and decision makers should ensure that their supermarkets websites are developed with features that will guarantee secure transactions as data privacy and security have been identified as a major concern for consumers with respect to e-payment in Nigeria and other developing countries. They should also ensure that the websites are developed to be simple and easy to use to make it user-friendly; ensure the reliability of the items they send to customers that purchased online; ensure effective and efficient packaging/delivery system and other customer services to promote impressive online shopping experience, improve online customer satisfaction, and secure the trust and loyalty of online customers. These will help to keep them shopping online and ensure sustainability of high level of e-commerce adoption.

7.4.3 Recommendation for the IT Consultants and Web Vendors

This study equally has recommendations for IT consultants and web vendors. They should employ the knowledge provided by the findings of this research work on the factors that influence various adoption levels of e-commerce and measures to improve adoption in designing and developing strategies for sustainable high adoption levels among the supermarket chains in Nigeria.

They should also employ the findings of this study to gain a better understanding of the knowledge and perceptions of the supermarkets' top managers on the use of e-commerce applications, identify reasons for their current level of adoption, and tailor solutions for them. They should design a suitable model for each level of adoption, based on the findings of this study.

Furthermore, since this study found that relative advantage is a significant factor in the adoption of e-commerce, the IT consultants should enlighten the decision makers on attainable benefits of e-commerce through personal visits, seminars, and conferences. Lastly, the web vendors should ensure that ease of use and security of data are factored in designing supermarkets websites to help promote sustainability of higher level of e-commerce adoption.

7.5 Contribution of Study

This study has made significant contributions to theory, to method, and to practice. These contributions are detailed in the subsections that follow.

7.5.1 Contributions to Theory

This study provides a holistic image of the available literature on information technology, especially in the adoption of e-commerce. It reviewed the most important theories and models in the adoption of IT systems and evaluated their strengths and weaknesses, and the organisational applicability of these models to give the best explanation of the adoption of e-commerce in supermarket chains particularly in Nigeria, and supermarket chains generally in developing countries.

On that basis, this study created a conceptual framework anchored on Technology-Organization-Environment framework, and the Diffusion of Innovation (DoI) theory to investigate the different factors that affect the level of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains.

7.5.2 Contributions to Method

This research applied a mixed research method, a trend that has been gaining growing relevance in social research (Bell, et al., 2003). Many previous studies in e-commerce adoption have used mono methods, predominantly quantitative method, which relies on a single data set and does not provide the researcher with an opportunity to richly gain insights from multiple points of view. The mixed research method used in this study, which involved collecting quantitative data with questionnaires and collecting qualitative data with semi-structured interviews allowed the researcher to view the same phenomenon from different perspectives. Also, the findings from the qualitative study consolidates the findings from the quantitative study. Therefore, this study adds voice to the significance of data triangulation, which has helped to gain critical insight on the adoption of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarket chains.

Additionally, this study measured its dependent variable as multichotomous variable which evaluates different adoption levels (non-adoption, e-connectivity, e-widow, e-interactivity, e-transaction, and e-enterprise). This is opposed to majority of the previous studies that measured the dependent variable as a dichotomous variable consisting of only adoption and non-adoption. Unlike the dichotomous measure, the multichotomous measure used in this study captures the depth and broadness of e-commerce technology adoption (Rahayu 2015; Gibbs and Kraemer, 2004), eliminating the limitations of the dichotomous measure.

Hence, the approach of this study on the concept of e-commerce adoption levels boosts the strength of the study and adds to the body of knowledge. The study found that various e-commerce adoption levels are influenced by different predictors in the model proposed in the study. A good understanding of the influencing factors for different e-commerce adoption levels in supermarket chains adds value to e-commerce adoption literature in developing countries, especially in the context of Nigeria. Furthermore, the measurement model used in this study will hopefully be applied for studies in supermarket chains in other developing countries.

7.5.3 Managerial Implications

This study provides a holistic knowledge of the factors that affect the extent of e-commerce application in Nigerian supermarket chains, and measures to improve the extent of application and sustainability of high-level e-commerce in the industry. The study further developed a framework to help improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability in the supermarket chains, which may be applied to supermarket chains in other developing countries. Therefore, the study's findings will help Nigerian supermarket chains decision makers and policymakers to comprehend the significant elements of various e-commerce adoption levels and measures to improve their e-commerce adoption levels and sustainability. Some managerial implications to help improve e-commerce adoption and sustainability of high-level e-commerce application in the supermarket chains based on the findings of the study are outlined in the following subsections.

7.5.3.1 Improve Cybersecurity and Online Privacy

This study identified cybersecurity as one of the serious challenges of e-commerce that needs to be addressed to improve e-commerce application levels and sustainability in Nigerian supermarkets. The managers and decision makers within the supermarkets need to collaborate with the relevant government regulatory bodies and other stakeholders to improve online privacy and security of sensitive data used in online transactions. They can also employ Artificial Intelligence methods, particularly deep learning and machine learning, to enhance cybersecurity measures (Zeadally et al., 2020). Data science can also be applied with AI to improve cybersecurity (Humayun et al., 2021). Other measures that could be employed to improve cybersecurity include establishing basic central contacts for guidance and advice; training the employees to recognise cybersecurity warning signs; regular software update; implementing multi-factor authentication; and regular system vulnerability audit (Green, 2021).

7.5.3.2 Make Websites User-Friendly

The supermarket managers and policymakers should ensure that their websites are designed to be user-friendly. This will make it easy for customers to find information and items from their websites with ease and successfully check out with less difficulty and improve the overall user experience. This is in line with Davis (1989) Technology Acceptance model which postulates that perceived ease of use influences attitude towards the use of an innovation. This also agrees with the findings of Lee and Zubir (2022), Sudiana et al. (2021), and Omotayo and Omotope (2018), who reported that a well-designed website and ease of use positively influence the adoption and acceptance of e-commerce.

7.5.3.3 Review Current Adoption Level

The supermarket managers and policymakers should review their current level of e-commerce application, evaluate the prospects of adopting a higher level and make a strategic decision on whether to improve their adoption level for more benefits since this study and previous studies found that higher adoption levels result in greater benefits; or to remain at their current application level. They should be willing to accept the changes associated with adopting a higher e-commerce level and prepare their staff for the change through appropriate change management process.

7.5.3.4 Develop a Strategy for E-Commerce Improvement and Sustainability

The supermarket chains top managers and decision makers need to map out a clear strategy for e-commerce improvement and sustainability. Although the findings of this study show that a reasonable percentage (over 27%) of the supermarket chains in Nigeria have well advanced in their application of e-commerce technology to the extent of e-transaction which permits online shopping and transaction, and the use of barcode scanners and EPOS (Electronic Point of Sale) system is widespread in the industry, there is still need for the various decision makers in the industry to map out strategy for either improvement of adoption level for those operating below the e-transaction level, or sustainability of advanced level of adoption. Therefore, they should review their various adoption levels, and identify areas of improvement.

7.5.3.4 Capacity Building

The supermarkets decision makers need to commit to capacity development in terms of both infrastructure and human capacity, for effective application and sustainability of high e-commerce adoption level. This is in line with Maryama and Suhongb (2022) who recommended capacity building to Nigerian SMEs to improve adoption of ICT.

7.5.3.5 Embark on Public Sensitisation

Although the use of online shops is increasing among Nigerians, many Nigerians still feel constrained from using online shops due to poor house and street addressing systems in the country. However, this poor addressing system challenge can be mitigated with the use of What3Words for delivery services. What3words uses three random words to create a geocoding system and has been found to work well in Nigerian locations with non-standardised addressing system (Stewart, et al., 2020). Nevertheless, many Nigerians are ignorant of this innovation. Therefore, the supermarkets need to embark on sensitisation programmes to create more awareness on Wha3Words capabilities, and further enlighten the public on the potentials of e-commerce. This can be done with the use of advertisements.

7.5.3.6 Improve User Experience

There is need for the supermarket managers to improve customer satisfaction and customer trust through improved packaging and delivery system and other customer services. This will help to encourage the customers to use and to keep using the supermarket chains online services and ensure sustainability of high-level e-commerce adoption in the industry. This is in line with Usman and Kumar (2021) who found that perceived service quality influences consumers intention to use online shops.

7.5.3.7 Collaborate with the Government and other E-commerce Stakeholders

The supermarkets need to utilize public-private partnerships (PPP) to work together with the government and other e-commerce stakeholders in the country to create a favourable environment for e-commerce progress and e-commerce sustainability in the country. This collaboration is essential as this study found government support as one of the most influencing factors on the extent of e-commerce application in the supermarket industry. The government can play a significant role in improving e-commerce related infrastructures like good road network, efficient house and street addressing system, reliable internet service, efficient power supply, and enforcing cybersecurity laws. The need for improving e-commerce adoption and its sustainability in Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized as it is a vibrant source of economic growth which can significantly add to the country's GDP. As Bvepfepfe (2019) rightly remarked, the adoption of prevailing technologies around the world, like e-commerce, is the key to economic growth in Africa.

7.6 Limitations of Study

Although this study presents a holistic view of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains, it still suffers some limitations as discussed hereunder.

1. This is a cross-sectional study which was completed within a pre-defined timeframe due to it being a doctoral study for an international student in the UK. Being a strategic decision, e-commerce related decision-making process for some supermarkets may evolve over time, which may necessitate a longitudinal study. Nevertheless, collecting both quantitative and qualitative data in this study helped to mitigate the impact of this limitation as the semi-structured interviews allowed the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the variables that influenced the adoption decisions for the supermarket chains. Also, the data collection for this study lasted for over three months which enabled the researcher to gain an insight on how e-commerce adoption decisions changed overtime time.
2. The data for this study was collected just at the beginning of Covid-19 pandemic. E-commerce adoption levels in all countries improved due to Covid-19, however, its impact was not fully captured in the data for this study. Nevertheless, evidence from some of the semi-structured interviews which were conducted at the early stage of the pandemic revealed that some of the supermarkets improved their extent of e-commerce application due to the pandemic. Furthermore, the study made references to pieces of literature that portrayed the impact of covid on e-commerce in the country.
3. The data for this study was collected only from Nigerian supermarkets which may restrict the applicability of its findings by supermarkets in other developing countries. However, the researcher collected data extensively, and this study can serve as a basis for theoretical framework development for e-commerce studies in supermarket chains in other developing countries.

7.7 Suggestions for Future Research

Given the limitations of this study outlined in the preceding section, opportunity for further research arises from the current study. These research opportunities are outlined below.

1. Since the current research is a cross-sectional study which concentrated on a particular time, a longitudinal study that will investigate the antecedent factors that culminate to the adoption decisions of the supermarkets is recommended.
2. Covid-19 is known to have hugely sped up the growth of e-commerce (Koetsier, 2020). Therefore, a comprehensive study on the impact of Covid-19 on the level of application of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarkets is suggested.
3. Given that the data for this research was collected only in Nigerian which limits the generalisation of its findings to supermarkets in other developing countries, there is need

for future research to replicate this study in other developing countries, especially in Africa to broaden the generalisability of the study.

7.8 Chapter summary

This research presents a comprehensive analysis of e-commerce adoption in Nigerian supermarket chains. The study covers not only the influencing factors in the uptake of e-commerce, but also covers the current level of adoption, the benefits of adoption and measures to improve the adoption levels. The study made significant contribution to theory, methods and practice and provided a framework for the stakeholders to improve and sustain the adoption of higher levels of e-commerce in Nigerian retail industry. These stakeholders include the top managers and decision makers in the supermarkets, the government (policy and legislation makers), and the IT consultants and web vendors for the supermarkets. Following a discussion of the study's limitations, recommendations for future research were offered.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A1

Questionnaire Sample

ADOPTION OF E-COMMERCE IN NIGERIAN SUPERMARKETS

Questionnaire

Part One: General Information

Respondent's Position:

Company's location (town/state):

Participant's study code number (for official use):

Company's Profile

Q1) How long has your company been in existence in Nigeria?	Q2) How many branches has your supermarket chain?
<input type="radio"/> Less than one year <input type="radio"/> 1–2 years <input type="radio"/> 3-5 years <input type="radio"/> 6-10 years <input type="radio"/> More than 10 years	<input type="radio"/> Just one <input type="radio"/> 2-3 branches <input type="radio"/> 4-7 branches <input type="radio"/> 8-15 branches <input type="radio"/> More than 15 branches
Q3) How many people work in your supermarket (this branch)?	Q4) What is the total assets of this branch of your supermarket (excluding land)?
<input type="radio"/> Less than 4 people <input type="radio"/> 4-10 people <input type="radio"/> 11-15 people <input type="radio"/> 16-20 people <input type="radio"/> More than 20 people	<input type="radio"/> Less than N5 million <input type="radio"/> N5 million – N10 million <input type="radio"/> N10.1 million – N20 million <input type="radio"/> N20.1 million – N30 million <input type="radio"/> Above N30 million

Respondent's Profile

Q5) Which of the following is the highest level of education you have achieved?	Q6) How old are you?
<input type="radio"/> Below Secondary School Certificate	<input type="radio"/> Below 20 years

<input type="radio"/> Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE) / Ordinary National Diploma (OND) <input type="radio"/> Higher National Diploma (HND) <input type="radio"/> Bachelor's degree <input type="radio"/> Post graduate degree	<input type="radio"/> 20-29 years <input type="radio"/> 30-39 years <input type="radio"/> 40-49 years <input type="radio"/> 50 years and above
Q7) How long have you worked in this company?	Q8) What is your sex?
<input type="radio"/> Less than one year <input type="radio"/> 1- 2 years <input type="radio"/> 3-5 years <input type="radio"/> More than 5 years	<input type="radio"/> Male <input type="radio"/> Female <input type="radio"/> Others

Part Two: Current State of E-Commerce

Q9) Which of the following best describes your current level of e-commerce application? (Please chose one option)

- Our company is not connected to the internet
- Our company is connected to the internet with only e-mail but no website
- Our Company has a static website that presents company's information and advertises its products but without any interactivity
- Our company has an interactive website, that accepts queries, e-mail and form entry from users
- Our company operates online transaction through a website that allows buying and selling as well as customer services
- Our company operates integrated e-commerce. We have a website, that is integrated with suppliers, customers and other back office systems allowing most of the business transactions to be conducted electronically.

Part Three: Benefits of E-Commerce/Attributes of E-commerce

Q10) The following statements relate to your company's viewpoints about relative benefits of using e-commerce. Kindly indicate your extent of agreement or disagreement with these statements by choosing from the numbers that ranges from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Feel free to make additional comment in the space provided.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
a. E-commerce reduces our company's overall operating cost.	1	2	3	4	5
b. E-commerce helps us to expand the market share of our company.	1	2	3	4	5
c. E-commerce helps us to increase our company's customer base.	1	2	3	4	5
d. E-commerce increases our sales and revenues.	1	2	3	4	5
e. E-commerce creates new channel for advertising.	1	2	3	4	5
f. E-commerce enhances our company's image.	1	2	3	4	5
g. E-commerce enhances company's competitive advantage	1	2	3	4	5
h. E-commerce improves customer services and satisfaction.	1	2	3	4	5
i. E-commerce improves business relationship with suppliers	1	2	3	4	5
j. E-commerce helps us to perform our jobs more quickly	1	2	3	4	5
k. E-commerce provides new opportunities	1	2	3	4	5
l. E-commerce reduces our marketing cost	1	2	3	4	5
m. E-commerce allows us to learn more about our competitors	1	2	3	4	5
n. Any other perceived benefit (please list them)					
	1	2	3	4	5
	1	2	3	4	5

Part Four: Factors Affecting E-Commerce Adoption Levels

Kindly indicate your level of agreement or disagreement with the following statements that relate to factors that affect e-commerce adoption levels, by choosing from the numbers that ranges from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
	TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS					
11	Compatibility Issues					
	a. Ecommerce is compatible with our business	1	2	3	4	5
	b. E-commerce is compatible with the IT infrastructure of our company	1	2	3	4	5
	c. E-commerce is compatible with all aspects of our business operations	1	2	3	4	5
	d. E-commerce is compatible with our culture and values	1	2	3	4	5
	e. E-commerce is compatible with our working style	1	2	3	4	5
	ORGANISATIONAL FACTORS					
12	Technology Readiness					
	a. Our company has sufficient experience with network-based application	1	2	3	4	5
	b. Our company has high bandwidth connectivity to the internet	1	2	3	4	5
	c. Our company is well computerized with LAN and WAN	1	2	3	4	5
	d. Our existing systems can be customised to our customers' need	1	2	3	4	5
	e. We have IT support staff in our company	1	2	3	4	5
13	Adoption Cost					
	a. The cost required to set up e-commerce applications in my company is too high for us	1	2	3	4	5
	b. The cost of e-commerce maintenance is high for our company	1	2	3	4	5
	c. Additional cost is required to train staff on e-commerce applications	1	2	3	4	5
	d. Additional cost is required to employ IT support staff	1	2	3	4	5
	e. The cost of steady high-speed internet access is too high for our company	1	2	3	4	5

MANAGERIAL FACTORS						
14	Top Management Support					
	a. I am interested in the use of electronic commerce in our company's operations	1	2	3	4	5
	b. I am willing to provide necessary resources for e-commerce adoption.	1	2	3	4	5
	c. Our company has a clear vision on electronic commerce technologies	1	2	3	4	5
	d. I am willing to accept changes and take the risks associated with e-commerce adoption	1	2	3	4	5
	e. Our CEO is/will be involved in E-commerce adoption and implementation	1	2	3	4	5
15	Personal Knowledge and Attitude towards internet and E-commerce					
	a. I have formal qualification in the use of computer	1	2	3	4	5
	b. I have good understanding of computer applications and internet	1	2	3	4	5
	c. I like to interact with people on the internet	1	2	3	4	5
	d. I have done online shopping before it was introduced in my company	1	2	3	4	5
	e. I believe e-commerce will be adopted in most supermarkets in the country in the near future	1	2	3	4	5
	MARKET ENVIRONMENT FACTORS					
16	Pressure from Market Environment					
	a. Many of our competitors have already adopted e-commerce	1	2	3	4	5
	b. The competition among companies in the supermarket industry is very intense	1	2	3	4	5
	c. We are under pressure from our customers to use e-commerce	1	2	3	4	5
	d. We are under pressure from our suppliers to use e-commerce	1	2	3	4	5
	e. Our partners are demanding the use of e-commerce in doing business with them	1	2	3	4	5
17	Government and Technology Vendor Support					
	a. Existing governmental legislation regarding e-commerce and cyber-crime encourages e-commerce adoption	1	2	3	4	5
	b. The telecommunication infrastructure and availability of internet technology (ADSL, Cable, wireless) in the country encouraged us to adopt e-commerce	1	2	3	4	5
	c. The government provides loan facilities to encourage us to adopt e-commerce	1	2	3	4	5

	d. The vendor provides adequate technical support for e-commerce system	1	2	3	4	5
	e. The vendor provides adequate e-commerce training	1	2	3	4	5
18	Other Factors That Affect Your Ability to Adopt Higher a Level of E-Commerce (Please list them)					
		1	2	3	4	5
		1	2	3	4	5

Adapted from Alrousan (2014) and Rahayu (2015)

Appendix A2

Operationalisation of Constructs

Construct	Label	Measures	Adapted From
		E-commerce Adoption Levels	
Level 0 (Non-Adopter)	LVL0	Our company is not connected to the internet.	Alrousan (2014); Molla and Licker (2004)
Level 1 (e-connectivity)	LVL1	Our company is connected to the internet with only e-mail but no website.	Alrousan (2014); Molla and Licker (2004)
Level 2 (e-window)	LVL2	Our company has a static website that present company's information and advertise its products with one-way communication using e-mail and without any interactivity.	Alrousan (2014); Molla and Licker (2004)
Level 3 (e-interactivity)	LVL3	Our company has an interactive website that accepts online orders, queries, forms, and e-mails from customers and suppliers, but online payment is not integrated on the website.	Alrousan (2014); Molla and Licker (2004)
Level 4 (e-transaction)	LVL4	Our company accepts online transition through website that allows buying and selling of products and services to customers and suppliers including customer services.	Alrousan (2014); Molla and Licker (2004)
Level 5 (e-enterprise)	LVL5	Our company has a website connected with computer systems that allows our company to do the most of business processes such as accounting system, inventory system, CRM, and any traditional paperwork to electronic one.	Alrousan (2014); Molla and Licker (2004)
		ATTRIBUTES OF INNOVATION	
Relative Advantage/ Benefits of E-commerce Adoption	RA1	E-commerce reduces our company's overall operating cost.	Rahayu (2015); Alrousan (2014)
	RA2	E-commerce helps us to expand the market share of our company.	
	RA3	E-commerce helps us to increase our company's customer base.	
	RA4	E-commerce increases our sales and revenues.	
	RA5	E-commerce creates new channel for advertising.	
	RA6	E-commerce enhances our company's image.	
	RA7	E-commerce enhances company's competitive advantage	
	RA8	E-commerce improves customer services and satisfaction.	

	RA9	E-commerce improves business relationship with suppliers	
	RA10	E-commerce helps us to perform our jobs more quickly	
	RA11	E-commerce provides new opportunities	
	RA12	E-commerce reduced our marketing cost	
	RA13	E-commerce allows us to learn more about our competitors	
Compatibility	COMP1	Ecommerce is compatible with our business	Rahayu (2015); Alrousan (2014)
	COMP2	E-commerce is compatible with the IT infrastructure of our company	
	COMP3	E-commerce is compatible with all aspects of our business operations	
	COMP4	E-commerce is compatible with our culture and values	
	COMP5	E-commerce is compatible with our working style	
	COMP1	Ecommerce is compatible with our business	
		ORGANISATIONAL FACTORS	
Technology Readiness	TECR1	Our company has sufficient experience with network-based application	Rahayu (2015)
	TECR2	Our company has high bandwidth connectivity to the internet	
	TECR3	Our company is well computerized with LAN and WAN	
	TECR4	Our existing systems can be customised to our customers' need	
	TECR5	We have IT support staff in our company	
Financial Barriers	FBR1	The cost required to set up e-commerce applications in my company is too high for us	Rahayu (2015); Alrousan (2014); Tan (2010)
	FBR2	The cost of e-commerce maintenance is high for our company	
	FBR3	Additional cost is required to train staff on e-commerce applications	
	FBR4	Additional cost is required to employ IT support staff	
	FBR5	The cost of steady high-speed internet access is too high for our company	
		MANAGERIAL FACTORS	
Top Management Support	TMS1	I am interested in the use of electronic commerce in our company's operations	Alrousan (2014); To and Ngai (2007)
	TMS2	I am willing to provide necessary resources for e-commerce adoption.	
	TMS3	Our company has a clear vision on electronic commerce technologies	
	TMS4	I am not willing to accept changes and take the risks associated with e-commerce adoption	

	TMS5	Our CEO is/will be involved in E-commerce adoption and implementation	
Managers Knowledge and Attitude Towards E-commerce	MKA1	I have formal qualification in the use of computer	Rahayu (2015); Alrousan (2014)
	MKA2	I have good understanding of computer applications and internet	
	MKA3	I like to interact with people on the internet	
	MKA4	I have done online shopping before it was introduced in my company	
	MKA5	I believe e-commerce will be adopted in most supermarkets in the country in the near future	
		ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS	
Market Environment Pressure	MEP1	Many of our competitors have already adopted e-commerce	Rahayu (2015); Alrousan (2014); Ifinedo (2011)
	MEP2	The competition among companies in the supermarket industry is very intense	
	MEP3	We are under pressure from our customers to use e-commerce	
	MEP4	We are under pressure from our suppliers to use e-commerce	
	MEP5	Our partners are demanding the use of e-commerce in doing business with them	
Government and Vendor Support	GVS1	Existing governmental legislation regarding e-commerce and cyber-crime encourages e-commerce adoption	Alrousan (2014); Ifinedo (2011); Tan and Eze (2008)
	GVS2	The telecommunication infrastructure and availability of internet technology (ADSL, Cable, wireless) in the country encouraged us to adopt e-commerce	
	GVS3	The government provides loan facilities to encourage us to adopt e-commerce	
	GVS4	The vendor provides adequate technical support for e-commerce system	
	GVS5	The vendor provides adequate e-commerce training	
		GENERAL INFORMATION	
Company's Profile	CP1	Number of years of operation	Developed by researcher
	CP2	Number of branches	
	CP3	Number of branch employees	
	CP4	Branch's total assets	
Respondent's Profile	RP1	Highest level of education	Developed by researcher
	RP2	Age	
	RP3	Number of years of active service	
	RP4	Sex	

Adapted from Alrousan (2014) and Rahayu (2015)

Appendix A3

Sample of Transcribed Semi-Structured Interview with One of the Participants

ADOPTION OF E-COMMERCE IN NIGERIAN SUPERMARKETS

Interview Session

Study code number (for official use only): 8 (████████)

INTERVIEW PROPER

Interviewer: Thank you once more for the opportunity given to me to interview you for my research.

Respondent: The pleasure is mine

Interviewer: Like I mentioned earlier, I am working on the Adoption of E-commerce in Nigerian Supermarkets.

Respondent: Okay

Interviewer: I also want to appreciate you for allowing me to record the interview. The recording will allow me to extract your responses to my questions without making mistakes.

Respondent: Okay

SECTION A: BACKGROUND (DEMOGRAPHIC) INFORMATION

COMPANY PROFILE

Interviewer: Without wasting much of your time, I would like to ask you few questions about the background of your company. I know this branch is located in Lagos. How long has your company been in operation in Nigeria?

Respondent: Ok, So, my name is ██████████. I am the accountant of ██████████ ██████████. ██████████ is the brand name here in Nigeria, but in our home country, in South Africa, that is the registered business name. So, when the business came to Nigeria in 2005, we started our operations in December 2005. When the company came down to Nigeria, because of some other companies that have already chosen that type of name with Corporate Affairs Commission, we were unable to register as ██████████. So, the registered name is ██████████, but the brand name is ██████████. People know us as ██████████.

Interviewer: So, people know you as ██████████?

Respondent: Yes. So, we operate under a franchise agreement with the [REDACTED] in South Africa, you know, just like the MTN and the other multinational companies that are operating here. So, the first store was opened in 2005. That's the store down there ([REDACTED]).

Interviewer: So, this is the head office?

Respondent: Yes, this is the head office. So, the store is down there by Entrance One. Presently, we have 25 stores in Nigeria. We have eight here in Lagos, we have one in Ogun state, we have five in Abuja, we have one in Kano, we have one in Onitsha, one in Owerri, one in Umuahia, one in Asaba, one in Warri, we have two in Ibadan, we have one in Akure. That should be all.

Interviewer: That's a lot of branches

Respondent: We should have even done more than that if not for the current economic situation in the country. Ordinarily, we are supposed to be on like 65 by the end of 2020, but because of the economic situation in Nigeria, the home office decided to step down the level of expansion for now. May be, by next year, we'll start again.

Interviewer: Thank you so much for that response.

Respondent: You are welcome.

Interviewer: I would also like to ask you about the estimate number of employees you have in this very branch.

Respondent: In this branch we should have about 200, both direct and indirect.

Interviewer: Thank you so much. Can you also give me the estimate for total number of your staff?

Respondent: For total, we should have more than 5000.

Interviewer: Okay. Can you also give me an estimate of your total assets for this branch, excluding land and building?

Respondent: The thing is that in everywhere our store is located, we rent the space. We don't own the mall. Some people will build the mall, we just come and rent a space there. But we always happen to be the anchor tenant in every mall. When people are coming to the mall, they rather than saying I am going to the palms, they will say I am going to [REDACTED]. So, most times people believe we own the mall. No, we are just the anchor tenant. So, if you are talking about

assets, it should just be the furniture and fittings, and computer equipment in each store. So, for this particular store, the asset is around 4 million USD, including the goods.

Interviewer: Alright. Thank you so much. I wouldn't want to bother you with the total estimate asset for all the branches.

Respondent: Hmmm, that will be quite huge.

Interviewer: Okay. Let me not bother you about that. Thank you so much.

Respondent: You are welcome

RESPONDENT PROFILE

Interviewer: Let's talk about yourself. You have given me the background of the company. Can we just get your background? I know you have already told me your name. If you don't mind, can you please confirm your sex, your age bracket, and your position?

Respondent: Okay. I'm male. My age bracket is between 40 and 45, and I am the accountant.

Interviewer: Is it the overall accountant or for this branch?

Respondent: I'm the overall [REDACTED] Nigeria accountant. Because we run the central operation. The head office oversees what happens in the stores. If there is any issue in the stores, they refer back to us for confirmation.

Interviewer: Okay. I guess the store downstairs is the first store in the country and is more like the head office. Isn't it?

Respondent: Yes, it is.

Interviewer: Thank you. And how long have you worked in the company?

Respondent: This is my sixth year. I joined [REDACTED] in 2014.

Interviewer: So, [REDACTED] started in Nigeria in 2005, and you joined in 2014?

Respondent: Yes.

Interviewer: If you don't mind answering this question, can you tell me your highest academic qualification? You don't have to answer the question if you are not comfortable with it.

Respondent: I have HND in Accountancy, and I am as well a Chartered Accountant. I'm a member of ICAN (Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria) which is a professional accountancy body with a regulatory authority in Nigeria.

Interviewer: Thank you.

SECTION B: LEVEL OF E-COMMERCE APPLICATION (Note: The respondent also discussed some benefits here)

Interviewer: Let us now go to the main questions for the research

Respondent: Okay

Interviewer: Let's talk about the extent of your e-commerce application. How much of e-commerce do you apply in your company? You know, there are different levels of e-commerce application. Some companies have just an e-mail address, some have static website which is uninteractive, some have interactive websites where you can make queries and stuff like that, and make orders. Some have a full-blown e-commerce, operating a normal e-commerce where you can do transactions, you can buy and pay online.

Respondent: Okay. So, for [REDACTED], presently, we dwell so much on brick and mortar aspect of the business. What this means is that we do majorly the physical location. On e-commerce aspects, what we have that is a little bit relevant to that is our website. We have a website: [REDACTED].

Interviewer: Is the website interactive?

Respondent: Definitely yes. So, on that website, we throw out information about our products; new products or just to promote existing ones. Then, we give information about discounts and if there is any marked down items that are not moving, we give the information to the customers, and at any point in time we do promos, like we say, if you buy this quantity, you get this much as a freebie. So, people normally go to the internet, I mean to the website and also on social media. We are on Facebook, and also on Instagram, where people always go to get information about our products, and they make comments on their expectations from the organisation, what they feel. Also, we get criticisms from there to know what we are not doing right that we need to improve on. So, all this information we use to further develop the business.

Interviewer: So, it's more like you accept queries on the website?

Respondent: Yes

Interviewer: Okay. So, we can say that you have an interactive website which accepts queries, and you have an e-mail, and the website also allows data entering from users, and is also used for customer service issues, but you don't operate online transactions like buying and selling online?

Respondent: That's correct.

Interviewer: Okay. Thank you so much.

Respondent: You are welcome.

SECTION C: BENEFITS OF E-COMMERCE APPLICATION (Note: The participant discussed the factors and few benefits in this section)

Interviewer: Another question I would like to ask you is about the benefits of e-commerce. Considering your level of e-commerce, what are the benefits of e-commerce, both the ones you are currently enjoying and the ones you think you can enjoy if you adopt higher levels of e-commerce?

Respondent: When [REDACTED] started operations, at that point in time we were like trailblazers in the retail industry, because in the 1970s and 1980s, we had shops like Leventis, we had shops like, all these franchise companies then of which many of them went under due to one reason or the other. So, by the time we came, we are the ones that revived the retail industry. And, by that time, there was not much competition. There was nothing like SPAR, like Hubmart, like GAME. None of them was around then. But, 15 years down the line, from where we started to where we are now, we see a lot of competitions coming up. That's on the brick and mortars side. Then on the e-commerce side, full e-commerce aspects, we have companies like Jumia and Konga. So, now, we know that they have been taking some chunk of the business. Let's take for instance, last time I was in the US, there are sometimes you can sit at the comfort of your home and order food, and they will send it down to your house. You don't even need to move from where you are. So, people are tilting, one way or the other, towards that side. But, from our own side as a business, we run the model that is similar or that is the same to what is obtainable in every [REDACTED] location anywhere that we are. So anywhere we operate, whether you go to Rwanda, or you go to Angola, or you go to South Africa itself, whatever you see here should be what you will get there. So, we don't want a situation whereby someone will come here, and then they will have a major complaint that will get to our home office, and they would say we have deviated from the line of business. So, if there will be any migration or any

incursion made by us to the e-commerce itself, it has to cascade down from the home office to us. So, they are not practicing it there now. I think they wanted to start sometime, about last year or two years ago, they wanted to do a pilot in some locations to see how it will work for them, before they will replicate it in other locations, and one major thing the company is guarding against is product traceability. You know, if anybody buys may be a clipper from [REDACTED] and they deliver it to your house. Anything could happen to the product along the way. We won't put a bad product on our shelves. But it might get your house, and it won't work. And somebody, who is not patient enough will just go to the social media and say [REDACTED] is selling substandard items, and then the brand name itself will be impacted. So, the company is trying to guard against such occurrences whereby, when you get that issue, you won't say it is [REDACTED]. It can be from the manufacturer itself. We don't have that capacity yet to manage all the e-commerce-related issues when they occur. That's why we prefer that you come to the store, you can come back to the store if you have any issue, because if you order from our site, it can be sent from any of the stores. But if you come to any particular store and buy, with your receipt, we will be able to know where you got this from and you will be able to get a replacement for that. So, that's why the company is delaying or drawing back a little bit from going into full-blown e-commerce.

Interviewer: It seems you have been discussing the factors affecting your e-commerce application level?

Respondent: Yes.

Interviewer: You remember my question was the benefits?

Respondent: Okay. So, the benefits itself could be, the fact we are the leader in the industry, so, if we could add full e-commerce to the business, it will give us more leverage over companies within the retail industry. People have so much faith in our products. So, they know that they can always get the best at the lowest prices. So, the benefit will be of an immense magnitude to us if we go into advanced e-commerce.

Interviewer: Thank you so much. I know, you have discussed the factors that affect your e-commerce application level when I asked about the about benefits. Are there any other influencing factors you would like to discuss?

Respondent: No. Those are the major factors.

Interviewer: Okay. Thanks.

SECTION D: FACTORS AFFECTING THE LEVEL OF E-COMMERCE APPLICATION (Note: The respondent already discussed factors within the benefits)

SECTION E: MEASURES TO IMPROVE E-COMMERCE APPLICATION AND SUSTAINABILITY IN NIGERIAN SUPERMARKETS

Interviewer: One of the objectives of this research is to develop a model to enhance the adoption and continued use of e-commerce in Nigerian supermarkets. What are the things you think could be done or put in place to facilitate the adoption and sustainability of higher levels of e-commerce by the supermarkets?

Respondent: So, what I personally believe is that whatever will guarantee the customer's trust in your products, in your business, and whatever will ensure efficient customer service. I said that based on the experience I mentioned earlier in the US. The person I stayed with in the US happened to be someone that does deliveries. There was a time I went out together with him as I didn't want to be bored at home. So, he moved from one place to another and picked from the stores or from fast food restaurants and take them to the customers. You know, here in Africa, we have a lot of distrust. Somebody would have said, "maybe they have tampered with the food on the way, or something could have happened". So, we have had instances where somebody will buy food from our store here, they will get home, and they will tell you that they consumed that food, and something happened to them. You know, also when we are sure that it might not be from our side, the food might have been contaminated when you got home. So, anything that can guarantee a customer to trust in your product, and say that whatever I get from you, or whatever I order from your site, or may be through a phone call or sending mail, I will get the actual value of what I am paying for. Then if any issue comes up, a solution that will ensure that the customer is well protected and well compensated at the end of day. You know, customer is king. If you open a supermarket and no customer is coming, there is nothing you can do. What will guarantee that customer is happy at the end of the day, that is what I believe that e-commerce will focus more on. Such that if there is any issue or controversy, it will quickly be rectified and the customer will be satisfied.

Interviewer: Okay. Thank you so much for your time. I also appreciate your allowing me to record the interview. I can assure you that every data you have provided to me will be treated anonymously and with strictest confidence in the report. Your company's name will not be mentioned anywhere in the report that will result from this research, and your name will not be

mentioned anywhere. Although, I may keep record of the name, but it will not be mentioned anywhere in the report. Thank you once more for your time.

Respondent: You are welcome.

Interviewer: You already have a soft copy of the participants information sheet for this research. I will also leave a hard copy for you. Feel free to contact me anytime if you have any concern about the research or you want to change any part of the information you provided.

Respondent: Okay. Thanks.

APPENDIX A4

List of 21 Supermarket Chains Considered for Data Collection

S/N	Supermarket Name
1	Shoprite
2	Spar
3	Chanrai's Supermarket and Departmental Store
4	DePrince Supermarkets
5	Escapade Supermarket
6	Everyday Supermarket
7	FoodCo Supermarkets
8	Game Stores
9	Goodies
10	Hubmart stores
11	Justrite Superstore Limited
12	Jara Superstore
13	Marketsquare Supermarkets
14	Blenco Supermarket
15	Next Cash N Carry
16	CCD Superstores
17	Prince Ebeano Supermarkets
18	Addide Supermarket
19	Ceci Supermarket
20	Yem-Yem Supermarkets
21	Roban Stores

Source: Selected from the sample frame

Appendix B1

Mahalanobis Distance X^2

Case Number	Mah. Dist.	P value	Case Number	Mah. Dist.	P value	Case Number	Mah. Dist.	P value
1	51.61022	0.33458	58	55.95814	0.20089	114	47.96632	0.47422
3	79.70264	0.00273	59	53.32968	0.27675	115	43.58398	0.6542
4	48.4167	0.45602	60	58.9584	0.13349	116	48.58397	0.44931
5	62.33799	0.07997	61	72.88118	0.01177	117	29.69188	0.9825
6	39.57683	0.80142	62	52.62129	0.29983	118	44.19055	0.62969
7	40.97706	0.75367	63	57.94885	0.15394	119	71.07606	0.01686
8	55.98176	0.20028	64	48.94128	0.43508	120	52.74374	0.29576
9	39.56924	0.80166	65	49.24109	0.42326	121	49.50085	0.41311
10	83.86425	0.00104	66	66.57318	0.03912	122	58.1687	0.1493
11	54.45358	0.24239	67	61.83992	0.08653	123	70.15329	0.02017
12	46.54948	0.53239	68	14.38855	1	124	66.55858	0.03923
13	73.02911	0.01143	69	23.07822	0.99912	125	51.27961	0.34638
14	33.94357	0.9376	70	16.12836	1	126	42.33852	0.70314
15	60.04368	0.1139	71	54.6435	0.23686	127	35.61472	0.9071
16	62.1998	0.08174	72	53.82306	0.26131	128	60.11241	0.11274
17	21.13962	0.99973	73	38.7112	0.82841	129	17.70628	0.99998
18	16.03874	1	74	54.09818	0.25295	130	32.93711	0.95214
19	47.43692	0.49582	75	56.68981	0.18259	131	51.03574	0.35521
20	61.98293	0.0846	76	52.54482	0.30238	132	52.44841	0.30562
21	38.84099	0.8245	77	91.56889	0.00015	133	44.16241	0.63083
22	63.78655	0.06317	78	62.38236	0.0794	134	83.8763	0.00104
23	36.3982	0.88993	79	67.4923	0.03317	135	41.73995	0.72579
24	51.35662	0.34361	80	23.87385	0.99862	136	65.19444	0.0498
25	43.61199	0.65307	81	45.62992	0.57048	137	34.31423	0.93154
26	38.86019	0.82391	82	54.55429	0.23945	138	37.12455	0.87234
27	25.34671	0.99708	83	52.87708	0.29137	139	31.67309	0.96671
28	49.92657	0.39668	84	54.72249	0.23459	140	39.8479	0.79255
29	56.42078	0.18917	85	39.26962	0.81123	141	50.23066	0.38511
30	60.00042	0.11464	86	34.89831	0.92118	142	65.53356	0.04696
31	32.7955	0.95397	87	47.51709	0.49254	143	60.49672	0.10643
32	46.16893	0.54815	88	33.34795	0.94654	144	41.7437	0.72565
33	47.26919	0.5027	89	36.21646	0.89408	145	42.78327	0.68591
34	59.22256	0.1285	90	43.70665	0.64927	146	49.83672	0.40013
35	34.83643	0.92233	91	57.21088	0.1703	147	37.99858	0.84906
36	21.95801	0.99955	92	48.47872	0.45353	148	59.43177	0.12465
37	42.1667	0.70971	93	35.39731	0.91154	149	52.99615	0.28748
38	68.84102	0.02587	94	35.51208	0.90921	150	79.42561	0.00291
39	28.77977	0.98741	95	62.82519	0.07395	151	28.95749	0.98655
40	32.61926	0.95618	96	45.57944	0.57257	152	29.45121	0.98392

41	33.26251	0.94774	97	47.91401	0.47634	153	29.87314	0.98136
42	37.62044	0.85941	98	70.37216	0.01934	154	47.55483	0.49099
43	48.03728	0.47134	99	53.92969	0.25805	155	30.05207	0.98019
44	50.13054	0.38891	100	68.51074	0.02751	156	22.76671	0.99926
45	47.99677	0.47298	101	51.45505	0.34009	157	27.01322	0.99378
46	46.73364	0.52478	103	66.11096	0.04246	158	36.14424	0.8957
47	65.92966	0.04383	104	51.38439	0.34261	159	29.72318	0.98231
48	15.07437	1	104	46.07436	0.55207	160	21.59444	0.99964
49	44.84471	0.60291	105	39.53523	0.80276	161	30.11341	0.97977
50	47.50808	0.4929	106	44.69237	0.60917	162	52.36829	0.30833
51	44.8634	0.60214	107	49.16423	0.42628	163	47.01291	0.51325
52	53.76338	0.26315	108	39.0541	0.81796	164	43.98858	0.63789
53	67.25192	0.03464	109	40.57862	0.76773	165	60.80538	0.10156
54	58.73964	0.13774	110	72.11047	0.01375	166	45.31768	0.5834
55	25.85624	0.99628	111	49.02292	0.43185	167	51.65432	0.33302
56	19.72488	0.9999	112	65.02206	0.05129	168	43.58593	0.65412
57	54.10926	0.25261	113	56.02445	0.19918			

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Appendix B-2

Factor Analysis Results

Table B2.1: Initial result for Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
RA2	1.00	.669
RA3	1.00	.760
RA4	1.00	.774
RA5	1.00	.759
RA6	1.00	.753
RA7	1.00	.772
RA8	1.00	.736
RA11	1.00	.443
RA13	1.00	.518
COMP1	1.00	.807
COMP2	1.00	.764
COMP3	1.00	.751
COMP4	1.00	.696
COMP5	1.00	.732
TECR1	1.00	.790
TECR2	1.00	.739
TECR3	1.00	.902
TECR4	1.00	.837
TECR5	1.00	.773
FBR1	1.00	.900
FBR2	1.00	.613
FBR3	1.00	.739
FBR4	1.00	.730
FBR5	1.00	.591
TMS1	1.00	.586
TMS2	1.00	.705
TMS3	1.00	.802
TMS4	1.00	.817
TMS5	1.00	.709
MKA1	1.00	.755
MKA2	1.00	.820
MKA5	1.00	.741
MEP3	1.00	.677
MEP4	1.00	.836
MEP5	1.00	.828
GVS1	1.00	.715
GVS2	1.00	.731

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table B2.2: Initial result for total variance explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	13.585	36.717	36.717	13.585	36.717	36.717
2	3.602	9.736	46.452	3.602	9.736	46.452
3	2.473	6.683	53.135	2.473	6.683	53.135
4	2.198	5.939	59.075	2.198	5.939	59.075
5	1.550	4.189	63.264	1.550	4.189	63.264
6	1.370	3.703	66.967	1.370	3.703	66.967
7	1.353	3.656	70.623	1.353	3.656	70.623
8	1.141	3.083	73.706	1.141	3.083	73.706
9	.858	2.318	76.024			
10	.780	2.108	78.132			
11	.756	2.043	80.174			
12	.674	1.822	81.996			
13	.573	1.548	83.544			
14	.540	1.459	85.003			
15	.509	1.377	86.379			
16	.457	1.235	87.614			
17	.427	1.155	88.769			
18	.380	1.026	89.795			
19	.358	.969	90.764			
20	.323	.873	91.637			
21	.314	.850	92.487			
22	.305	.823	93.310			
23	.268	.725	94.035			
24	.250	.675	94.710			
25	.246	.664	95.374			
26	.211	.571	95.945			
27	.198	.534	96.479			
28	.186	.502	96.981			
29	.182	.492	97.473			
30	.180	.485	97.959			
31	.151	.408	98.367			
32	.145	.391	98.758			
33	.120	.323	99.081			
34	.109	.294	99.375			
35	.091	.247	99.622			
36	.088	.238	99.860			
37	.052	.140	100.000			

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Figure B2.1: Initial Scree plot

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Figure B2.2: Third (final) scree plot

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Table B2.3: Second Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix ^a							
	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
RA2	.721						
RA3	.802						
RA4	.832						
RA5	.837						
RA6	.840						
RA7	.810						
RA8	.821						
COMP1			.821				
COMP2			.801				
COMP3			.743				
COMP4			.621				
COMP5		.525	.570				
TECR1				.761			
TECR2				.709			
TECR4				.786			
TECR5				.818			
TMS1		.637					
TMS2		.730					
TMS3		.740					
TMS4		.811					
TMS5		.719					
MKA1						.828	
MKA2						.872	
MKA5						.738	
MEP3					.802		
MEP4					.895		
MEP5					.901		
GVS1							.860
GVS2							.847

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis

Appendix B-3

Multinomial Logistic Regression Result

Table B3.1: Parameter estimates with e-interactivity as reference category

E-commerce Adoption Levels ^a		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
								Lower Bound	Upper Bound
E-transaction	Intercept	-11.645	3.431	11.517	1	0.001			
	RA	8.644	2.881	8.999	1	0.003	5675.792	20.012	1.610E+06
	COMP	5.970	1.875	10.143	1	0.001	391.565	9.934	15434.019
	TECR	3.725	1.205	9.547	1	0.002	41.461	3.904	440.295
	TMS	4.783	1.338	12.781	1	0.000	119.414	8.676	1643.495
	MKA	4.933	1.526	10.444	1	0.001	138.758	6.966	2763.818
	MEP	1.455	0.786	3.433	1	0.064	4.287	0.919	19.988
	GVS	1.956	0.641	9.302	1	0.002	7.069	2.012	24.841
E-enterprise	Intercept	-14.207	5.261	7.292	1	0.007			
	RA	6.577	3.827	2.953	1	0.086	718.236	0.397	1.299E+06
	COMP	4.471	2.488	3.228	1	0.072	87.412	0.666	11470.317
	TECR	5.283	2.853	3.428	1	0.064	196.901	0.734	52819.041
	TMS	5.585	2.015	7.682	1	0.006	266.321	5.133	13819.024
	MKA	3.780	2.085	3.286	1	0.070	43.799	0.736	2608.131
	MEP	0.355	0.959	0.137	1	0.711	1.426	0.218	9.339
	GVS	3.391	1.272	7.109	1	0.008	29.682	2.455	358.842

a. The reference category is E-interactivity

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis